

OPENMed

Opening up Education in South-Mediterranean Countries

A Compendium of Case Studies and Interviews
with Experts about Open Education Practices and Resources

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Opening up Education in South-Mediterranean Countries

A Compendium of Case Studies and Interviews with Experts
about Open Educational Practices and Resources

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Université Ibn Zohr
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Palestine

Association of Arab Universities
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Associate Partner

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Princess Sumaya University for
Technology Jordan

European Distance and
E-Learning Network UK

Executive Summary

OpenMed is an international cooperation project co-funded by the Erasmus+ Capacity Building in HE programme¹ of the European Union during the period 15 October 2015 – 14 October 2018 involving five partners from Europe and nine from South-Mediterranean (S-M) countries (Egypt, Jordan, Morocco, and Palestine).

The overarching goal of OpenMed is to raise awareness and facilitate the adoption of Open Educational Practices (OEP) and Open Educational Resources (OER) in the S-M countries, with a particular focus on Higher Education (HE) in Egypt, Jordan, Morocco and Palestine. OpenMed fosters the role of universities as knowledge providers not only to their on-campus students but also beyond the walls of institutions, especially towards disadvantaged groups (e.g. low-income people, disabled students, people living in rural areas, learners at risk of low achievement, and refugees).

Work Package One (WP1) of the project, led by the OER Research Team at Coventry University, has involved a review of Open Educational Practices and is the focus of this compendium. A survey is included outlining the level of participation in Open Educational Practices (OEP) within the partner institutions, to capture current practice at the time of completion (early 2016), and also to identify the future goals of the participating institutions.

Eleven case study initiatives of current practices in Open Education (OE) globally, and particularly in the S-M region, are presented. The focus of the compendium is to generate a reliable and evidence-based body of knowledge on OEP in the region to inform the subsequent phases and work packages of the project.

¹<http://eacea.ec.europa.eu/erasmus-plus/actions/key-action-2-cooperation-for-innovation-and-exchange-good-practices>

The main findings from across the case study initiatives have been considered under five themes:

- Top–Down and Bottom–Up Implementation
- Supporting Staff in Using and Integrating Open Practices and Open Resources
- Collaborative Creation in Communities of Practice
- Enhancing the Quality of Student Learning
- Licensing of OER Content.

Each theme is represented with key recommendations for the next phases of OpenMed, as outlined below.

Outline of Key Recommendations:

Top–Down and Bottom–Up Implementation:

- Clarity about the justification for the provision of high–quality OEP and OER in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) is required
- Investment in infrastructure will ease process development and ways to transition materials and programmes
- Institutions should organize themselves according to local need
- Piloting course accreditation schemes through institutions may be a useful means of promoting OEP as a reputable form of learning, where national educational authorities do not recognize online education
- Building on and using what is already out there is an important premise of OEP/OER
- Resources are required to support the upskilling of staff.

Supporting Staff in Using and Integrating Open Practices and Open Resources:

- Staff need to be supported to problem–solve ways to integrate OER with their official academic learning resources
- Staff need to appreciate that openness has to go far beyond making content publicly available

- Staff development needs should be prioritized
- Incentives are required to engage staff
- The effort and focus required for staff to work effectively in a digital world needs to be better acknowledged.

Collaborative Creation in Communities of Practice:

- A collaborative approach to the creation of OER needs to be adopted
- If the level of expertise is not available in the institution, or if people in the institution are reluctant to adopt OER, OER advocates should collaborate outside of the institution
- The potential of Open Education to have greater impact can be realized when a consortium of institutions collaborate together rather than something happening within just one institution
- Learning resources, context related, can help to raise the profile of scholarship occurring in the S–M region to inspire and evoke further sharing, collaboration and social commitment.

Enhancing the Quality of Student Learning:

- Important opportunities for saving money are achievable through developing non–commercial OER while still using high quality content
- OER can support anytime, anywhere learning, offering new communication models and possibilities between teachers and students
- OEP should engage students as co–creators
- Issues of quality need to be carefully considered and managed
- OER need to be accessible to meet a wide range of learner needs including students with learning disabilities
- Understanding how computer–mediated communication works, including how we connect with each other and build trust within networks, is required for effective online intercultural exchange.

Licensing of OER Content:

- Those providing OER should review their licensing approach

and work with their institutions, where possible, to formulate guidelines for OER creators.

- Further detailed discussion of these recommendations is available in Sections Nine and Ten.

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Acronyms

CC	Creative Commons
HE	Higher Education
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IR	Institutional Repository
LMS	Learning Management System
MENA	Middle East and North Africa Region
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
OA	Open Access
OE	Open Education
OEP	Open Educational Practices
OER	Open Educational Resources
S–M	South Mediterranean

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Introduction to the OpenMed Project

OpenMed

Introduction to the OpenMed Project

By Marcello Scalisi, Director, UNIMED

In October 2016 the Mediterranean Universities Union (UNIMED), celebrated its 25-year anniversary. Since 1991 UNIMED has implemented cooperation projects among universities of the two shores of the Mediterranean in several subject areas including cultural heritage, renewable energies, journalism, water, management of international relations, and many other topics. Further, UNIMED has organized several cultural and political initiatives, events and meetings for the benefits of its members and non-members, aimed at promoting Euro-Mediterranean dialogue.

UNIMED has been able to achieve this work through the cooperation and collaboration of scientific and academic communities living and working in the Mediterranean region. The Mediterranean university community, populated by students, teachers and researchers, plays a pivotal role in providing important contributions and in building bridges between respective cultures. UNIMED promotes messages of unity and educational cooperation towards all its associated universities, in order that the extraordinary value of cultural and scientific knowledge can be better used and mobilized to give voice to the needs of young people in Mediterranean society.

Within this framework, and the continuous aim for collaboration and enhancement of sharing and networking opportunities, Open Education (OE) assumes a crucial and essential role. Due to the typical top-down governing systems of universities in S-M countries there has been an often-timid participation of university institutions in relation to OE practices. The OpenMed project seeks to transform and support all universities across the Mediterranean region to contribute to the democratization of knowledge. The OpenMed project, focused on a bottom-up approach to OE, aims to ensure that the Mediterranean

university systems are better integrated in the dimension of global academic and scientific cooperation, the latter being an essential factor in the integration of Mediterranean communities and economies. Further, over time, OpenMed can impact upon the current political processes which limit the ambition of institutional OE practices. In this context, OE is a way to give back to universities their awareness of their role in society, not only through the use of open practices, licenses, and open education contents, but also by providing the skills and tools required for promoting active dialogue and participation in our knowledge (sharing) society.

By Cristina Stefanelli, OpenMed Project Manager, UNIMED

Why OpenMed?

The provision of equal opportunities for access to education are acknowledged not only as core conditions for the success of the 2011 EU Modernization Agenda and the broader Lisbon Strategy, but as a wider move towards the role of a knowledge-based society in fostering social inclusion and social cohesion.

Openness in HE seems a common sense approach for enabling equal and democratic access to knowledge. If universities really want to find more resources to invest in better teaching and research, it is essential that the open sharing of resources is encouraged. Knowledge must be shared and spread, teachers inspired to network and collaborate on course development, and institutions discouraged from fragmentation and a silo mentality.

Before this can be realized, we need a change in attitudes towards what we mean by education, teaching and learning. We need new attitudes towards collaboration and new literacy.

The resistance to embrace institutional changes, the mistrust of exchanging educational content and syllabus, or the poor adoption of new learning environments are major constraints in HE institutions in S-M countries. Most universities are still locked into conventional strategies, and the evolution of tertiary education systems raises questions about the equity of access and outcomes. The mismatch

between the current knowledge based society and refereed inflexible teaching practices demands an entirely new *modus operandi* regarding how content in HE is created, combined, updated and delivered.

An enormous amount of OER are already available but because of limited awareness of their existence, or the lack of specific knowledge on how to localize and integrate them into actual practices of learning and curricula, including the necessary open strategies within HE endorsed at managerial level, with staff incentives, this rich worldwide knowledge–sharing potential remains underused. Education policies and initiatives that combine infrastructure investment with a coherent and localized “open” approach to content are the most likely to have a significant positive impact and to realize a more inclusive education capable of inserting the learner into the knowledge society. Stimulating supply and demand for high–quality OER is essential for modernizing education.

OER is part of a larger trend towards openness in HE and democratization of access; it is a means to open up the curriculum to knowledge, materials and teaching methods from all over the world. The two most important aspects of openness have to do with free availability over the internet and as few restrictions as possible on the use of the resource. There should be no technical barriers (undisclosed source code), no price barriers (subscriptions, licensing fees, pay–per–view fees) and as few legal permission barriers as possible (copyright and licensing restrictions) for the end user.

Obviously teachers and learners need a substantial knowledge base and a clear concept of quality in education. It is not sufficient to simply “Google” their knowledge, nor is being born in a digital era reason enough to assume digital fluency. What matters more is the capacity to learn throughout their lives, to think, research, find information, and to adopt sustainable educational practices to open up flexible learning pathways, which can expose learners to international approaches and internationally–minded educators, with the many benefits this offers in terms of social externalities.

Opening up Education in South Mediterranean countries

How do OEP and OER co-exist in HE strategies and instructional materials in the S–M world? How are universities rethinking their mission, cost structure, international partnerships and learning experiences?

OpenMed “Opening up education in South Mediterranean countries” explores the adoption of strategies and channels that embrace the principles of openness and reusability within the context of S–M universities.

The overarching goal of OpenMed is to raise awareness and facilitate the adoption of OER and OEP in S–M countries, with a particular focus on HE in Egypt, Jordan, Morocco and Palestine. OpenMed fosters the role of universities as knowledge providers not only to their on-campus students but also beyond the walls of institutions, especially towards disadvantaged groups (e.g. low-income peoples, disabled students, people living in rural areas, learners at risk of low achievement, and refugees).

OpenMed envisions a multilevel and organic intervention, which articulates three key dimensions:

- Content and practices: understood as educational resources and learning experiences which are openly and freely available, promoting their continuing re-usability, replication, updating, and sharing;
- Platforms: hardware and software designed to simplify the interoperability of the resources, facilitating semantic structures (improving its findability) and the use of open standards and open source software that decreased its costs and trigger its adoption;
- Cultural aspects: promoting awareness of OEP and OER, explaining the value of openness, describing the educational and also the inter-institutional benefits, and not only identifying best practices, but implementing the incentives required to foster these practices in a variety of teaching-learning environments.

OpenMed is structured in three main phases: review of OEP, widening participation in OER, and training of trainers.

Figure 1: The road ahead in the OpenMed Project

The review of OEP focuses on a case analysis of current practices in open education globally and in particular the S–M region. It generates a reliable and evidence–based body of knowledge on OER in the region.

Widening participation to HE by means of OER adoption is a strategic priority for the HE sector in general and for the OER movement. Widening participation will be achieved by increasing HE engagement with OEP and involving key stakeholders from HEIs in the definition of the Regional Agenda of Open Education, i.e. a long–term common strategy for opening up education in S–M countries. The Regional Agenda will serve as a guideline for the definition of institutional roadmaps, i.e. short–term action plans for the implementation of OEP at the local/institutional level.

The initiative also includes a training of trainers component. An OER blended training course will be designed and delivered to university

educators to build capacity to make use of OER and to start up OEPs relevant to the educational ecosystem.

As a long term impact, OpenMed will increase OER adoption in the S–M countries, fostering the role of universities as knowledge providers.

Opening up education can truly change HE and make it better, accessible, and more relevant. Sharing information about OER initiatives can inspire others to reflect, develop their own initiatives, make connections, celebrate diversity, and work together to defend education as a public good and a basic human right.

About the OpenMed Project and the Review of Open Education Practices

HOW

About the OpenMed Project and the Review of Open Education Practices

Overview of the Project

OpenMed is an international cooperation project co-funded by the **Erasmus+ Capacity Building in HE programme**² of the European Union during the period 15 October 2015 – 14 October 2018 involving five partners from Europe (Italy, Spain and the UK) and nine from S–M Countries (**Egypt, Jordan, Morocco, and Palestine**).

The project will offer the possibility to other universities from Egypt, Jordan, Morocco, and Palestine or any other S–M country to join the action as *community partners* and it explores the adoption of strategies and channels that embrace the principles of openness and reusability within the context of S–M universities.

Aim of the Project

The overarching goal of OpenMed is to raise awareness and facilitate the adoption of OEP, with a particular emphasis on the use and production of OER, at universities in Egypt, Jordan, Morocco, Palestine and other countries in the S–M region.

OpenMed fosters the role of universities as knowledge providers not only to their traditional campus-based students, but also to learners outside their institution, particularly those who have reduced or limited access to education due to reasons such as poverty, disability, or relocation.

²<http://eacea.ec.europa.eu/erasmus-plus/actions/key-action-2-cooperation-for-innovation-and-exchange-good-practices>

The specific objectives of the project are to:

- Raise awareness and widen HEI participation in OEP and OER;
- Define the OER Agenda for the re-use of OER at HE institutional level;
- Define mid-term strategic roadmaps for the implementation of the OER Agenda at local-institutional level according to the local, cultural and institutional needs and strategies;
- Instruct university teachers about how to use and repurpose OER in a pedagogically-rich context and improve their digital competences;
- Pilot start-up OEP and offer students flexible and up-to-date open contents and learning paths, with a linkage to the international community and the needs of the job market.

We hope this document will inspire the creation and implementation of new OER initiatives in S-M countries and beyond, enabling the sharing of content and pedagogical practices both regionally and internationally.

Introduction to the Compilation of the Case Studies

The first OpenMed work package has involved gathering and analyzing data to inform the subsequent work packages of the project and ultimately aims to facilitate the adoption of OEP at the partners in the S-M region, other universities in each of their respective countries and, more broadly, at other HE organizations in the Arab World.

The role of this compendium is to provide inspiration and insight into the current practices around OER and OEP, in the S-M region and beyond.

It is also to promote reflection and discussion about current practices and priorities for change for OpenMed.

This compendium of relevant initiatives and interviews with experts aims to help partners achieve the objectives of OpenMed by generating a reliable and evidence-based body of knowledge. The

compendium includes written outputs, published as a report, and video content, released through the OpenMed website and online video platforms.

Methodology

The methodology used to collect the case study information was descriptive case study involving detailed, in–depth data collection involving multiple sources of information. The topic of the cases is Open Education (OE) and its practice within HEIs in the S–M partner region, the EU, and other areas of the world.

Webometric Analysis

At the start of the project, a webometric analysis was undertaken to assess the level of awareness of OE and OER in HE institutions in OpenMed partner countries: Egypt, Jordan, Morocco, and Palestine. The analysis searched for key terms associated with OE on HEI websites.

OEP Participation Survey

Participating HEIs in the OpenMed project were asked to complete an online survey to outline the level of participation in OEP within their institution.

Case Studies

All OpenMed partners were invited to nominate relevant initiatives, from their institution or elsewhere, to be considered for inclusion in a collection of OE case studies. Partners were asked to justify why and how they think a case study of the nominated initiative could help to advance the adoption of OEP in the S–M region.

The criteria for the selection of case studies was:

1. Potential of the initiative for transferability to other contexts within the South Mediterranean region
2. Extent of the initiative to offer valuable insights into the following aspects:

- Organizational changes
- Pedagogical innovations
- Funding model
- Strategic planning
- Incentives for engagement of educators
- Quality assurance mechanisms
- Assessment of learning outcomes
- Certification or accreditation of knowledge
- Technologies
- Open licences
- Response to massification and large class teaching

The case study nominations were reviewed by the Coventry University team and by relevant experts.

The quality assurance mechanism

Prior to collecting the case study nominations, the case study template and the concept note outlining the methodology and methods to be used were reviewed by the OpenMed Quality Assurance Team.

Twelve cases were selected and each partner was asked to complete one detailed case study on a nominated initiative, using the template in Appendix 4. Each of the case studies was reviewed by a different partner institution.

The analysis of 'Open Education by the Supreme Council of Universities in Egypt' by Cairo University has been included as part of the detail of Open Education in the Country Report of Egypt.

All partners were invited to review the country reports and the drafts of the compendium, and an external review was conducted by Javiera Atenas of University College London.

Case studies included

Discover Palestine

<http://moodle.najah.edu/course/view.php?id=1806>

Edraak

<https://www.edraak.org/en/>

JORUM

<http://www.jorum.ac.uk>

Nafham

<http://www.nafham.com/>

OER Commons Arabic

<https://arabic.oercommons.org/EN/>

OER Strategy of the University of South Africa (UNISA)

<http://www.unisa.ac.za/contents/unisaopen/docs/OER-Strategy-March-2014.pdf>

Open Humanities Press

<http://www.openhumanitiespress.org/>

Open Review Project

<http://openedgroup.org/review>

Plateforme Pédagogique – Centre E-learning UIZ

<http://foadm1.uiz.ac.ma/>

Revista REDES (REDES Journal)

<http://revista-redes.rediris.es/>

UC@MOOC

<http://mooc.uca.ma>

A synopsis of the included case studies is presented on part Eight of this document

Expert Interviews

A number of experts in OE were asked to comment on relevant initiatives and share recommendations with the aim of facilitating and encouraging the adoption of OEP in the S–M region. The experts, who were identified by the OpenMed partners, are from the S–M region, the EU, and from the wider international OE community.

Interviews were conducted with the following individuals:

- **Tel Amiel**, UNESCO Chair in OER at UNICAMP and Researcher at NIED/UNICAMP
- **Maha Bali**, Associate Professor of Practice at the Center for Learning and Teaching at the American University in Cairo (AUC)
- **Daniel Burgos**, Pro–Vice–chancellor for Research & Technology and UNESCO Chair on eLearning at the International University of La Rioja (UNIR)
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- **Teresa McKinnon**, Principal Teaching Fellow, Certified Member of the Association for Learning Technology, SF-HEA, University of Warwick, UK
- **Paul Stacey**, Associate Director of Global Learning, Senior Project Manager with Creative Commons, US
- **Peter Suber**, Director of the Harvard Office for Scholarly Communication, Director of the Harvard Open Access Project, Senior Researcher at the Berkman Klein Center for Internet & Society, and Senior Researcher at the Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition
- **Shireen Yacoub**, Chief Operating Officer Edraak, Queen Rania Foundation for Education and Development, Jordan.

Excerpts from the interviews are included as part of the recommendations section.

All of the interview recordings are available at the OpenMed YouTube channel³ and on the OpenMed URL <http://experts.openmedproject.eu>

Data analysis

Case studies provided in Arabic or French were translated into English. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the case study and interview data, led by the OER Research Team.

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1SPHHOxAtpk>

Partner Countries

Figure 2: Map showing OpenMed Partner countries

Key Concepts and Definitions

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Key Concepts and Definitions

Far from being a univocal term, the phrase Open Education is subject to multiple interpretations and its meanings have indeed significantly changed over time. For instance, after the second half of the 20th Century it was increasingly associated with the idea of using mass media channels, telephone and other communication technologies in order to enhance distance education, as exemplified by the UK's Open University (est. 1969) and other HE institutions around the globe based on similar principles and pedagogical approaches, such as Athabasca University (Canada), the National University of Distance Education (Spain) or Indira Gandhi National Open University (India). Unlike traditional institutions bound to physical campuses and more rigid timetables, these new universities were designed to open up education to wider segments of the population and address the needs of people traditionally excluded from HE education. With the rise of the Internet and online communications the idea of Open Education soon started to be equated with e-learning.

In order to understand the practices and phenomena usually associated with Open Education these days it is important to take into consideration other concepts such as Open Access, Open Data, Open Content or Open Licenses, all of which are based on, or directly inspired by, the ideas of Free Software and Open Source. Most notably, Open Educational Resources (OER) and Open Educational Practices (OEP) are key concepts when it comes to thinking of openness in education. According to the European Commission⁴, OER “are learning resources that are

⁴ European Commission, and Directorate-General for Education and Culture (2014), *Opening up Education Innovative Teaching and Learning for All through New Technologies and Open Educational Resources*. Luxembourg: Publications Office. available from http://bookshop.europa.eu/is-bin/INTERSHOP.enfinity/WFS/EU-Bookshop-Site/en_GB/-/EUR/ViewPublication-Start?PublicationKey=NC0214816 [20 August 2016]

usable, adaptable to specific learning needs, and shareable freely” (p.6). In a more narrow interpretation of the concept, UNESCO defines OER as “[t]eaching, learning and research materials in any medium, digital or otherwise, that reside in the public domain or have been released under an open license that permits no-cost access, use, adaptation and redistribution by others with no or limited restrictions.” (UNESCO 2012)⁵. An initiative was launched by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) under the name of OpenCourseWare (OCW)⁶ in 2001, the same year when Wikipedia was established. While MIT-OCW was preceded by similar initiatives such as Rice University’s Connexions⁷ (1999) and David Willey’s Open Content Project⁸ (1998), it gained unprecedented attention from the media and other HE institutions interested in replicating the model.

The term OER was originally coined at a forum arranged in 2002 by UNESCO with the aim of examining the potential of MIT-OCW. In response to the growing interest in the subject, the OpenCourseWare Consortium⁹ (recently rebranded as Open Education Consortium) was launched in 2005.

Numerous individuals, educational institutions and other organizations around the globe have since then contributed to the so-called Open Education movement. Other relevant initiatives were launched soon after that, such as the UK Open University’s OpenLearn¹⁰, the Khan Academy¹¹, or iTunes U¹², all of them established in 2006. And *The Cape Town Open Education Declaration*,¹³ resulting from a meeting of advocates in late 2007, helped to articulate the principles underpinning this emerging movement. In 2008 Dave Cormier

⁵http://www.unesco.org/new/fileadmin/MULTIMEDIA/HQ/CI/CI/pdf/Events/Paris%20OER%20Declaration_01.pdf.

⁶ <http://ocw.mit.edu/>

⁷ <http://cnx.org>

⁸ <http://web.archive.org/web/20030802222546/http://opencontent.org/>

⁹ <http://oeconsortium.org/>

¹⁰ <http://www.open.edu/openlearn/>

¹¹ <https://www.khanacademy.org/>

¹² <https://itunes.apple.com/gb/app/itunes-u/id490217893?mt=8>

¹³ <http://www.capetowndeclaration.org/>

coined the term Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)¹⁴ in response to an experience developed that same year by George Siemens and Stephen Downes, who ran a course on connectivism with a group of students at Manitoba University (Canada) and an extended cohort of more than 2,000 participants from the general public who were invited to follow and participate in the course for free¹⁵.

Over the next few years similar experiences were developed at other institutions, such as Mary Washington University (USA)¹⁶ and Coventry University (UK)¹⁷. In 2011 Sebastian Thrun and Peter Norvig ran another course on Artificial Intelligence at Stanford that, despite adopting a rather different pedagogical approach, was also regarded as a MOOC and involved more than 100,000 students. Inspired by this, a number of platforms developed by companies in partnership with or belonging to universities emerged over the following months (e.g. Udacity¹⁸, Coursera¹⁹, edX²⁰).

While OpenMed seeks as an aspirational goal that, as part of their service mission, HE professionals and institutions engage in the creation and use of educational resources that fully fit UNESCO's definition, we also acknowledge that the uptake of OEP may also encompass a wider range of materials that are available under more restrictive conditions (e.g. not allowing modifications). In this regard, we understand that OEP may also include the creation or utilization of content released for instance under CC licences that do not allow for derivative works, so adaptation is restricted, or are restrictive for other reasons.

¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Massive_open_online_course

¹⁵ <https://sites.google.com/site/themoocguide/3-cck08—the-distributed-course>

¹⁶ <http://ds106.us/>

¹⁷ <https://phonar.org/>

¹⁸ <https://www.udacity.com/>

¹⁹ <https://www.coursera.org>

²⁰ <https://www.edx.org/>

Figure 3: Acknowledging the range of Open Educational Practices

OpenMed takes the 2012 UNESCO definition as a desirable endpoint for a journey towards openness in education that might start with less ambitious goals, sometimes even starting simply by making copyrighted content publicly available on the internet (e.g. releasing educational videos on YouTube using their Standard Licence). Therefore, our interpretation of OEP emphasizes the idea of breaking boundaries and building bridges that expand the opportunities for any citizen to benefit from universities as a source of knowledge without having to become fee-paying students. In addition, apart from the creation and use of content, open pedagogic approaches that place “an emphasis on the network and the learner’s connections within this”²¹ also are key to our take on OEP.

²¹ Weller, M. (2014) *The Battle for Open: How Openness Won and Why It Doesn't Feel like Victory* [online]. London: Ubiquity Press. available from <http://dx.doi.org/10.5334/bam> [20 August 2016]

The Opportunities and Challenges of OER in the MENA region

The Opportunities and Challenges of OER- in the MENA region

By Professor Sana El Harbi, UNESCO Chair in OER at Université de Sousse, Tunisia

The Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region is in the midst of redefining its political system. Education is at the heart of vibrant social movements, it is the focal point of interactions between societal values, economic constraints and internationalization challenges. Despite its potential for promoting knowledge and its beneficial effects on boosting economic opportunities, Open Educational Resources (OER) originating from the region are rare and Open Educational Practices (OEP) are far from entering the mainstream of academic practices. Yet the MENA region is replete with young people who are naturally very exposed to Internet and social media and receptive to digitized content. This young population is a window of opportunity that would underpin the use of OEP. Sana Harbi analyzes the challenges and opportunities of OEP in the MENA region and the potential implications they may have on local communities as well as on the region.

The MENA region is to some extent a homogenous grouping of countries sharing similar institutional and demographic characteristics. While each country has its own specificities, they all fall within the same broad economic and social parameters. This region has some interesting and unique demographic features: for example, compared to developed countries, the region has significantly more young people²². These young people have grown-up in the Internet era. One can expect that digital technologies are fully embedded in the way these young people interact.

²² <http://www.unfpa.org/world-population-dashboard>

In terms of education, the MENA region has achieved remarkable progress. It has quadrupled the average level of schooling since 1960, halved illiteracy since 1980 and achieved almost complete gender parity for primary education, and certain countries of the region have even achieved gender parity for secondary and tertiary education.

According to World Bank statistics, Net Enrolment Ratios in 2012 are almost as high as the Net Enrolment Ratios in developed countries, and the public expenditure on education (as a percentage of total government expenditure) is even higher than countries such as the United Kingdom (UK) or United States of America (USA).

Public universities, where education is free, are the major players in the higher education (HE) field in the region. In Tunisia, for example, all persons with a baccalaureate have the right to be enrolled in a public university. In Algeria there are around 200,000 new students every year and the total number of students exceeds one million. However, as a direct consequence of this situation there is the problem of overcrowded universities.

At the same time there are restrictive laws that desperately try to limit the influx of students, for example restrictions on repeaters, aged persons, graduates seeking new specialities or new degrees, etc. These restrictions, along with the influx of new students, have created all kinds of tensions especially at the beginning of the new academic year when strikes, hunger strikes and 'sit-ins' become very common. The ultimate object of these movements is to claim the right to pursue HE. But the already overcrowded universities cannot accommodate the total influx of students. The existent infrastructure, coupled by severe financial constraints, is not able to meet the steadily increasing demand for HE.

With this massification of education in the MENA region comes the employment market problem. The new graduates find major difficulties securing a job. The unemployment rates are very high in the region (as compared to the category of middle income countries) exceeding 30% for females and around 30% for males²³.

²³ <http://data.worldbank.org/income-level/HIC>

The World Bank report “Jobs for Shared Prosperity”²⁴ relates this situation by explaining how young graduates from the region enter the labour market without skills for a competitive global market. The report criticizes the HE system in that it lacks quality and is not adequately preparing young people for global market requirements. From this perspective the quantitative realizations in terms of education are marred by a silent and elusive reality – that of educational quality. The region appears to have put a huge, but uncoordinated, effort into achieving education, yet without the expected satisfactory results in terms of employment.

Because schooling is not synonymous with learning, just as studying is not synonymous with skills acquisition, the quantitative performance of the MENA countries in terms of enrolment rates is reduced when it comes to quality and employability. The educational methods commonly used in MENA universities dwells on content transmission²⁵ rather than active pedagogy. Yet social cognitive theory (based on an individual’s motivation to learn, and an approach to pedagogical practice being promoted in many universities) confirms clearly how student involvement in learning enhances the effectiveness of skill acquisition.²⁶

Of course, the transmission of information is an important component of education. However, if students are to participate effectively in a democratic society, they must also be enabled to generate knowledge and to think critically about social issues. Pedagogy, in this case, would entail not only the promotion of content transmission but also entail a process of negotiation, interaction and collaboration between teaching staff and students. Igniting curiosity, openness, sharing, collaboration, and social commitment are the features of the pedagogical approach that fits the knowledge society era.

²⁴ World Bank. 2012. *Executive Summary*. Washington, DC: World Bank. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/2012/12/17076808/jobs-shared-prosperity-time-action-middle-east-north-africa-vol-1-3>

²⁵ Transmission model focused on: memorizing, authority, individualism and sanction

²⁶ “Tell me and I forget. Teach me and I remember. Involve me and I learn.” Benjamin Franklin

Because OEP are about encouraging learners to reflect on their skills and motivations and engaging interactions between learners and educators, they are a building block in participatory learning procedures leading to enhanced creativity in organizations, teachers and learners. By shifting from passive consumer of content to reflective learner, students can appreciate how to learn and how to organize information and take full advantage of the opportunity to update their knowledge.

At the social and economic levels, OEP can:

- Help realize an equitable distribution of high quality educational opportunities not yet fully exploited;
- Address training gaps, and extend opportunities for skill acquisition;
- Ease the tension on the overcrowded universities.

Yet OEP are not fully exploited in education. Why?

The education system in the S–M region has not caught up with the potential of new technology for 21st–century teaching and learning. In general, open licensed content in the region is very limited. The journey towards mainstreaming OEP seems still in its infancy. Generally, the conventional question when talking about OEP is: “what are the motives behind adopting Open Educational Practices?” and there are several answers we can use to defend the adoption of OEP; but I think that when it come to the S–M region the discussion should also be centred *on the opposite question*: “*What are the motives for not adopting Open Educational Practices?*” The response here is totally context dependent.

Is it an attitude problem? A resistance to change? An institutional and/or legal problem? An awareness problem? It would seem the answers revolve around combinations of all these factors.

As social beings, people act according to their interpretations of norms and values; from this perspective, it is important to know the prevalent norms about OEP. A recent study in the Tunisian context highlighted that whereas the overwhelming majority of students accept the idea of sharing knowledge, professors are significantly more reluctant about this idea. Collaborative practices were even more controversial and ambiguous among both professors and students.

Of course in order to introduce OEP in the HE sector, awareness-raising efforts as well as capacity building (training, infrastructure, administrative support, etc.) will be required. Nevertheless, there is more to do than capacity building, skills training, and offering easy-access systems. Even with a high degree of awareness and with the provision of the necessary infrastructure, the shift in practices will still be difficult unless individuals are provided with the right incentives to adopt OEP. Indeed, it will certainly require effective mechanisms and incentives in the area of human resource management to address both the hearts and the minds of all “actors” up and down the organizational hierarchy. The “minds” aspects refer to the contextual elements that reinforce the desired behaviour, i.e incentive compensation. It implies explaining to the different actors how OEP are beneficial from their individual perspective. The “hearts” aspects imply the creation of a moral adhesion to the new initiatives, relative to OEP.

Furthermore, given the centralized features of HE in this region, (even though Moroccan universities are gaining more decentralization and more autonomy), what is the share of the official aspects and the volunteer decentralized initiatives? OEP questions in the MENA region therefore centre on the challenge of making change in the HE public institution in a context of an intrusive state, coupled with very centralized management.

Is the state the right defender for the OEP agenda in the MENA region? In the current context of political turmoil, survival seems to be the priority. The government appears too fragile to implement change, and the challenge would impose unrealistic demands on already weak states. Paradoxically, adopting and mainstreaming OEP is not possible without official commitment. Therefore, the question is how to find a reasoned and reasonable commitment that legitimizes and valorizes actions without crowding out voluntarism and initiatives.

Of crucial importance is the partnership with international organizations. The FUA (Francophone University Agency), the IFIC (Institute Francophone of Knowledge Engineering Distance Learning), the European Union (namely through Erasmus projects), UNESCO and

ALECSO have the potential to support the region in terms of raising awareness about OEP.

And finally, the question of adopting OEP is about offering high quality education to the wider spectrum of the population. The ultimate objective being to attract young people of the region to embrace the spirit of open collaboration and sharing, in the hope that these young people would be deterred from the destructive impulses of fanatic and extremist ideologies.

Partner Country Reports

Country reports of the four South Mediterranean partners in the OpenMed project: Egypt, Jordan, Morocco and Palestine.

OpenMed

Written with the support of Silvia Marchionne, International Projects and Networking Officer, UNIMED, Mediterranean Universities Union

Partner Country Reports

Egypt Country Report

Country Demographics

Capital: Cairo

Official language: Arabic

Recognised national languages: Egyptian Arabic and English

Population: In July 2016 the population was 91,300,000 (<http://www.capmas.gov.eg/HomePage.aspx>)

Connectivity: In July 2016 there were 30,835,256 Internet users, which represents a 33% penetration rate (<http://www.internetlivestats.com/internet-users/egypt/>).

Open Education in Egyptian Universities

Provided by Prof. Dr. Elsayed Mohammad Tag Eldin, Irene Fahmy *lawendy*, and Somaya Ezzat Abdul Aati, of Cairo University.

Introduction:

Open Education (OE) began in Egypt in 1990 at Alexandria University and Cairo University, followed by the Universities of Ain Shams and Assiut. The focus then was on vocational rehabilitation and the development of individual skills, and the rehabilitation of those graduates who could not find appropriate jobs, who could access opportunities for self-learning and continuing training and continuing professional development.

Egypt has continued to lead the way in Open (Online) Education, through the establishment of Open Education centres in most universities, with the number of enrolled students (on online programmes) being 268,955 (according to statistics from the Supreme Council of Egyptian Universities, April 2015). There are now academic programmes adopting Open (online) Educational Practices in most of the public universities in the following faculties: Commerce, Law, Arts, Agriculture, Mass Communication, Dar Al Oloum (Arabic and Islamic studies), Tourism and Hotels, Social Service, Education and kindergarten courses.

Types of HEIs (Public/Private): In the current HE system, according to the periodical newsletter issued by the Information Unit of the Ministry of Higher Education in October 2015 for the academic year 2013/2014, there are 23 public universities with 357 faculties, eight public non–university higher technological colleges with 45 institutes (2 years), 19 private universities with 117 faculties and there are 138 private higher institutes (4–5 years) and 12 private intermediate institutes (2 years).

Number of students graduated: In the academic year 2014/2015, about 268,955 (tertiary) students were enrolled in the open education, and in the same year 25,724 students graduated (see the table at the end of the report).

Legal framework of the HE system: Public and private universities provide 4–5 year courses leading to an academic bachelor's degree.

In addition, HEIs provide 4–5 year courses leading to an academic bachelor's degree.

Technological colleges and intermediate private institutes (non–university education) aim to set up categories of professionals and technicians needed by sectors of the construction industry, hospitality, tourism and computing, and secretarial works and support posts in the health sector, medical services, social services and areas of modern agriculture and cooperatives. The duration of study at these colleges is two years.

The Ministry of Higher Education (MOHE) acts as a champion for reform. The Minister, appointed in 1997, quickly established a committee for the reform of higher education (known as the HEEP Committee) which drew in a wide range of stakeholders including industrialists and parliamentarians. A National Conference on higher education reform was held in February 2000, and a Declaration for action emanating from the Conference was endorsed by the President and the Prime Minister. The Declaration identified 25 specific reform initiatives. A range of multilateral and bilateral agencies, including the World Bank, also concur with the Declaration's proposals, and are committed to supporting various aspects of the reform process. Due to the dynamic nature of the reform strategy, a Strategic Planning Unit (SPU) was established for the MOHE to ensure the sustainability of planning and project monitoring during the several phases and for future ones. A Students' Activity Project (SAP) was also initiated as part of programme accreditation similar to scientific research and postgraduate studies.

Governance bodies

There are three bodies for the governance and control of higher education in Egypt:

- the Ministry of Higher Education,
- the Supreme Council of Universities (SCU), and
- the Central Administration of Al–Azhar Institutes.

The Ministry of Higher Education has jurisdiction over higher education through the supervision and coordination of all post-secondary education, planning, policy formulation, and quality control. It also oversees teacher training for basic education. The Supreme Council of Universities, founded in 1950, formulates the overall policy of university education and scientific research in universities and determines the number of students to be admitted to each faculty in each university.

Supervision and administration of the Al–Azhar HE system is the responsibility of the Central Administration of Al–Azhar Institutes. The latter is a department of the Supreme Council of Al–Azhar, responsible for the development of the general policy and planning for

the propagation of Islamic culture and the Arabic language throughout the Al–Azhar higher education system.

The policy of open education in the Egyptian governmental universities

The Egyptian Governmental Universities are keen to provide their educational and scientific services in conformity with the laws and systems which move educational policy in Egypt forward. In view of the law No. 49 in 1972, concerning the universities organization, the legal framework of open (online) education was organized through the following steps:

1. The Presidential Decree of the law No. 49 in 1972 concerning the universities organization.
2. The Presidential Decree No. 809 of the year 1975 concerning the executive regulations of the law of the universities organization.
3. University Council approval for the establishment of Open (online) Education Centres.
4. Approval of the Supreme Council of Universities in Egypt for the establishment of an Open (online) Education Centre at each university.
5. Approval from the Minister of Higher Education concerning the accreditation academic regulations of the open (online) education programmes.

There are two ways to manage programmes of open (online) education in Egyptian universities, either centralized or decentralized, where the organizational subordination of the open education programmes differs. In some universities the management of such programmes follows the faculties directly (decentralized system), while the organizational subordination of those programmes in most governmental universities is to the open education centres (and a centralized system). The Open Education programmes in the Egyptian universities are managed by the Boards of Directors of the Open Education Centres and their academic coordinating committees, or their subcommittees, at the different faculties

according to the decisions of the Supreme Council of Universities in Egypt.

The academic supervision of the programmes of open education varies according to the system followed by each university, where there are two systems: the first is the centralized system based on the formation of a coordinating academic committee; the second is the decentralized system, in which case sub-committees to faculties are formed.

The two different systems are shown as follows:

(a) The centralized system:

An academic coordinating committee is formed with the membership of the academic programme coordinators of the different faculties. This committee is responsible for planning and follow-up of the academic activities of the open education centre and coordination with the concerned faculties.

(b) The decentralized system:

Formation of a sub-committee in each faculty that has programmes in open education, with the membership of the heads of the scientific departments. The responsibility of this sub-committee is to follow-up the implementation of open education activities and programmes inside the faculty.

Programme	Faculty	Courses number per semester	Courses number for each programme
Accounting: Accounting and auditing major Accounting: Cost accounting major Accounting: Financial and tax accounting major Management: Production and industry major Management: Investment major Management: Marketing major Insurance: public insurance major	Commerce	5 courses	40 courses
Agriculture	Agriculture	6 courses	48 courses + 4 training courses
Law	Law	6-8 courses	55 courses
Languages: English French Spanish Hebrew Chinese Other Specializations: Publishing Electronic Archives Practical sociology Psychology and its practical applications Theoretical and practical philosophy Historical studies Geographic information systems	Arts	5 courses	40 courses
Mass communication	Mass communication	5 courses	40 courses
Dar al oloom	Dar al oloom (Arabic & Islamic studies)	5 courses	40 courses
Preparing teachers of early childhood Preparing special education teachers	Kindergarten	5 courses	40 courses + 4 practical training in a school

Programmes of Open Education at Egyptian Universities

Open education programmes offered by the Egyptian Governmental Universities vary to reflect the character of each university and to meet the needs of the surrounding environment. There are 22 Egyptian governmental universities which offer some programmes in open education:

- 1) **Cairo University:** (<http://www.ou.cu.edu.eg/>) – Cairo University established its Centre for Open Education in 1991 and began with course programmes in commerce and agriculture. The Centre now has 25 programmes in different specialities.
- 2) **Alexandria University** – Faculties of Commerce, Education, Fine Arts, Law, and Tourism and Hotels.
- 3) **Ain Shams University** (<http://ol.asu.edu.eg/>) – Faculties of Commerce, Law, Arts, Education, Agriculture, and Women's Studies.
- 4) **Assiut University** – Faculties of Commerce, Law, Arts, Physical Education, Agriculture, and Social Service.
- 5) **Tanta University** – Faculties of Commerce, Law, and Arts.
- 6) **Mansoura University** (<http://www2.mans.edu.eg/centers/olc/>) – Faculties of Commerce, Law, Arts, Education, Agriculture, and Tourism.
- 7) **Zaqaziq University** (<http://www1.zu.edu.eg/OpenEducation/homepage.html>) – Faculties of Commerce, Law, Arts, and Agriculture.
- 8) **Helwan University** (<http://www.helwan.edu.eg/olc/>) – Faculties of Commerce, Law, Social Service, and Tourism and Hotels.
- 9) **Menya University** (<http://oplearnminia.ucoz.com/>) – Faculties of Commerce, Law, Social Service, Tourism and Hotels, and Arabic & Islamic Studies.
- 10) **Minufiyah University** – Faculties of Commerce, Law, Arts, and Agriculture.
- 11) **The Suez Canal University** (<http://olc.scuegypt.edu.eg/>) – Faculties of Commerce, Arts, Agriculture, and Education.
- 12) **The University of the South Valley** (<http://www.svu.edu.eg/arabic/open-edu/>) – Faculties of Commerce, Arts, and Law.
- 13) **The University of Beni Suef** (<http://www.oplearn.bsu.edu.eg/>) – Faculties of Commerce, Arts, Law, Arabic & Islamic Studies, Social Service, and Mass Communication.

- 14) Fayoum University** (<http://www.fayoum.edu.eg/openeducation/>) – Faculties of Commerce, Law, Social Service, Mass Communication, Arabic & Islamic Studies, Arts, Agriculture, Tourism, and Kindergarten.
- 15) Banha University** (<http://www.olc.bu.edu.eg/>) – Faculties of Commerce, Law, Arts, and Agriculture.
- 16) Kafr El Sheikh University** – Offered programmes in partnership with Cairo University.
- 17) The University of Sohag** (http://www.sohag-univ.edu.eg/Open_learn/) – Faculties of Commerce, Law, and Arts.
- 18) The University of Port Said** – Faculties of Commerce and Education.
- 19) Damietta University** – Faculty of Arts.
- 20) Damanhour University** – Faculties of Commerce, Education, Arts, and Agriculture.
- 21) The University of Aswan** – Faculties of Commerce, Education, Arts, Agriculture, Law.
- 22) The University of Sadat City** – Faculties of Commerce and Law.

University	Enrolled Students		Registered students		Graduated students	
	Student	Total	Student	Total	Student	Total
Cairo	34617	87174	9148	23629	3136	7524
Alexandria	5513	16033	4116	8264	473	1245
Ain Shams	8399	18221	5433	12104	931	2085
Assiut	3177	7432	926	2210	613	1439
Tanta	2791	8549	2377	5062	0	0
Mansoura	2973	8035	777	2237	362	951
Zagazig	10292	20892	3673	8510	618	2135
Helwan	1825	4035	258	639	106	165
Minia	3219	8493	855	2730	225	645
Menoufia	1345	4037	424	1543	347	803
Suez Canal	2169	9626	1432	2633	537	1107
South Valley	4319	11295	1935	5643	784	1892
Beni Sueif	2675	8386	1455	3768	372	879
Al Fayyoun	4867	8605	0	0	861	1332
Banha	1591	20418	972	7057	192	873
Kafr El Sheikh	2802	6011	1391	2589	0	0
Sohag	3514	11076	653	1658	365	913
Port Said	1243	2290	562	987	180	420
Damietta	438	687	0	0	0	0
Damanhour	2683	5547	767	1565	541	1027
Aswan	674	2113	0	0	151	289
Total	103137	268955	39133	97794	10794	25724

Table 1: The number of students enrolled, registered and graduated in Open Education at Egyptian universities (according to the statistics of the Supreme Council of Universities April 2015).

Jordan Country Report

Country Demographics

Capital: Amman

Official language: Arabic

Population: at 1 November 2015 census: 9,531,712

Connectivity: In 2011, it is estimated that there are 2,209,229 Internet users, which represents the 35,74 % penetration rate in the population and a 34% growth rate since 2000 (<http://www.journaldunet.com/web-tech/chiffres-internet/jordanie/pays-jor>)

Higher Education in Jordan

Types of Higher Education Institutions (Public/Private): Jordan has 10 public universities, 16 private universities and 54 community colleges, of which 14 are public, 24 private and others affiliated with the Jordanian Armed Forces, the Civil Defense Department, the Ministry of Health and UNRWA.

Number of students graduated: The number of graduate students in Jordan is about 17,540. Out of these, 8,390 are females. Thus the percentage of female students is about 48%. Out of the graduate students, 13,054 students (about 74% of the total) study for master's degrees, 2,116 students (about 12% of the total) study for a Doctorate and about 2,370 students (about 14% of the total) study for a Higher Diploma (data up to 2011).

Legal framework of the Higher Education system

The Jordanian Council of Higher Education was established in 1982 in response to the need for regulation and planning of higher education policies and coordination among Jordanian public universities.

The Council formed the core for the Ministry of Higher Education & Scientific Research, which was established in 1985. The Ministry and the Council undertook the mission of applying the government's educational policies at post-secondary level, and of legislating up-to-date laws on higher education.

The Ministry of Higher Education was annulled in 1998, but was re-established in August 2001 according to instructions by His Majesty King Abdullah II, and renamed as The Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. The New Higher Education Law in Jordan: Consequently, a new Law on Higher Education was endorsed: Law no. 41 for the year 2001, which cancelled the previous Law. By this law, a Ministry of Higher Education & Scientific Research was established, and took over supervising all higher education issues, and includes the following Councils:

- The Higher Education Council (which comprises the Higher Committee for Scientific Research)
- The Accreditation Council.

The new Higher Education Law assigned the Ministry of Higher Education & Scientific Research the following prominent functions:

- To implement the general policy of higher education in Jordan
- Co-ordinate between higher education institutions and public and private centres for consultations and research
- Sign cultural and scientific agreements in the field of higher education and scientific research
- Represent Jordan in international conferences and symposia on higher education
- Recognize foreign institutions of higher education and equating certificates issued by them
- Set student eligibility rules for scholarships inside and outside Jordan
- Follow up the affairs of Jordanian students abroad through Jordanian cultural counselors.

The Law enables the Higher Education Council to carry out the following main functions:

- 1) Formulate the general policy of higher education in Jordan
- 2) Endorse the establishment of new higher education institutions
- 3) Issue instructions concerning administration and finance of the higher education sector
- 4) Coordinate between local higher education institutions
- 5) Evaluate the quality of higher education in terms of sufficiency and efficiency
- 6) Determine the basic admission requirements at higher education institutions.

Under the jurisdiction of aforementioned Law, The Accreditation Council carries out the following major duties:

- To define the regulations for the accreditation of higher education institutions, amending and developing them in light of the general policy of higher education
- Supervise the performance of higher education institutions and their commitment to applying the rules of accreditation
- Appoint the specialized committees needed to carry out the tasks of the Accreditation Council
- Ensure that institutions of higher education reach their pre-defined goals through continuous evaluation of their programmes

First stage: Undergraduate level – Most universities in Jordan follow the English–American education systems and are associated with many American and English universities. Bachelor’s degrees normally take four years.

Second stage: Postgraduate level – A master’s degree is awarded after a further one to two years’ study following a bachelor’s degree. It can be obtained either by course work and a thesis (c. 24 credit hours of courses and nine credit hours of research), or by course work (c. 33 credit hours) and a comprehensive examination.

Third stage: Doctorate – A doctoral degree is awarded after three to five years of further study and the submission of an original dissertation. It requires, depending on the subject, 24 credit hours of course work and 24 credit hours of research.

Non-traditional studies: Distance higher education – This type of education is offered at the newly established branch of the Arab Open University.

Governance Bodies

Each university has a Board of Trustees (BoT). The BoT of a public university consists of a Chairman and 12 members, while the BoT of a private university has 14 members in addition to the Chairman. The BoT of a public university is appointed through a Royal Decree upon recommendation by the Prime Minister, while the BoT of a private university is appointed by the Board of Higher Education.

The BoT undertakes a number of responsibilities, including the following:

- Drawing up the general policy of the university
- Approving the strategic and annual plans of the university, based upon the recommendation of the University Council and follow-up of its implementation and evaluation
- Evaluating the performance of the university from all aspects (academic, administrative, financial and infrastructure)
- Appointing the Vice-Presidents and Deans
- Recommending to the Board of Higher Education the establishment of faculties, departments, institutes and centres, as well as academic programmes and specialisations
- Determining the tuition and study fees and approving the annual budget and annual report, after recommendation from the University Council
- The University Council is chaired by the President and comprises of representatives from the various categories of stakeholders, including representatives from the local communities. It is responsible for the quality of the services offered by the university (teaching, research, training and community service)
- The review of the annual plan for infrastructure and recommending it to the BoT, recommending tuition and fees, approval of the annual budget and performance and accomplishment reports before submission to the Board of Trustees.

It is to be noted that although the above-mentioned Councils and Boards include good representation from enterprises, faculty and

department Councils have only limited numbers of representatives from enterprises.

State of the Art of Open Education:

There are interesting developments in distance learning in Jordan, framing the development of open education. Many of Jordan's universities have begun adopting online portals providing a gateway to online learning. Moodle is widely used as a platform. The University of Jordan is prominent in this regard and has its own YouTube channel providing troubleshooting information for its portal. The University of Jordan also provides free and open e-learning courses that can be found without needing to log on to their Moodle e-learning platform. A MOOC platform (Edraak – see Section Eight) was agreed for launch in November 2013 as part of Queen Rania Al Abdullah's initiatives under The Queen Rania Foundation.

In 2010, the Jordanian Minister of Education announced Jordan's intention to start BLOSSOMS II in ten selected high schools. "BLOSSOMS (Blended Learning Open Source Science or Math Studies) is an Open-education initiative started by MIT in partnership with Jordan and Pakistan," and "has been designed as an Open Educational Resource (OER) consisting of web-based materials offered freely and openly for re-use in teaching, learning and research"²⁷.

The Jordan Open Source Association²⁸ successfully proposed an Arabic Open Educational Resources Platform which was originally launched in June 2011.

There has been some involvement in Jordan with open access publishing, details of which have been reported by UNESCO²⁹.

²⁷ <http://linc.mit.edu/news/2010/blossoms032910.html>

²⁸ <http://jordanopensource.org/>

²⁹ <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/communication-and-information/portals-and-platforms/goap/access-by-region/arab-states/jordan/>

Morocco Country Report

Country Demographics

Capital: Rabat

Official languages: Arabic and Berber

Recognised national languages: French is the first foreign language

Population: At 1 September 2014 census: 33,848,242

Connectivity: Currently it is estimated that there are 18.3 million Internet users, which represents a 56% penetration rate in the population (Wikipedia).

Higher Education in Morocco

Types of Higher Education Institutions (Public/Private): The higher education system comprises 13 public universities, 8 private universities, and 211 private institutes and schools. Public universities are free, except for Al Akhawayn University and the International University of Rabat, which are tuition-based.

Number of students graduated: The number of Moroccan students enrolled in higher education is 677,291 where 640,238 are enrolled in public education and the remaining 37,153 in private education (2014-2015).

Legal framework of the Higher Education System

Higher education in Morocco, regulated by Statute No 01-00, is the responsibility of the state, which provides for the planning, organisation, development, regulation and guidance of the system. The National Education and Training Charter of 1999 laid down the principles and guidelines for the reform of the Moroccan education system. Statute No

01–00 of May 2000 provided for the implementation of these principles and guidelines in the realm of higher education.

Improving the quality of outcomes in the education sector has become a key priority for Morocco's government. A comprehensive renovation of the education and training system was developed in a participatory manner in 1998–99, which led to the vision for long-term expansion of this sector in response to the country's social and economic development requirements. The outcome was the promulgation of the 1999 National Education and Training Charter (CNEF). The CNEF, with strong national consensus, declared 2000–2009 the decade for education and training, and established education and training as a national priority, second only to territorial integrity. The reform programme, as laid out by the CNEF, also received strong support from the donor community. Nevertheless, during the course of implementation, the reform programme encountered delays.

As part of the new educational reform, Moroccan universities have adopted the LMD system in 2003. The system of bachelor's, master's and doctoral degrees now prevails throughout the university structure except at the English-speaking University of Al Akhawaynin Ifrane, which maintains a system of four year bachelor's courses and master's degrees. Master's degrees were introduced in Morocco at the start of the 2006/2007 session; the new centres for doctoral studies, established in 2008, became operational in 2009. The studies are thus based on 3 grades:

- Degree (6 semesters)
- Master's (10 semesters) and
- PhD (3 years after the master's).

In 2005 the Moroccan government adopted a strategy with the objective of making ICT accessible in all public schools to improve the quality of teaching: infrastructure, teacher training and the development of pedagogical content was also part of this national programme.

Governance Bodies

- Higher Council for Education (CSE) monitors and evaluates public policies related to education.

- National Coordination Committee for Higher Education (CNCES) & the Coordinating Committee for Private Higher Education (COCESP). These two committees have been created as part of the quality assurance process of the reforms.
- National Evaluation Authority whose role is to audit and evaluate education policies and works under the Higher Council of Education's supervision.
- National Accreditation and Evaluation Committee (CNAE) is in charge of the accreditation process for master's and doctoral degrees and private institution degrees.

State of the Art of Open Education

Morocco is among the most active of the S–M countries in the OER movement. The Ministry of National Education created the National Laboratory of Digital Resources, which produces and collates digital educational resources, some of which are OER. There are also several other projects in this field in Morocco. For example, the Korea International Cooperation Industry project produces digital resources that are free to access and use for scientific disciplines at the secondary education level in partnership with Al Akhawayn University in Morocco. There is also a Unit for the Promotion of Software and Open Educational Resources at the Moroccan–Korean Centre of ICT Training. The Centre was created with the main objective of promoting the use of software and OER to support the national policy of widespread use of these technologies through the GENeralization of Information Technologies and Communication in Education (GENIE) programme by offering very low–cost, and often free, ICT solutions. The GENIE programme for secondary school incorporates OER, and the strategy was adopted by the National Laboratory of Digital Resources of the Ministry of Education, where a reference to OER is presented in draft ministerial notes regarding validation and certification of digital resources that are in development.

Distance learning is significantly increasing in Morocco in both public and private universities. The increased availability and functionality of information technology (IT) has brought new teaching tools to the Moroccan market, including mobile phones, video–conferencing, e–mail, discussion forums, chat software and document sharing.

Morocco's finance ministry recently decided to integrate a dedicated distance learning service into its organizational structure.

The Ministry of National Education has begun work on an interactive television system (TVI) which aims to provide remote training for teachers across the Kingdom. The E-learning Centre is dealing with E-learning and is supervising distance learning on the use of ICT for university teachers of the Maghreb (Algeria, Tunisia and Morocco). Additionally, the MUN (Maroc Université Numérique) was launched in July 2015 as a collaboration between Morocco's Ministry of Higher Education and France's FUN (France University Numérique).

Morocco has the most competitive expert-trainers in the field of e-learning in the Francophone world. Most Moroccan universities have one or more LMS (predominantly Moodle) with online courses (Ibn Zohr University has more than 100 courses and Cadi Ayyad University has developed many MOOCs in addition to a traditional e-learning Moodle platform). The interest of teachers and students is growing every year in the country.

Palestine Country Report

Country Demographics

Capital: Jerusalem

Official languages: Arabic

Population: In the 2014 census the population was 4,550,000³⁰.

Connectivity: The percentage of Internet users for both males and females increased during the year 2014 compared to 2000. The percentage of Internet users among males increased from 7.9% to 59.6% and the percentage of Internet users among females increased from 2.8% to 47.5%³¹.

Higher Education in Palestine

Types of Higher Education Institutions (Public/Private): There are 52 Palestinian HEIs in the West Bank and Gaza Strip.

Types of tertiary education institutions:

- 14 universities (3 Palestinian Authority, 8 public, 3 private)
- 1 Open Education
- 19 university colleges (8 Palestinian Authority, 7 public, 3 private, 1 UNRWA)
- 18 community colleges (2 Palestinian Authority, 9 public, 5 private, 2 UNRWA).

There is only one open learning university, with 17 centres distributed in the West Bank and five centres in Gaza.

³⁰ http://www.pcbs.gov.ps/Portals/_Rainbow/Documents/gover_e.htm

³¹ http://www.pcbs.gov.ps/portals/_pcbs/PressRelease/Press_En_IntDyInfoSoc2015E.pdf

Number of students graduated: The number of graduate students in higher education institutions for the academic year (2013/2014) is 40,043 students, divided into:

- Traditional universities: 25,166 universities
- University colleges: 3,592 students
- Community Colleges: 3,213 students
- Open Education: 8,072 students.

Legal Framework of the Higher Education System

The development of higher education (HE) in Palestine is relatively recent. Two-year colleges have existed since the 1950s. These institutions, which focus on teacher training, technical education or liberal arts, were organized either by the government or by the United Nations Relief and Works Agency (UNRWA). It is only since the 1970s that universities came into existence. Created during the Israel occupation, these institutions were part of a Palestinian collective effort to preserve their identity as well as to provide young Palestinians with the opportunity to pursue HE, after it became increasingly difficult for them to go abroad for such studies. However, the sector has expanded only since the transfer of education from Israel to the Palestinian National Authority (PNA) after the Oslo Accords of 1990.

Higher education is regulated through the Law on Higher Education No 11 of 1998. This law gives every citizen the possibility to access HE (Article 2), gives legal status to HE institutions, and provides the legal framework for their organization and management. The law recognizes three different types of institutions in HE. These are governmental, public (established by non-governmental organizations (NGOs)), and private institutions. Most higher education institutions (HEIs) in Palestine are public.

The Council of Higher Education is responsible for drafting and enacting the rules that all HEIs must adopt. The ministry also provides partial support and funding to non-governmental HEIs. The HEIs are mostly independent but they have to follow the abovementioned law, regulations of the ministry and the Council of Higher Education.

According to the Law on Higher Education, HE institutions can be one of the following:

Universities (AL–Jamiaah): consisting of no less than three colleges or faculties which confer bachelor’s degrees or higher;

University colleges (Alkulliah Al–Jamiaaiah): offering academic, technical or professional programmes and conferring two or three–year diplomas or ordinary or honours bachelor’s degrees;

Polytechnics (Alpolytechnik): conferring diplomas or bachelor’s degrees and higher degrees in professional and technical fields;

Community colleges (Kulliat Al–Mujtamaah): offering academic, professional or technical programmes of a minimum of one year’s duration, leading to diplomas in the respective programmes.

Governance Bodies

In accordance with international norms, the Law on Higher Education No 11 of 1998 combines two approaches:

- Central national planning and supervision by MoEHE and the Council for Higher Education,
- Self–management, self–monitoring and self–control at institutional level.

This means that HEIs enjoy autonomy and self–management. They are responsible for admissions, recruitment of staff, assessment of students, granting of degrees and diplomas and the development of facilities. In addition to the Council of Higher Education, a Council for Scientific Research and a National Commission for Accreditation and Quality Assurance has been established. With regard to Vocational, Technical Education and Training (VTET), the Law also stipulated setting up a Supreme Council and an Executive Council for VTET. In May 2012, the Ministry of Education and Higher Education was divided into two separate Ministries. Therefore, there is now one single Ministry devoted to HE.

In terms of governance (management, supervision and funding) there are five types of HEIs:

- **Governmental:** The Palestinian National Authority runs and finances the governmental HEIs in the West Bank (Palestine

Technical University–Khadoorie) and the Gaza Strip (Al Aqsa University) which are under the supervision of the Palestinian Ministry of Education and Higher Education.

- **UNRWA:** The United Nations Relief and Works Agency (UNRWA) for the Palestinian Refugees operates one of the largest school systems in the Middle East and has been the main provider of basic education to Palestinian refugees for nearly five decades. The Agency provides primary and junior secondary schooling free of charge for all refugee children in the area of operations. Vocational and technical training courses are given in the eight UNRWA vocational training centres. The Agency also runs an extensive teacher–training programme and offers university scholarships to qualified refugee youth.
- **Private:** these institutions are run and financed by several foundations, charitable societies, religious denominations, individuals and companies.
- **Public:** most HEI (universities) were set up during the period of Israeli occupation of the West Bank and the Gaza Strip.
- **Vocational, Technical Education and Training (VTET):** These institutions are supervised by several bodies, consisting of the Ministry of Education and Higher Education, Ministry of Labour, Ministry of Social Affairs, UNRWA, charitable and religious associations, international non–governmental organisations, developmental organizations and private sector institutions. The governing bodies of the HEIs are mentioned above.

State of the Art of Open Education

Al–Quds Open University is an independent public university and the first university in the Palestinian Territory to deliver distance learning. It was established in Amman by a decree issued by the Palestinian Liberation Organization (PLO) and started operating in the Palestinian territories in 1991. QOU is the only Open Learning Institute in the Palestinian territories. It has 60,000 students studying in 19 branches and centres distributed all over the West Bank and Gaza Strip. The university has six centres located in the Palestinian Territories, as follows:

- The Information and Communication Technology Center (ICTC) is responsible for technical development, computerizing all

administrative, academic, financial and productive works of the university;

- The Continuing Education Center (CEC) was created to make connections between academic knowledge and practical experience;
- Media Production Center (MPC): This centre is responsible for producing educational multimedia to support the philosophy of distance education. The centre uses audio–video, video editing units, graphics and filming;
- Open Learning Center (OLC): The OLC is an educational/technical centre in Al–Quds Open University, established in 2008.

The main achievements in the Palestinian HE system in terms of Open Education are the following:

- Al–Quds Educational Channel is the latest educational method of Al Quds Open University in the field of e learning.
- The establishment of the biggest computerized network in Palestine by the ICTC which is an accredited testing centre for specialized international certificates. It also has most of its systems and curricula computerized. The network, a partnership with the Palestinian Development Gateway, was funded by the Programme for Assistance to the Palestinian People, part of the United Nations Development Programme.
- Increasing the number of students to 60,000 which makes Al Quds Open University the biggest non–campus university in Palestine.
- Opening 19 branches and study centres.

Palestine promotes and sustains an enabling environment in which the OER movement can flourish. This is being achieved by:

- developing an ICT in Education policy
- proposing a vision and strategy for not just developing OER but also for using them at all levels: primary, secondary and tertiary
- recognizing OER–development as comparable to academic publications to reward faculty who are investing their skills and resources in OER promotions.

An-Najah National University sets an example in open education for traditional universities which develop learning using technology. ANNU has developed 231 courses (1,771 lectures) which are open to the public, 280 online open courses, and has designed the Discover Palestine MOOC (see Section Eight) which is an open and free online course about the geography, history and culture of one of the holiest lands in the world. All of the open resources provided by ANNU aim to enhance educational opportunities, connect communities of educators and learners around open content, increase awareness, embed OER in the teaching profession, share best practices in OE, and improve learning environments.

Webometric Analysis

Webometric Analysis

In late December 2015, a webometrics analysis was undertaken to assess the level of awareness of open education and OER in HE institutions in OpenMed partner countries: Egypt, Jordan, Morocco, and Palestine. This analysis, which was presented at the OpenMed kickoff meeting in January 2016, examines the presence of some key terms associated with open education on institutional websites at the *outset* of the OpenMed project.

Drawing on previous webometrics studies (Villar–Onrubia 2012, 2013, 2014³²), researchers at the Disruptive Media Learning Lab decided to take the mentions of particular words on HE institutional websites as an indicator of institutional awareness of open education and OER. The terms included in the study were: “CC,” “open educational resources” or “OER;” and “MOOC.” These websites were sourced from the Web Ranking of Universities, and 215 relevant sites were identified: Egypt (62); Jordan (36); Morocco (97) and Palestine (17).

³² Villar–Onrubia, Daniel (2014). ‘The Value of Web Mentions as Data: Mapping Attention to the Notion of OER in the HE Arena.’ In *Ciencias Sociales Y Humanidades Digitales Técnicas, Herramientas Y Experiencias de E–Research E Investigación En Colaboración*, edited by María Sánchez and Esteban Romero Frías, 163–81. CAC, Cuadernos Artesanos de Comunicación, 61, 2014. <http://www.cuadernosartesanos.org/2014/cac61.pdf>.

Villar–Onrubia, Daniel (2013). ‘Mapping Attention to OER across Spain’s HE Sector: A Web Impact Assessment.’ In *Proceedings of OER13: Creating a Virtuous Circle*. Nottingham, England, 2013. www.oer13.org.

Villar–Onrubia, Daniel (2012). ‘Assessing Awareness on Open Education by Means of Online Research Tools. Work presented at the UNESCO Open Educational Resources (OER) World Congress, Paris, 20 June 2012. <http://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2085585>.

The Google Scraper tool³³ was then used to search for the selected keywords on the 215 websites. Prior to running the scraper tool, the researcher running the analysis logged out of Google, cleared all cookies, and removed personalization features from Google. These actions were taken to ensure that the researcher's prior use of Google did not impact upon the data retrieved by the Google scraper tool.

There is, however, an important limitation which must be considered. Some – but not all – of the websites included contained both national language and English language translations of the text. However, the keywords CC, MOOC and open educational resources/OER were not always translated on the national language webpages. This means that some institutions may be over-represented, in that a keyword might be present on two or more separate webpages which are exact translations of one another. A number of the Moroccan Universities, for example, contained English, French and Arabic translations.

Of the 215 institutions searched, 44% (95) contained one or more of the three English-language search terms. The breakdown by country is detailed below in Table 2

Country	Number of HEI sites	Number of HEI sites containing 1 or more keywords	% of total
Egypt	62	30	48%
Jordan	36	17	47%
Morocco	97	37	38%
Palestine	17	11	65%
Total	215	95	44%

Table 2: Number of HEI websites per country and number of sites containing one or more search terms (with percentage of total)

³³ <https://tools.digitalmethods.net/beta/scrapeGoogle/>

Data were then re-analysed to identify the HE institutions which most often mentioned the three keywords, as shown in Figures 4, 5, 6 and 7.

Figure 4: Top 20 HEI sites by combined total matches

Figure 5: Top 10 HEI sites containing the keyword “CC”

Figure 6: Top 10 HEI sites containing the keyword “MOOC”

Figure 7: Top 10 HEI sites containing the keywords “open educational resources”/OER

These figures indicate an extremely high representation of the CC keyword in comparison to the presence of MOOC and open educational resources/OER. However, the findings should be interpreted with caution. Many of the institutions used CC licensed images on their websites and, as is required, identified them as CC images. Consequently, the high proportion of this keyword does not necessarily indicate increased discussion around CC as opposed to MOOCs or OER. It does, however, highlight that the HEIs were familiar with and used CC images and licenses appropriately.

The findings also indicate that for each keyword, there were three or four institutions with a high number of web mentions. These data can be useful for the subsequent work packages of the OpenMed project, in particular in the creation of an extended network of universities. Having an overview of the level of awareness of key phrases at

universities in the region could help ensure that a mix of institutions is involved in the network.

For instance, institutions with a high level of awareness could be invited to share their expertise, while institutions with low or no level of awareness are ideal candidates for benefiting from the capacity building opportunities that the OpenMed project will make available.

OEP Participation Survey Information

Sever

OEP Participation Survey Information

All partners in the OpenMed project were asked to complete a survey outlining the level of participation in OEP within their institution. The survey sought to capture current practice at the time of completion (early 2016) and also to identify the future goals of the participating institutions.

The following pages summarise the responses to the surveys and are listed in alphabetical order by full institution name.

Alexandria University, Egypt

Alexandria University (AU) was established in 1942. Since then it has established the Beirut Arab University in Lebanon, which is run and supervised by staff from AU, and has also established branches in N'djamena in Chad in the south of Sudan. According to Times Higher Education in 2011, AU ranked 303rd in the world's top 400 Universities.

AU has over 143,500 undergraduate students and 8,752 postgraduate students, across six campuses.

AU seeks to provide an accessible, adaptable and challenging learning environment to develop graduates and researchers that meet the needs of its regional, national and international communities. The Faculty of Agriculture aims to occupy a leading position in the production and promotion of knowledge related to the sustainable development of human, natural and agricultural resources at the national, regional and global level. It also seeks the production, dissemination and application of knowledge through research and development, education and training in order to contribute to the sustainable development of agricultural and human resources capable to compete locally, regionally and globally, consistent with human values and ideal standards.

Definition of Open Education

AU defines open education as:

... a system of open source education with no obligation to attend regular classes. It is suitable especially for students who wish to pursue university study and have no availability to attach to regular courses

AU states that at least 75% of course materials should be available online via distance learning. In some cases 100% of the materials are online. Open educational practice currently takes place in six AU faculties: arts, fine arts, commerce, law, education, and hotel and tourism. There are memoranda of understanding with four other Universities in this area: Cairo, Suez Canal, Assuit, and Damanhour.

Online Teaching and Learning

AU offers four online degrees, which are also offered to full-time students. There are currently 17,000 open education students. Some modules are also available online as open courses. These modules are supported by non-academic technical staff, who support the design, management and release of the materials.

Online learning materials are shared via the university website³⁴ or on the faculties' websites.

AU uses the Moodle LMS³⁵ and also has a YouTube channel³⁶ containing videos of seminars and lectures.

Institutional Resources

AU has an institutional repository (IR)³⁷, which is completely open and accessible by those outside the university. The IR contains research papers.

³⁴ <http://www.alexu.edu.eg>

³⁵ <http://www.alec.alexu.edu.eg/#>

³⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/user/AlexandriaELearning?gl=EG>

³⁷ <http://research.alexu.edu.eg/>

Academics in AU are free to release educational materials openly, although no details are available for any open licenses used.

Current Practice and Future Goals

There are several members of staff within AU who have a particular interest in OER.

An-Najah National University, Palestine

An-Najah National University is the largest university in Palestine, with approximately 20,000 students and 860 academic personnel spread across three campuses. Currently, An-Najah has 12 academic faculties offering 73 undergraduate and 48 graduate programmes, including two PhD programmes and three medical specialization programmes. Recognized and accredited by numerous international associations and agencies, An-Najah ranks first among Palestinian Universities and twelfth among 983 Arab World Universities.

In addition to the teaching and research activities that typically characterize a university, An-Najah seeks to tackle the development needs of Palestine from a unique perspective. In particular, through a cadre of highly specialized Scientific Centres and support from the Project Management Unit, An-Najah provides vital services to promote the economic and societal development of Palestinian communities including, among others, Poison Control Unit, Urban Planning Centre, Material Science and Nano Technology, and Business Innovation Centre. Recently, An-Najah has established the first teaching hospital in Palestine. It seeks to improve the quality of medical services available to the public and to simultaneously train professionals for the healthcare sector. An-Najah cultivates a multicultural, pluralistic outlook among students through a number of initiatives designed to foster cross-cultural dialogue and tolerance.

Definition of Open Education

An-Najah does not have a formal definition of open education but practices openness and describes it as:

giving opportunity for learning with no boundaries.

The university is moving towards improving awareness of OER and OEP, and is developing resources such as open databases, an e-library, online courses and MOOCs, and recorded lectures.

As a country, Palestine does not currently have a formal national policy on open education, although the development of such a policy is in progress.

Online Teaching and Learning

An-Najah does not run any online-only courses: at this time the Palestinian Ministry of High Education does not accredit online degrees. However, almost 700 courses (taken by over 11,000 students) are run as blended learning and approximately 200 courses are recorded. Staff are rewarded for teaching using OER: these rewards include financial awards, points for promotion, and decreased teaching load.

The online and blended courses are supported by an e-learning centre with nine members of technical staff, and by the university library.

An-Najah uses the Moodle LMS and hosts its courses there³⁸. Educational content is shared online in a variety of ways: the university also hosts an openly available repository of recorded lectures³⁹, and in addition has a YouTube channel⁴⁰ and TV and radio channels.

Institutional Resources

An-Najah has an institutional repository (IR)⁴¹, containing journal articles, conference papers, and master's theses, which is completely open and accessible by those outside the university.

The openly available educational content created by An-Najah is not released under a license.

Current Practice and Future Goals

An-Najah has a commitment to using OER and several members of staff are described as being champions of OER.

³⁸ <http://moodle.najah.edu/>

³⁹ <https://videos.najah.edu/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/user/NajahUniv>

⁴¹ <https://scholar.najah.edu>

Birzeit University, Palestine

Birzeit University (BZU) started as a school in 1924, and became the first institution of HE in Palestine in 1972. BZU currently comprises nine faculties offering 46 undergraduate programmes and 23 master's programmes. BZU is also home to 11 institutes and centres that support community oriented programmes geared towards training, capacity building, research and maintaining sustainable development in Palestine. BZU has a student body of approximately 11,000 students, of which about 1400 are graduate students, and 450 full time faculty members, as at the academic year 2014–2015.

Definition of Open Education

BZU does not have a definition of open education, although it aspires to make quality education accessible to all; something particularly important in Palestine where there can be restriction on movement.

There are currently no policies within BZU on open education, although plans are in place to create and implement institutional/departmental policies which will encourage faculty members and students to make their work openly accessible by depositing it in BZU's institutional repository.

Online Teaching and Learning

BZU does not offer any online-only degrees: at this time the Palestinian Ministry of High Education does not accredit online degrees. However, the university offers blended courses which include both face-to-face and online elements. Students, both undergraduate and postgraduate, have access to the online components of 93 courses. The majority of these courses are approximately two-thirds face-to-face and one-third online. Only registered BZU students can access these courses. During any semester, more than 2,700 students access the online components via the Instructional Technology Center⁴².

Staff within BZU are encouraged to use online educational resources in order to enrich their lectures and the curriculum, although there are no specific requirements to do so.

⁴² <http://itc.birzeit.edu>

The use of online educational material and development of OER is supported by the Unit for Learning Innovation, part of the Center for Continuing Education. This Unit has a team of instructional designers, multimedia specialists, pedagogy experts, and experts in innovative learning.

There are two Learning Management Systems in use at BZU: Moodle and Ritaj. Ritaj is a content distribution and management system for educational resources, which was developed in-house and is expected to evolve into a full-fledged LMS.

Institutional Resources

BZU is currently developing an open-access institutional repository called 'Fada' (meaning space, or cosmos). Fada⁴³ uses the open-source DSpace institutional digital repository which is designed to preserve and enable easy and open access to all types of digital content including text, images, video, and data sets.

In addition to Fada, there are three other IRs within BZU, each of which contains different types of content:

- Approximately 2,500 master's theses;⁴⁴
- Research studies, white papers, books, and other BZU publications;⁴⁵
- Palestinian legislation: laws, court judgements, and research studies related to the legal system and legislative processes. This IR also includes a legal lexicon and a legal thesaurus⁴⁶.

BZU also has a YouTube channel⁴⁷. BZU does not currently have a policy on publishing content under open licenses, but the Council is currently working on adopting CC licensing for all educational resources which are published in the Fada institutional repository.

⁴³ <http://fada.birzeit.edu>

⁴⁴ <http://library.birzeit.edu/library/bzu-ths/bzu-ths.php>

⁴⁵ <http://library.birzeit.edu/library/bzupublications.htm>

⁴⁶ <http://muqtafi.birzeit.edu/en/>

⁴⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/user/universitybirzeit>

Current Practice and Future Goals

BZU is in the process of establishing a Center for Excellence in Teaching and Learning which will work to bring about formal/informal educational reform through:

- Innovation in the development of teaching/learning skills;
- Keeping up to date with advances in education;
- Design based research and “use of classrooms as laboratories”;
- Utilising technology as an effective enabler in educational development.

Cadi Ayyad University, Morocco

Cadi Ayyad University (UCA) was founded in 1978. It is made up of 13 faculties and schools that cover all the scientific, technical, economic, legal, medical, and social sciences. UCA has a presence in four cities: Marrakech, Safi, Essaouira and Kelaa Sraghna.

The University has approximately 63,000 students, 1,400 teachers and researchers, 850 administrative staff, and more than 600 foreign students of 50 nationalities.

Currently, UCA faces a major problem due to the increasing number of students (massification) from year to year: however, university structures are not big enough to host all the students at UCA. It is becoming increasingly difficult to provide quality education to a growing number of students without using educational innovations, considering that financial and human resources cannot cope with this rapid increase in student numbers. Furthermore, students who have studied in Arabic in high school are getting their HE in French, which is generating language difficulties. More than 25% of first year students fail to adapt to this radical change and leave university.

The adopted solution is the establishment of an educational innovation centre that aims to produce innovative and relevant OER for teachers and students of UCA. One of these is the MOOC (Massive Open Online Course), a unique initiative in Morocco. It offers flexible and adapted learning for students without any restriction of access. This innovative initiative aims to reduce the effects of overcrowding and the failure rate, especially in the open-access institutions, by providing students with direct and unlimited access to lessons and allowing the interaction between students and teachers through the UCA portal.

Definition of Open Education

UCA does not have a clear definition of open education, nor does it have an institutional policy.

Online Teaching and Learning

UCA does not currently run any online-only degree courses, although

some teaching staff use OER. The teaching staff do the majority of the support work on these resources, although there is some additional assistance from technical staff, if available.

UCA runs the UC@MOOC platform, which offers online, open, free courses from a variety of institutions⁴⁸ and which has attracted approximately 3 million international visitors.

UCA uses Moodle as a LMS, and also uses the Open edX open courseware platform. In addition, it hosts an educational platform which is accessible to staff and students⁴⁹.

Institutional Resources

UCA does not have an institutional repository, nor does it make any educational content available under open licenses.

Current Practice and Future Goals

UCA has a number of staff who are actively involved in using OER. Current projects relating to open education include the UC@MOOC platform mentioned above.

⁴⁸ <http://mooc.uca.ma>

⁴⁹ <http://learn.uca.ma>

Cairo University, Egypt

Cairo University (CUE) (previously King Fuad I University, Egyptian University) is a public university in Giza, Egypt, and was founded on 21 December 1908. It is the second oldest institution of HE in Egypt, notwithstanding the pre-existing higher professional schools that later became constituent colleges of the university, after Al Azhar University. It was founded and funded as the Egyptian University by a committee of private citizens with royal patronage in 1908 and became a state institution under King Fuad I in 1925. In 1940, four years after his death, the University was renamed King Fuad I University in his honor. It was renamed a second time after the Free Officers Coup of 1952. The University counts three Nobel Laureates among its graduates and is one of the 50 largest institutions of HE in the world by enrolment.

CUE is usually ranked in the top universities in Egypt. It is also ranked as one of the top universities in Africa. In the QS ranking 2014 CUE was ranked 2nd in Egypt, 7th across Africa, and 551–600 worldwide. In the ARWU 2014 ranking the university was ranked 1st in Egypt and it was the only Egyptian university in the ranking. It was rated 401–500 worldwide.

CUE currently has over 190,000 undergraduate students: these students learn face-to-face and also online. There are 32, 376 traditional postgraduate students, and 682 postgraduates studying via open education, who learn and are assessed online.

Definition of Open Education

CUE provided the following definition of open education:

We believe that open education is a philosophy about the way people should produce, share, and build on knowledge, as we believe everyone should have access to high-quality educational experiences and resources, and we work to eliminate barriers to this goal and to enhance the quality at the same time.

CUE does not currently have a formal policy or strategy on open education. However, the university is pursuing the development and

expansion of OER within CUE through co-operation with the Egyptian Knowledge Bank (EKB), a wide-ranging digital library containing information in a variety of formats.

Online Teaching and Learning

CUE runs a number of degree and diploma courses, in various faculties, which are run as online-only courses. Online courses are supported by teaching assistants who support courses and upload materials, and by technical staff who design, develop and manage open/online educational resources.

There is no requirement within the university for teaching staff to use online educational resources; however, there is increasing use of an electronic learning system.

CUE has a YouTube channel⁵⁰ and also has a television channel on Nilesat (a satellite television company broadcasting approximately 700 channels)⁵¹.

CUE does not currently use a LMS, but is seeking to develop an in-house LMS.

Institutional Resources

Cairo University does not have an institutional repository, and does not currently release educational content under open licenses.

Current Practice and Future Goals

With regard to future projects to do with open education, Cairo University is pursuing the development of OER through co-operation with the Egyptian Knowledge Bank, and also seeks to develop partnerships with international open Universities.

⁵⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/user/openedu2013>

⁵¹ <http://nilesat.com.eg/Home.aspx>

German–Jordanian University, Jordan

The German–Jordanian University (GJU) is a public university located in Mushaqar. It was founded in 2005 by a Royal Decree, in accordance with a memorandum of understanding reached between the Ministry of HE and Scientific Research of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan and the Federal Ministry of Education and Research of the Federal Republic of Germany.

The university is modelled on the German applied–sciences model, characterized by their focus on putting knowledge into practice and on promoting knowledge transfer. They aim to play a significant role in promoting links between Jordan and Europe, particularly Germany.

The university's focus is on providing undergraduate and graduate programmes of the highest quality. They offer over 20 programmes, with a student body of around 5,000, drawn predominantly from Jordan, but also including international students.

Definition of Open Education

Due to the fact that open education is not recognised by the Ministry of HE in Jordan, GJU does not have an institutional definition of open education. Nor does it offer any courses via online learning.

Online Teaching and Learning

As noted above, no courses are offered by GJU which are online–only. However, the e–learning resources provided via the university's LMS are widely used by teaching staff. These resources are supported through GJU's Computer Center, which is a non–teaching unit.

The LMS used by GJU is Moodle. E–learning materials are supported and shared via this learning environment.

Institutional Resources

The GJU has an institutional repository, though it is not open access, and is not available to those outside the university. The IR is used by teaching staff to deliver educational materials to students, such as presentations, assignments, and announcements.

There is currently no information available about the release of content under open licenses by GJU.

Current Practice and Future Goals

A number of staff within GJU intend to incorporate innovative and open technologies within their teaching. GJU is currently involved with an EU Tempus funded project on Open Source Software Curricula Enhancement in Universities.

Within the context of the OpenMed project, German–Jordanian University seeks to expand the online learning resources in order to support the traditional educational programmes.

Ibn Zohr University, Morocco

Ibn Zohr University (UIZ) is a public institution under the Ministry of National Education, HE and Scientific Research in Morocco.

The University was established in Agadir and it aims to ensure university education for four Moroccan areas, representing almost 52% of the national territory. In addition, UIZ contributes to scientific research in a variety of fields due to its commitment to a variety of local, national and international projects. For the academic year 2014/2015 UIZ had a total of 110,000 students enrolled in the five branches of the University (Agadir, Ouarzazate, Laâyoune, Guelmim, and Taroudant).

UIZ strongly recognizes the importance of new technologies within the education and training fields, such as the use and production of resources through its E-learning Unit.

Definition of Open Education

UIZ uses the UNESCO (2002) definition of open education:

The open provision of educational resources, enabled by information and communication technologies, for consultation, use and adaptation by a community of users for non-commercial purposes.

UIZ further states that the university policy on open education is about:

...giving opportunity for educators to share open educational resources with each other, and the world. High quality resources and service to inspire teachers, be directly used by students, and be improved upon, or localized by others. The Ibn Zohr University has seeded 72 modules, written by educators from different faculties and schools to help students share information.

Online Teaching and Learning

UIZ has 21,000 online learning students, but does not run any online-only courses; these students study on blended learning courses.

There are no institutional requirements for academic staff to use online educational resources. Support for students studying online predominantly comes from doctoral level students.

UIZ has two online platforms – an e-learning portal⁵² and a teaching platform⁵³, where educational content is shared. The university uses Moodle as a LMS.

Institutional Resources

UIZ does not currently have an institutional repository, nor does it release any educational content under open licenses.

Current Practice and Future Goals

A number of teaching staff within UIZ use ICT within their courses. Since 2012 UIZ has organised online training every year for university teachers in the Maghreb region, on how to use e-learning in their teaching.

A current and ongoing project within UIZ is a MOOC, being developed by the E-Learning Centre, entitled 'Le Métier d'Étudiant' (Student Occupation). This MOOC will help students with their academic life in various areas, including concentration, motivation, writing theses, preparing for exams, and organizing everyday life.

⁵² <http://foadm1.uiz.ac.ma/>

⁵³ <http://foad-v2.uiz.ac.ma/>

Princess Sumaya University for Technology, Jordan

Princess Sumaya University for Technology (PSUT) has emerged in the past six years as a centre of excellence in ICT education, research and innovation and a model of the future university in Jordan. It was established in 1991 as a non-for profit academic arm of the Royal Scientific Society (RSS), which is considered as the only comprehensive applied research centre in Jordan.

PSUT strives to become a nucleus for a modern Jordanian knowledge industry, which actively animates the process of socio-economic and cultural development locally, regionally and globally. PSUT aims at supplying Jordanian, regional and global societies with technically and scientifically qualified ICT graduates and with solid applied research work. PSUT has been actively involved in the renewable energy and resource efficiency domain.

PSUT currently runs 12 undergraduate programmes and 8 graduate programmes.

Definition of Open Education

PSUT does not currently have a definition of open education; nor does it have an institutional policy, although it is part of the eQTeL Tempus project⁵⁴ ('Enhancing Quality of Technology-Enhanced Learning at Jordanian Universities') which may lead to the creation of such policies in the near future.

Online Teaching and Learning

PSUT does not run any online-only degree courses, although some lectures are posted online to YouTube⁵⁵. There is also an ongoing project which is experimenting with using remote labs for engineering subjects.

PSUT uses the Moodle LMS. All course materials are expected to be posted online, as well as homework submissions, projects, and student communication.

⁵⁴ <http://eqtel.psut.edu.jo/Home.aspx>

⁵⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/user/PSUTUniversityoffici>

Moodle class management is supported by IT staff on a semester basis.

Institutional Resources

PSUT does not have an institutional repository, and does not release openly available content at an institutional level. However, some materials are published at a faculty level using CC licences, for example 'Hacking Techniques and Intrusion Detection' (2013)⁵⁶.

Current Practice and Future Goals

PSUT has participated in a Tempus project which included sharing the curriculum and learning materials for one master's programme across ten Universities (MSC–ESE)⁵⁷, and is currently participating in the eQTel project mentioned above. In addition, PSUT shares some learning activities with other Universities, for example through programming competitions.

⁵⁶ <http://opensecuritytraining.info/HTID.html>

⁵⁷ <http://www.tempus-msc-ese.eu/about-msc-ese>

Case Studies of Relevant Initiatives

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Case Studies of Relevant Initiatives

Synopsis

The following paragraphs briefly summarise each of the following case studies. These are ordered alphabetically by title.

Discover Palestine

This initiative is a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC), provided by An-Najah National University in Palestine. Discover Palestine is an English language MOOC about Palestinian history, archaeology, culture, and heritage. The case study outlines the content of the MOOC and the processes undertaken in order to design, develop, and implement the course. It also provides a brief reflection of the challenges and opportunities encountered throughout the development of the initiative.

<http://moodle.najah.edu/course/view.php?id=1806>

Edraak

Edraak is a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) initiative, provided by the Queen Rania Foundation (QRF) in Jordan. It is built on the EdX open online learning platform. There are currently 31 courses on Edraak, which have been taken by more than 435,000 learners. 80% of the courses are developed by Edraak in Arabic, and 20% are EdX courses from international institutions such as Harvard and MIT, translated into Arabic by Edraak. The case study details the history of the initiative, its structure and funding, and outlines how the courses are selected, offered and managed.

<https://www.edraak.org/en>

Jorum

This initiative is a large online repository for discovering and sharing OER for higher education, further education, and skills training, funded by Jisc in the UK. Jorum currently holds over 16,000 educational resources, licensed under Creative Commons, and ranging from single documents to complex packages (e.g. full courses). The case study outlines four successful aspects of the Jorum initiative: multiple stakeholder involvement; engagement strategy; acquisition framework; and openness to change.

<http://www.jorum.ac.uk>

Nafham

Nafham is a free educational website which was started by a group of individuals and is funded by advertising. It hosts and produces video content based on the school curriculum in Egypt and Syria, from kindergarten to 12th grade. Nafham also promotes 'crowd-teaching', encouraging students, parents or teachers to submit a video explaining a subject. The case study outlines the background and the structure of Nafham, with a particular focus on the value of crowd teaching to everyone involved.

<http://www.nafham.com>

OER Commons Arabic

This initiative is a repository of learning objects, developed by the Institute for the Study of Knowledge Management in Education (ISKME) in California, and funded by Qatar Foundation International. It holds a range of educational resources at primary, secondary and post-secondary level which come from institutions such as Khan Academy and MIT Blossoms. It also hosts a user community which provides support for students, educators, designers and for the general public. The case study describes the structure and design of the initiative, and the ways in which teachers and instructional designers can evaluate and use the resources provided.

<https://arabic.oercommons.org/EN>

OER Strategy of the University of South Africa (UNISA)

This initiative is an institutional policy for the adoption of OER. UNISA is an open distance learning (ODL) university, with over 90% of its students as part-time. The publication of a governmental White Paper for Post-School Education and Training in 2014 led to the development of an OER strategy within UNISA. The case study outlines the comprehensive planning which took place before the development of the policy, and the importance of top-level support for such a policy.

www.unisa.ac.za/contents/unisaopen/docs/OER-Strate-gy-March-2014.pdf

Open Humanities Press

The Open Humanities Press (OHP) is an open access publishing initiative which seeks to create high quality publications without depending on commercial publishers. It is a not-for-profit company which is predominantly funded by the sale of hard copies. The case study outlines the underlying philosophy of OHP and the principles under which it operates, and focuses particularly on the importance of the free exchange of scholarly knowledge.

<http://www.openhumanitiespress.org>

Open Review Project

This initiative is an ongoing evidence-based review of OER use, predominantly in North America, and is supported by the Open Education Group. Although not an OER initiative in itself, the Open Review Project evaluates empirical studies on the efficacy/perception of OER in HE. The case study outlines the methods used by the Review Project, and summarises some of the conclusions drawn so far from the research which has been reviewed.

<http://openedgroup.org/review>

Plateforme Pédagogique - Centre E-learning UIZ

This initiative provides open online education via two Moodle e-learning platforms in a variety of different disciplines. There are 100 courses, with over 21,000 students. The case study focuses on the value of teachers and lecturers in computing and related subjects, outlining the courses provided and the guidance provided for publishing course materials online.

<http://foadm1.uiz.ac.ma>

REDES

REDES is an open access online journal, publishing research in the field of social network analysis. It is the only social network analysis journal published in Spanish, and all texts are subject to a CC licence 4.0. REDES was born out of an online community of researchers on an email list, and is run by volunteers. The case study explores the history of the community which led to the development of REDES, the organisation of the journal, and focuses on the importance of openness and collaboration to the initiative.

<http://revista-redes.rediris.es>

UC@MOOC

This initiative is a platform which provides online access to learning materials for students at Cadi Ayyad University (UCA) in Morocco. It was established in order to resolve the problem of over-large classes, and contains a variety of course materials in the form of podcasts, videos and other resources. The case study outlines the background to the initiative, and provides some statistical details of the courses hosted on the platform. There is also some discussion of the importance of using a variety of pedagogies in order to support the high numbers of students.

<http://mooc.uca.ma>

Discover Palestine⁵⁸

Completed by Dr Saida Affouneh of An–Najah National University.

Case Study Overview

Type of initiative: MOOC (Massive Open Online Course).

Country: Palestine.

Organisation behind the initiative: e–Learning Centre, An–Najah National University.

Initiative team:

- Dr Saida Affouneh – Course team leader
- Dr Ahmed Ra’fat Ghodieh – Geography specialist
- Dr Loay Abu Alsaud – Archaeology specialist
- Eng. Arij Abu Obaid – Multimedia specialist

Type of organisation: HE Institution.

Who funds the initiative?: An–Najah National University.

History and Goals of the Initiative

Description of the Initiative

This initiative was started in 2012 by a team from the university, under the supervision of the E–Learning Centre. Discover Palestine is the

⁵⁸ <https://elc.najah.edu/sites/default/files/flash.htm>

first English language certified Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) about Palestinian history, archaeology, culture, and heritage.

Discover Palestine explores the ancient land of Palestine. Participants will learn about the geographical and ecological makeup of the land, the different types of agriculture and water installations that have been adopted by various groups over the centuries, as well as trade and other relations between groups. They will also learn about the art, architecture, and technology of the different periods covered by this course.

From a chronological perspective, the course will cover a period of time extending from the Late Bronze Age to the earliest Islamic periods. In order to add depth to the course, therefore, it will be necessary to focus on some periods more closely than others. Students will be encouraged to deepen their learning experience by exploring some of the more superficially covered periods. If the current state of historical and archaeological research is insufficiently developed to permit us to resolve a problem with confidence, we will identify the problem and lay out the evidence as fairly we can. They will also choose several possible ways of referring to areas or the people in it, explaining our choices and methods, e.g., “Palestine,” “Canaanites,” etc.

The course will focus on conductivities and interrelationships, how each group of people learned from others and how each succeeding period emerged from, and built on, the culture and technology of preceding periods.

The initiative became a part of the university’s academic responsibility and social role. Palestine is not well known within international communities; the political conflict is the only issue that Palestine is remembered for. The aim of this initiative is to introduce Palestine and Palestinians to the international world in a very interactive way by reflecting its beauty, history, geography, and culture.

The course was established by a team which consists of geography, history, and culture experts, instructional designers and multimedia specialists. The team did initially not know much about MOOCs, and started to learn about them from literature and by participating

in a MOOC on how to develop a MOOC. The experience was very interesting, using the concept of learning by doing.

The content of the course consists of readings, videos, audios, photos, interviews, latest news, announcements, forums, projects, and many web links. Developing the course content was not an easy process; agreeing on the outline and then on the material itself went through many stages between developing, discussion, evaluation, and approving. The evaluation process was conducted on three main themes; the subject, the design, and the delivery. Five different workshops were conducted in the university and led by the E–Learning Centre to discuss the idea, the methodology, the course outline, the quality of the course, and the expected challenges. The evaluation of the initiative was conducted by an internal team of experts in the first stage and then an evaluation workshop was conducted with the participation of external evaluators.

The course was first introduced for piloting and then lessons were derived from the first trial. The course was developed and finalised in its final version and now is offered each semester for honour students in the university, and twice a year for the international community as a MOOC. Three main facilitators follow the implementation of the course; they supervise forums, assignments and projects. They also respond to all questions from participants. Technical support was also offered to all participants from E–Learning Centre staff.

The course was designed in Moodle as the LMS which is not a common LMS for MOOCs; the team decided to do so since they are familiar with Moodle and it is the LMS that is used as the university’s e–platform. The course was announced through the university website, MOOCs database, and through social media. The language of the initiative is English since our main target group is the international community; eventually it will be translated onto French.

The course has been offered three times: the first started on 16 October 2014 and ended on 17 December 2014. The second started on 1 April 2015 and ended on 2 June 2015, while the third started on 8 October 2015 and ended on 9 December 2015. There were a total of 247 participants, distributed as follows:

Male 106

Female 141

Country	Palestine	United States	United Kingdom	Spain	India	Italy
No.	76	30	26	12	11	10
Country	France	Malaysia	Netherlands	Canada	Morocco	Sweden
No.	7	6	6	4	4	4
Country	Australia	Germany	Hungary	Indonesia	Jordan	Mexico
No.	3	3	3	3	3	3
Country	Argentina	Brazil	Colombia	Israel	Norway	UAE
No.	2	2	2	2	2	2
Country	Afghanistan	Bulgaria	Chile	China	Croatia	Greece
No.	1	1	1	1	1	1
Country	Iceland	Ireland	Mauritius	Pakistan	Philippines	Portugal
No.	1	1	1	1	1	1
Country	Romania	Serbia	Slovenia	Somalia	Sudan	Switzerland
No.	1	1	1	1	1	1
Country	Thailand	Vietnam	Yemen			
No.	1	1	1			

Table 3: Gender and Location of Discover Palestine Visitors

Participants find out about Discover Palestine through a variety of sources, as follows:

Figure 8: Ways in which users find Discover Palestine

Key Aspects of the Initiative

Main Course Topics

The course consists of five main topics:

Topic One – Geography of Palestine: This topic sheds light on the characteristics of the geographical location of Palestine, which is built in the middle of the ancient world, the climate, and factors affecting it.

Topic Two – The History of Palestine: The second topic is dedicated to the historical perspective. It discusses the history of Palestine from the beginning of the prehistoric ages until the end of the Iron Age, and the different groups of people who lived in Palestine through those different periods, in addition to the different foreign attacks. There is a set of forums about interesting questions regarding ancient civilizations such as the Canaanites, Philistines, etc.

Topic Three – Heritage and Culture: This topic discusses Palestinian culture such as traditional customs, handicrafts, and of course cuisine. This topic also discusses the architecture of Palestinian houses and historical sites, in addition to the different ethnic groups who still live in Palestine, such as Samaritans.

Topic Four – Cities: This topic focuses on the major cities in Palestine, starting with their location, encountering their rich past history, and ending with their monuments and historical places. The content is

designed as an interactive presentation; all you need to do is to click on the city name on the map, then start your new journey throughout the amazing and rich historical facts beneath those locations.

Palestine in Photos: This topic shows pictures about Palestinian currency, Palestine before 1948, occupied and destroyed villages, traditional costumes, An–Najah National University, the environment, sea, lakes and Negev.

Figure 9: Screenshot of Discover Palestine MOOC

Course Grading, Accreditation and Certification

Upon successful completion, participants will be awarded certificates. There are two types of certificates: participants who do not complete the course receive a partial certificate; and a complete certificate is given for participants who complete the nine weeks of studying and who successfully complete the final project. There are no regulations that are related to MOOCs in the Ministry of Education and HE; legislation on open education is in progress but is not yet approved, so there is no accreditation for this type of learning at this time.

Lessons Learned and Transferability Opportunities

Main Challenges

- No previous experience in MOOC development.
- Lack of experts in MOOC design.
- Learning by doing was the strategy used, but this took more time and effort.
- Lack of external funding.

- Unclear roadmap and unexpected results.
- Participants did not finish the course.
- Decreasing number of participants.
- Variety of participants, original, background and basic information about Palestine.
- The need to follow up on a regular basis; the facilitators coordinate this as additional work.
- Teaching load for the working team.

Opportunities

- The university management support for the initiative.
- The team's enthusiasm for the initiative and hard work.
- Some of the participants visited Palestine after the course.
- More knowledge about An-Najah National University.
- The importance of the subject.
- Being part of the international open community.

Edraak⁵⁹

Completed by Dr. Sufyan Almajali, Dr. Abdullah Alzoubi, and Dr. Omar Hasan Ootom of Princess Sumaya University for Technology, Jordan.

Case Study Overview

Type of initiative: MOOC platform.

Country: Jordan.

Organization behind the initiative: Queen Rania Foundation (QRF).

Type of organization: Non-governmental organisation.

Who funds the initiative?: QRF.

History and Goals of the Initiative

Introduction

Education is very important in people's lives, as it transforms a person to become more successful, productive, and self-confident. Education grants people the chance to evolve and grow their abilities. A person with a good education will in general end up a better citizen and more dependable at work. In today's competitive world, education has become a necessity.

Many people in several parts of the world, including the Arab world, are deprived of this necessity due to multiple reasons such as financial,

⁵⁹ <https://www.edraak.org/en/>

political, geographical, and language barriers. Many cannot afford to buy an expensive textbook, or register in an expensive university. In addition, many countries have an unstable political situation that affects their education systems and makes them unable to deliver education according to plan. Some people also live in rural areas where high quality education might not be an option. In addition, learning resources might not be available in the language choice desired by the learner. The problem is amplified when HE is the target.

One promising initiative expected to minimize the impact of the aforementioned barriers is the concept of Open Education. Open Educational practices include opening education to a broader set of potential learners, in some cases at no cost, using the latest technologies that facilitate reaching out to a large set of learners.

The concept of Open Education is new to the Arab world. There are a few initiatives that support open education and Edraak is one of them. In this case study, we will be focused on Edraak. Several people have been interviewed to prepare this case study. General information about Edraak will be presented such as the goals, the organization structure, the approach, and its technical structure. In addition, the Edraak model will be visited in this study from different perspectives.

Edraak Initiative

In 2014, the Queen Rania Foundation (QRF) in Amman/Jordan launched an initiative called Edraak with the intention of delivering quality education to the Arab world for free using a new approach for the region. Edraak is a massive open online course (MOOC) platform, and is the first not-for-profit Arabic online education platform.

The Edraak platform was built using OpenEdx technology. EdX is a not-for-profit organization composed of over 30 leading global institutions founded by Harvard and MIT. QRF signed an agreement with edX in 2013.

QRF launched Edraak with three main objectives. First, Edraak will allow Arabic learners to access education delivered by the best Arab professors and subject matter experts, offering original Arabic courses,

developed by Edraak, to further enrich Arab education. In addition to originally developed content on Edraak, the platform will also give Arab learners access in Arabic to courses taught and developed at top tier institutions such as Harvard, MIT, and UC Berkeley. Edraak will be responsible for translating these course into Arabic. All courses are delivered at no cost to the learner.

Second, Edraak seeks to expose learners from the MENA region to Arab role models by delivering short online courses by professionals and thought leaders from a variety of fields.

Finally, QRF believes that the platform will enable the Arab world to take advantage of the international interest in regional affairs to tell its own story to the world. Arab university professors and regional experts can use the Edraak platform to give courses in English about the region and its history.

Edraak was founded by QRF in partnership with Sheikh Mohammed bin Zayed Al Nahyan, Crown Prince of Abu Dhabi, UAE. In addition, Edraak is sponsored and supported by the Mikati Foundation, based in Lebanon, and the Arab Fund for Economic and Social Development, based in Kuwait.

So far, Edraak has been able to create more than 50 online courses. More than 750,000 learners signed up to learn on Edraak.org and more than 60,000 certificates have been issued to date.

Key Aspects of the Initiative

Edraak's Content Strategy

Most of the platform's courses are created by Edraak in collaboration with partner institutions and individual subject matter experts. In addition to the demand driven courses, Edraak focuses on five critical development areas:

- Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM).
- Teaching and Learning.
- Business and Entrepreneurship.
- Employability skills.
- Education for Citizenship.

As stated earlier, Edraak runs surveys to collect feedback about desired courses. In this case, Edraak searches for a qualified instructor to teach the course. In some cases, Edraak licenses courses from edx and localizes them to be offered in Arabic on the platform.

Course Life Cycle

Most of Edraak courses run through a cycle of three stages as illustrated below.

Figure 10: Edraak Course Process

In the first stage, the course is offered for the first time. Each course is assigned one instructor and two or more teaching assistants (TAs). Some courses may have more than one instructor. Students take two surveys each time a course is offered: a Course Entry survey and a Course Exit survey. In addition to the surveys, feedback is collected via other channels. Edraak analyses the surveys and collects feedback as part of its quality monitoring and course improvement process. This might result in modifying the course content. The process repeats by rerunning the course twice more. In the final stage, the course becomes self-paced with no instructor intervention. Once it becomes self-sufficient, students can register on it at any time and take advantage of the course content.

Course Content and Structure

Edraak courses are designed using sound instructional design and best practice in educational media as fully fledged learning experiences. These high quality courses contain the following components:

- Video lectures divided into 7-minute segments
- Assessments (multiple types: multiple questions, virtual labs, peer and self assessments among many others)

- Readings
- Discussion forums
- Games
- Links to external resources.

The interactive discussion forums allow strong interaction among learners and between the learners and the instructors during the course time. Learners can help each other to understand new content, under the supervision of instructors and TAs. In addition, learners can communicate with instructors/TAs outside of class time.

Course Grading and Certification

Each course has a minimum passing score that varies from course to course. In order for a learner to receive a certificate of course completion, learners are required to take the assessments and assignments allocated within the course and to attain the minimum passing score of that course. Assessment and graded homeworks have due dates.

Course Accreditation

While the majority of the courses on the platform are not accredited, Edraak has recently launched a pilot accredited course in partnership the German–Jordanian University (GJU). The course was delivered as a blended learning one: the online part was offered via the Edraak platform and the face–to–face part was offered on campus. Towards the end of the course, successful students earned three credit hours.

Course Content Rights and Licensing

Edraak is keen on pushing the envelope on promoting high quality Arabic open educational resources online. As part of its mission to revolutionize access to and delivery of education in the Arab world, the platform has adopted the creative commons license and is actively encouraging its partners to do the same.

Learner Perspective

The table below shows statistics collected by Edraak indicating the learner profile and overall course statistics.

General Statistics	
Most Common Age Group	19-28
Have completed Bachelor's Degree	50%
Percentage of Female Learners	40%
Learners' Countries	**Edraak learners countries
Number of Courses Offered	+50
Number of Learners	+740,000
Number of Issued Certificates	+60,000

Table 4: Learner Profile and Overall Course Statistics of Edraak

Statistics show that the majority of learners are either at the age of undergraduate students or are graduates who are looking to improve their skills. Learners at pre–university stage have not yet taken advantage of this platform. This could be due to the nature of the courses offered so far. Edraak has succeeded in reaching the Arab world, as many of the learners come from different Arabic countries. In addition, the majority of learners do not come for certificates: they come for knowledge and course content.

In an interview conducted with one of the learners, Arch. Maysoon, she shared her experience with Edraak courses. She had taken three different courses using the Edraak platform. The courses were as follows:

- Entrepreneurship Who is Your Customer – from MIT courses;
- The Modern Arabic City – from Urban Planning Perspective;
- The Six Factors of Success.

In general, she was thrilled with the platform. She finished one of the courses completely, and finished more than half of the course for each of the other two. Maysoon said that she is looking for knowledge more than certificates. Maysoon liked the short videos approach, and liked most the openness of the platform as she can still access the material of all of the courses that she took at Edraak. Maysoon read about Edraak in newspaper articles and Facebook posts. According to her, it

was a positive experience overall, which she benefited from, and she registered for new courses and recommended the platform to others.

Acknowledgement

During this study, we interviewed four different stakeholders. We at PSUT would like to express our great appreciation for the following individuals who made this case study possible:

- Mr. Waleed Al Baddad (Online Course Manager at Edraak). Mr. Waleed provided great support and help: his interview was very useful to this study, and most of the information provided in this study was derived from his interview.
- Mr. Omar Al-Ithawi (Senior Engineer at Edraak).
- Arch. Maysoon Al-Khuraissat (Edraak learner).

JORUM⁶⁰

Completed by Antonio Vetrò and Anita Tabacco of Politecnico di Torino, Turin.

Case Study Overview

Type of initiative: Repository for discovering and sharing OER for HE, Further Educations and Skills.

Country: United Kingdom.

Organization behind the initiative: Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC).

Type of organization: Non–departmental government body.

Who funds the initiative?: JISC.

History and Goals of the Initiative

The Jorum platform is one of the biggest online repositories for learning and teaching purposes. It has been founded by JISC, a non–departmental public body (i.e., not related to any specific government department, but supporting ministers’ work) in the United Kingdom in 2002, and has been run jointly by the JISC National Data Centres, EDINA⁶¹ and Mimas (since 2014 part of JISC’s digital resources division). The project initial goal was to develop a national repository to store the outputs of national funded learning and teaching resources.

Between August 2008 and August 2011 the development of the second Jorum’s “Service in Development” took place. Jorum made use of a commercial software platform to host educational resources uploaded

⁶⁰ <http://www.jorum.ac.uk>

⁶¹ <http://edina.ac.uk/>

by staff from registered educational institutions in the UK, and make them searchable. However, by August 2011, Jorum successfully concluded an important transition by shifting to an open model, both from the software point of view and from the type of users perspective. In fact JISC customized an open-source software platform and permitted people worldwide – and not only UK registered users – to utilize the service.

With such a shift, Jorum became an OER platform. This change implied a significant effort in terms of engaging with the education community (to gather requirements and communicate new developments) and of providing support for the increasing number of users (through telephone and email by the EDINA helpdesk, with the Jorum team providing second-line support for more complex queries).

The Jorum platform today contains more than 16,000 educational resources, licensed under CC licenses, most of which (over 9,000) have been acquired by an ad-hoc programme, i.e. the second phase of the JISC/HEA OER Programme, which aimed at extending the range of materials openly available, documenting benefits offered by OER to those involved in the learning process and enhancing the discoverability and use of OER materials.

The learning resources contained in Jorum range from single documents to more complex resource packages (e.g., full courses or interactive units).

In September 2016 JISC will retire Jorum and refresh its OER offer, with a shift that will allow new forms of collaboration and communication between the Jorum users.

Figure 11: Screenshot of the Jorum Homepage

Key Aspects of the Initiative

Jorum's primary aim is to support communities of lecturers who can share, reuse and re-purpose learning resources in all discipline areas.

In this section we enlist and describe four distinctive aspects that helped Jorum in achieving its goal and made it a successful initiative worldwide.

Multi-stakeholder Governance

As described in the previous section, a relevant aspect of the initiative is that its development has involved multiple stakeholders: the Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC), the JISC National Data Centres, EDINA and Mimas. The collaboration of the different actors involved in such multi-stakeholder governance has allowed the flexibility necessary to go through a number of necessary transitions. In the first one, between August 2008 and August 2011 (Jorum's second "Service in Development" project), Jorum moved from being a national repository whose access was limited to UK registered teachers to being an open platform providing worldwide users the possibility to find, share and discuss thousands of learning material. This substantial change has been achieved through close collaboration between the two JISC National Data Centres, with Mimas leading on Engagement, while EDINA has led on Content and Infrastructure. The task of managing a project whose team is split across two organisations and

three geographical locations has presented some challenges and at the same time has brought many benefits such as the ability to more effectively engage with Jorum's wide audience.

Engagement Model

Another relevant aspect is the effort by the Jorum team to engage users through different activities and with different goals.

The first objective of the Jorum model engagement is to raise awareness through conferences, academic publishing, email marketing, case studies: staff from both Mimas and EDINA presented the platform at over 100 events so far. Such involvement is effective for meeting stakeholders and potential users face to face as well as to establish and maintain relationships. In addition to conferences, papers studying the impact of sharing resources and shorter articles were published in a variety of venues. Throughout the course of the project, news have been released to communicate changes to Jorum and highlight the benefits of sharing learning materials, and are distributed through press, email (including JISC mailing lists), blogs, social media and the Jorum website, which is also continuously updated to be a reliable presence online. Finally, an important successful engagement activity has been the Learning Object Competition with prizes to engage teachers in sharing their learning resources.

As part of the engagement strategy, support for users is provided through telephone and email by the EDINA helpdesk, with the Jorum team providing second-line support for more complex queries. The project provides also training, however with the move to open licences, the adoption of a simpler metadata schema and interface, and the increased popularity of online training, traditional training events are becoming less necessary.

Collaboration with other initiatives is also a further engagement tool. The team has explored joint activities with a number of other projects in order to deliver mutual benefits and maximise efficiency. Examples of collaborative activities have included joint events, shared knowledge, experiments with technology and assisted population of the platform.

Finally, Jorum's key collaboration is with its users, who help to shape the service by defining requirements, providing feedback on prototypes and releases, and using and promoting the service. Working with users is achieved through user groups, social media, forums, user testing, studies and surveys.

Socio-Technical Framework for Content Acquisition and Management

The main asset in Jorum is its educational content, which is available for everyone. Much of the content has been acquired during the JISC OER programme, while significant other learning resources have been acquired through several initiatives with partners, including universities (e.g. the Open University or the Staffordshire University) and other projects and centres (e.g., the Information Computer Science Subject Centre, the GEES C-Change Project). The educational artifacts coming from these external projects have been deposited into the Jorum open collection through a plethora of technical mechanisms: in bulk, through APIs, RSS feeds, the web user interface or other specific tools (e.g., Selenium). Such flexibility in content acquisition has been possible thanks to the transition of Jorum towards an open platform based on DSpace and an inclusive development process in which the Jorum team has worked closely with users to gather requirements. In addition, the development team has introduced user-centred techniques such as ethnographic studies and user testing into the development process.

Therefore the development of the Jorum platform is the result of an extensive engagement activity with the education community in the UK and worldwide. By responding to community feedbacks, the team adapts its focus not only to promote the content of Jorum to teaching professionals, intermediaries such as learning technologists and librarians, but also develops platform services to allow users to upload and promote their own content more easily. These services range from a simple API and widgets, to collaborative-oriented features like conversations or participatory events that take place around the content and are based on Web 2.0 technologies.

The technological infrastructure described above is bound to a legal framework, processes and policies that support the Jorum service. The

legal framework has been developed in conjunction with the University of Edinburgh, and consists of the Terms and Conditions, a Notice and Takedown Policy, a Privacy Policy, and a Collection Development Policy. This framework disciplines also the use of licenses for the content reuse, mainly CC licenses and the Jorum Education UK licenses.

Openness to Change

We have described as Jorum underwent through two major transitions, that influenced each other: the shift from a closed-source platform to a (customized) open-source platform and the shift from being a UK-based platform to being usable by anyone in the world. We have seen that a key role in those transitions has been played by the strong engagement with the education community that was not only a force pushing towards the change, but also a force that supported and drove it, thanks to the deep involvement of the users in the development process of the platform.

Such openness to change is a key factor of the success of the Jorum initiative. In line with this openness, a new transition is ahead, in response to the changing digital demands of the education community: in September 2016 Jorum will be retired in order to refresh its OER approach. Over the coming months JISC will be testing and looking into the possibility of new services, as for example: bringing together existing resources and enabling educators to discuss, rate and use items within their own environments; or building forums and engagement spaces to enable users to share resources peer to peer. JISC will also explore the usage of a “Jisc App” and “Content store”, a digital platform (still free to access), where users can blog, share and discuss challenges and solutions as well as a further education online academy.

The idea behind these different approaches is to develop digital literacy and confidence in using technology, bring together existing resources and allow crowdsourcing to promote the sharing of ideas and resource amongst the education and research community.

The 16,000 resources available through Jorum will be progressively moved to the new platforms and enabled to accommodate the new foreseen services.

Lessons Learned and Transferability Opportunities

In a transferability perspective, the main lesson learned in the Jorum case is the strong engagement with the education community (practitioners and trainers) and with intermediaries such as librarians and learning technologists. The engagement has been implemented through a wide spectrum of activities, each one tailored to the target audience.

The interaction with users has been fruitful also for developing an OER platform, which actually responded to the users' needs. The platform has been built around a socio–technical framework that allowed the flexibility needed to respond to the changing needs.

The openness of the platform is reflected by a multi stakeholder governance system: although managing a project whose team is split across two organizations and three geographical locations is a challenging endeavor, it has also brought many benefits, especially regarding the effectiveness of Jorum's reach out.

Finally, from a stricter technical point of view, multi–channels for uploading material have been an evident facilitator.

Nafham⁶²

Completed by Mohammad Daoud, Jordan Sabri and Raba Sabri of German Jordanian University, Jordan, Egypt.

Case Study Overview

Type of initiative: Nafham provides a platform for explaining the school curriculum in Egypt, Syria, Saudi Arabia, Algeria, and Kuwait using short videos. All services provided by Nafham are free of charge.

Country: Egypt.

Organization behind the initiative: Initiated by a group of individuals.

Type of organization: Firm initiated by a group of individuals.

Who funds the initiative?: Funded by advertising.

Data sources used for the initiative: Review of course documentation, websites, and publications.

History and Goals of the Initiative

Nafham was established in 2012. It is an online, free educational website that hosts and produces video content based on the Egyptian and Syrian curricula. In addition to original videos content, Nafham encourages crowd-teaching among students. The target group addressed by Nafham includes students in kindergarten through the 12th grade.

The educational content hosted by Nafham includes more than 10,000 videos that cover more than 75% of the national curriculum.

⁶² <http://www.nafham.com/>

The educational material hosted by Nafham includes videos produced in-house, and crowd-sourced material, where all these items can be sorted by grade, subject, and academic term. Nafham actively promotes its crowd-teaching model which allows anyone – student, parent, teacher – to submit a video explaining a lesson or problem.

Recently, Nafham has expanded its content to incorporate video lessons that cover the Syrian curriculum for children who are missing school but might have access to Internet. Moreover, Nafham also hosts a monthly competition to encourage peer education. In these competitions, users gain points for uploading videos. Also, additional points are given to the users based on the quality of the instruction and visual components of their uploaded educational material.

Key Aspects of the Initiative

Key People

- Ahmed Alfi, Founder of Nafham
- Mostafa Farahat, GM & Co-Founder, Nafham
- Muhammad Habib, Co-founder & COO, Nafham
- Badr Alaa Ahmed, Website Admin/ Instructional Designer, Nafham
- Mohamed Guda, Content Manager, Nafham.

Associated Pedagogical Innovations

Nafham is based on a model that provides free online K–12 educational video content, where the funding is mainly based on advertising. The videos provided by Nafham range between 5 to 20 minutes. These videos are crowd-sourced educational and revised by professional teachers. The videos are coming from 3 different sources (teachers, students, parents). The three sources contribute by aggregating content available online, creating content for the missing parts, and answering questions raised by students. The most important feature of Nafham is the empowering of the public crowd to create online educational videos, which Nafham calls “Crowd-Teaching”. Videos are covering the mandated public curriculum in different Arabic countries. The educational videos are categorized by grade, term, subject and academic schedule, which makes it easy for students to navigate to the lesson they want to get and save huge family’s spending on

private tutoring. The student group targeted by Nafham includes the age ranges between 6 and 17 years.

Funding Models

Nafham is mainly funded by advertising. Moreover, other funding sources include NGOs, businesses, and customers.

Quality Assurance Mechanisms

There is no clear indicator about the quality assurance policy employed by Nafham. However, based on the “The Re–imagine Learning Network”⁶³, Nafham is receiving positive feedback from the learners community. For example, the website stated that “a mother reported that their 2 daughters in primary stage are spending their summer vacation competing with each other doing educational videos. Another six–grade girl created French language videos for 10th grade students as she is a French school student. Other parents said that Crowd–Teaching helped them to discover new talents in their kids and improve their kids’ self–confidence. Further, those students who are studying online at Nafham reported that it’s an amazing experience”.

Infrastructure

Nafham is hosted by Flat6Labs⁶⁴, which is a startup accelerator that provides support for startup companies in the MENA region. The main technology that is used to deliver the educational material is based on e–learning resources, mainly short videos prepared by volunteers. Therefore, the backbone infrastructure is composed of the electronic resources, such as servers and Internet connect, to deliver the educational material.

Technologies

The main technology that is used by Nafham is to post short videos that explain the school curriculum by volunteers, and how learners can access these videos through the Internet free–of–charge.

Accessibility for Disabled Learners

The online video can be access through the personal computers,

⁶³ <http://www.changemakers.com>

⁶⁴ <http://www.flat6labs.com/>

which might be equipped by the user with any supporting technologies for disabled people.

Lessons Learned and Transferability Opportunities

Nafham employs an interesting approach by providing free educational services to school students using e-learning resources. The educational materials are prepared by public contributors, including teachers, students, and parents. One important feature of Nafham that might be of interest to the OpenMed project is the capability of the students to provide educational resources to their peers. Such capability will encourage university students to participate in constructive discussions and collaborative educational activities.

Nafham has gained the following awards:

1. MC Egypt (Mercy Corp) – Best Social Impact Award during ArabNet Beirut 2013
2. ArabNet Beirut 2013 – 3rd Place Startup Demo Award

OER Commons Arabic⁶⁵

Completed by George Yerousis of Center for Continuing Education, Birzeit University.

Case Study Overview

Type of initiative: Repository of learning objects.

Country: USA.

Organization behind the initiative: Institute for the Study of Knowledge Management in Education (ISKME).

Type of organization: Education non-profit.

Who funds the initiative?: Qatar Foundation International.

History and Goals of the Initiative

Developed by Institute for the Study of Knowledge Management in Education – ISKME, the OER Commons Arabic “micro-site” is built on the existing framework of OER Commons. As such, it contains the full functionality of that site, including a system for saving priority content and the Open Author Tool (Figure 12), which allows educators to build, translate, and remix content.

In 2012, the portal featured around 413 resources, primarily K–12 focused including mathematics and science content from Khan Academy, MIT Blossoms, and the University of Colorado’s PHeT Physic Simulations. In 2016, the number of resources has grown to 8,842 (primary level: 235, secondary level: 4482, and post-secondary: 4125).

⁶⁵ <https://arabic.oercommons.org/EN/>

During this initial launch phase, ISKME's OER Commons and Open Author tools have been translated into Arabic; included are search and metadata descriptions in both Arabic and English. With support from Qatar Foundation International (QFI), a curriculum alignment tool has also been developed for tagging and querying resources to Qatar's achievement standards for science, mathematics and English, as well for the U.S. Common Core State Standards, and future work will be to include mapping standards across countries. OER Commons Arabic also features a custom Arabic Language Learning Resources community – developed as a joint effort by ISKME and a consortium with partners from The Center for Languages, Arts and Societies of the Silk Road (CLASSRoad) and the Language Acquisition Resource Center (LARC) at San Diego State University.

Situated within OER Commons Arabic, the custom community aims to offer up-to-date, accessible information about instruction, course materials and opportunities for Arabic language educators and students, for designers and administrators of Arabic language programmes, and for the general public.

Figure 12: The Open Author Tool

The Open Author Tool, depicted in Figure 12, allows the author to combine text, pictures, sound, files and video. Saved as openly licensed educational resources, the author can share them with friends, colleagues and educators from around the world.

Key Aspects of the Initiative

The portal was established to cater to the type of teachers who would like to re-invent the wheel every day and to re-make educational resources on their own – making use of and building upon other teachers' work. The portal is meant to provide those teachers with basic digital media resources, lessons, work samples that were created by teachers and who have tried them in their educational environments. Such resources can be utilized 'as-is' or re-mixed, re-formulated, translated, built-upon, and then re-shared – all for free. They can be summarized by 4Rs: Reuse, Redistribute, Revise, Remix. Further, the portal provides a rich platform for teachers to contact and connect with other teachers of the same or of different disciplines thus facilitating opportunities for collaboration, open discussions, and reciprocal learning.

Taxonomies

The resources available on the portal are of the following types:

- Activities and Labs
- Assessments
- Audio Lectures
- Case Studies
- Full Courses
- Games
- Homework and Assignments
- Images and Illustrations
- Instructional Material
- Interactive Objects
- Lecture Notes
- Lesson Plans
- Readings
- References
- Simulations
- Syllabi
- Teaching and Learning Strategies
- Textbooks
- Unit of Study
- Video Lectures
- Others

They are classified according to the following 2 main (primary) classifications:

- Subject Areas
- Grade Level

Furthermore, the resources are categorized as the following:

- Material Type
- Provider
- Provider Set
- Author
- Conditions of Use

Each resource is also tagged (in a non-hierarchical way) to add more specific information about the content's subject area. Such additional meta-data helps users find additional resources of similar subject area.

Figure 13: Tagging and Metadata for OER Commons

Advanced Site Search and Navigation

The portal offers easy-to-use advanced search techniques so that users can refine their searches for OERs. Primary search results can be further refined according to:

- Education Standards
- Subject Area
- Education Level
- Material Type
- Conditions of Use
- Content Source

- Primary User (Teacher, Student, Administrator, Parent)
- Media Format
- Educational Use

Furthermore, primary and refined search results can be sorted according to:

- Resource Title
- Relevance
- Rating
- Date Added
- # of Visits

Evaluation and Rating

The portal offers series of rubrics to help gauge various aspects of quality, allowing an additional filter for sorting and another way to discover OERs. These kinds of ratings are essential, especially for educational institutions looking to recommend specific OER to their teachers.

Following are the set of 6 rubrics that the experienced teacher or instructional designer can use to evaluate and rate the OERs:

- **Quality of Explanation of the Subject Matter:** Used to rate how thoroughly subject matter is explained or otherwise revealed in the resource. Teachers might use object with whole class, small group, or individual student. Students might use this object to self-tutor.
- **Utility of Materials Designed to Support Teaching:** Applies to objects designed to support teachers in planning or presenting subject matter. Primary user would be teacher. Evaluates the potential utility of an object for the majority of instructors at the intended grade level.
- **Quality of Assessments:** Applies to objects designed to determine what a student knows before, during, or after a topic is taught. When many assessments are included in one object, the rubric is applied to the entire set.
- **Quality of Technological Interactivity:** Applies to objects that have a technology-based interactive component. Used to rate degree and quality of an object's interactivity. Interactivity broadly

means that the object responds to the user – the object behaves differently based on what the user does. This is not a rating for technology in general, but for technological interactivity.

- **Quality of Instructional and Practice Exercises:** Applies to objects that contain exercises to help foundational skills and procedures become routine. When concepts and skills are introduced, providing a sufficient number of exercises to support skill acquisition is critical. However, when integrating skills in complex tasks, as few as one or two may be sufficient. A group of practice exercises is treated as a single object, with the rubric applied to the entire set.
- **Opportunities for Deeper Learning:** Applies to objects that engage learners to: Think critically and solve complex problems. Reason abstractly. Work collaboratively. Learn how to learn. Communicate effectively. Construct viable arguments and critique the reasoning of others. Apply discrete knowledge and skills to real-world situations. Construct, use, or analyse models.

For teachers who do not feel confident enough to evaluate using the rubrics, they can leave comments about the OERs. User-generated evaluations are transformed into an overall rating score.

Contributing Resources and Authoring

Users can develop (create) resources, submit ones from the different locations on the web., or re-mix existing ones.

Figure 14: Contributing Resources to OER Commons

Usability – Support for People with Disabilities

The portal is built while taking into consideration accessibility for people with disabilities – mainly those with visual impairments. Users with special needs can make the text size bigger, increase the line spacing, and change the colours and contrast of the screen.

Collaboration and Co-Creation

Users (students, administrators, teachers) can create online groups and work together on utilizing, authoring, and discussing OERs. Furthermore, users can ask to join existing groups and participate in special interest topics related to OER and OEP.

Users can search for user groups according to the following:

- Group Subject (i.e. math, science,)
- Group Type (i.e. teachers, students,)
- Group Level (i.e. High School, Grade 8,)

Lessons Learnt and Transferability Opportunities

In addition to offering open educational resources, the portal facilitates sharing pedagogical ideas and provides equal access to educational content. The portal's objectives are mainly:

- Enriching students' learning experience
- Enabling teachers to implement more creative lessons and more engaging assignments using non-textual sources
- Giving teachers the ability to explain concepts in different ways opening up new perspectives for them to teach the lessons

Although this is pedagogically not radical, but students usually find it to be very helpful for their learning journey.

There are 2 ways for users to utilize the portal's OERs: simple and complex. In the simplistic form, users can use videos, images, animations, or simulations to enrich the lesson – and in this case the portal is regarded as a great source of ideas and imagination. In the complex form, teachers can utilize the 4Rs to develop OE resources in such a way so as to provide greater opportunities for research, inquiry, collaboration, and most importantly– differentiation – when preparing for their instruction.

Perhaps the most seamless way for educational institutions to foster a culture of building, sharing, and re–using digital resources is to consider this area as a subset of existing organizational strategies that are tacking the enhancement of teaching and learning methodologies using technology and/or digital literacy. So strategies that encourage the utilization of OERs can be blended within existing strategies.

Perhaps the most successful form of OER remixing and re–using is when teachers start to move towards open forms of teaching practice – i.e. team teaching, or, being more visible with the teacher’s practice on the Internet – so that other teachers as well as other players in the field can provide constructive feedback.

OER Strategy of the University of South Africa (UNISA)⁶⁶

Completed by Fabio Nascimbeni of Universidad Internacional de La Rioja, Spain.

Case Study Overview

Type of initiative: Institutional policy for OER adoption.

Country: South Africa.

Organization behind the initiative: University of South Africa (UNISA).

Type of organization: University.

Who funds the initiative?: UNISA.

History and Goals of the Initiative

The University of South Africa (Unisa) is the largest university on the African continent and attracts a third of all HE students in South Africa, making it one of the world's mega Universities. Unisa offers both vocational and academic programmes, many of which have received international accreditation, as well as an extensive geographical footprint, giving their students recognition and employability in many countries the world over.

Unisa is an open distance learning (ODL) university that presents academic offerings associated with both technological and traditional Universities. These include, but are not limited to, a combination of career-orientated courses usually associated with a university of technology, and formative academic programmes typically linked to a traditional university.

⁶⁶<http://www.unisa.ac.za/contents/unisaopen/docs/OER-Strategy-March-2014.pdf>

Unisa has more than 400,000 students from over 130 countries, offering a total of 839 formal qualifications (Unisa, 2016)⁶⁷. According to the student profile, 90.4% of these students are part-time students and only 9.6% are full-time students. Of all registered Unisa students, 8.5% were not South African residents (Unisa, 2014).

In 2014, the South African Ministry of Education issued a White Paper for Post-School Education and Training⁶⁸, adding impetus by a policy commitment to OER. The paper states that South Africa will create a post-school distance education landscape based on open learning principles. Further to this, the White Paper affirms that the Department of HE and Training (DHET) will support efforts that invest in the design and development of high-quality learning resources that should be made freely available as open resources.

Aligning with this White Paper, in April 2014 Unisa developed and published a new OER Strategy for the period 2014–2016, aiming to respond to the change that ICTs and OER are bringing in the areas of teaching and learning and the way in which content is developed and disseminated. The rationale of the initiative is that the vast quantities of content and teaching materials produced and used by Unisa, especially openly licensed content, have significant potential to enhance the teaching and learning experience of its students. Based on this, Unisa recognises that OER can therefore no longer be restricted to a marginal, socially acceptable, and ‘nice-to-have’ activity that a few academics dabble in on the fringes, but their use must be integrated into mainstream institutional teaching and learning activities if their true potential is to be harnessed in the process of pedagogical transformation.

Key Aspects of the Initiative

Before launching the policy, a preliminary analysis took place through a survey which examined knowledge of OER, Intellectual Property (IP) Rights and Licensing, participation in OER, barriers to OER and OER

⁶⁷ Unisa (2016). Facts and figures: student enrolments.

⁶⁸ <http://www.dhet.gov.za/SiteAssets/Latest%20News/White%20paper%20for%20post-school%20education%20and%20training.pdf>

in the Unisa context with a view to determining the stage at which the institution is in terms of adopting and engaging with the OER initiative. Further to this, the policy is based on a SWOT analysis, which is annexed to the policy document itself. In management terms, an OER coordinator within the institution was appointed, who took care of the development and approval of the university OER strategy.

The OER strategy is grounded on the understanding that Unisa has of the actual HE context. Quoting from the Strategy Document: *“If Unisa continues to base its business model on the selling of content, it will become a progressively less appealing place to study and may well be overtaken by other providers who are more proactive in rising to the challenge. Conversely, the systematic integration into its courses of content produced outside of Unisa and the subsequent releasing of openly licensed content will enable Unisa to focus squarely on improving its academic and administrative services.”*

The university leadership seems to have fully understood that OER are not a way to save costs in course production but a trigger to revisit the university strategy, putting emphasis on the provision of high-added value services rather than in content production. *“Open licensing will also require Unisa to develop and implement value-added services as part of its courses – services that will focus on building the competences of that make up gradueness.”* And *“(…) OER cannot be considered as marginal, socially acceptable, nice-to-have activities. They must be integrated into mainstream institutional processes if we wish to harness the true potential of OER in our transformation process and if the shift to this paradigm is to be economically and practically sustainable.”*

Emphasis on Openness

The emphasis of the OER strategy at Unisa is initially on the harnessing of available openly licensed resources, for the development of courseware: managing intellectual property of study materials, harnessing OER for teaching and learning and the subsequent releasing of openly-licensed materials, as well as on contributing towards global knowledge and the review of institutional policies to incorporate OER values.

Comprehensive Strategic Planning

What is important in the strategy is its comprehensive planning: the strategy is more than a statement of intent, but is underpinned by a set of guiding principles and strategic priorities that demonstrate cohesive thinking about capacity and institutional planning needs.

The five strategic priorities set out in the policy document are:

- Development of an effective management system for intellectual property.
- Establishment of an open licensing framework.
- Systematic integration of high quality, available OER as appropriate into courses and their subsequent release for use by others.
- Contribution to the global OER repository of resources.
- Evaluation and review of institutional policies to incorporate OER values and processes.

For each priority, clear actions were proposed with timeframes and with responsible teams within the university.

Research

Importantly, the policy has been accompanied by some research along the way, such as the 2015 study by De Hart et al.⁶⁹, aimed at providing baseline data on the uptake and current success of mainstreaming OER at an open distance learning institution with a view to determining the maturity of the staff in adopting and engaging with the OER initiative or the DTFL OER Evaluation Report.

Current Status of the Initiative

Following the launch of the policy in 2014, the initiative has slowed down a bit, because of the difficult context in South Africa and in the university (students uprisings, huge transition in Unisa from an effective institution based on paper to a fully online university, etc.).

The following work has been done:

- **Development of an effective management system for intellectual property.** This has not been done, since it was

⁶⁹ <http://www.irrodl.org/index.php/irrodl/article/view/2047>

discovered that university does not have an IPR strategy (in Unisa the university owns the copyright of content produced) and this should be the first thing done. Furthermore, to do this the university would have to go fully online, with a centralised storage location.

- **Establishment of an open licensing framework.** This has been developed and an IP policy is in place, but not yet approved, where Open has been set as a default (with the possibility for exceptions), with interim guidelines on open licensing in the Unisa context.
- **Systematic integration of high quality, available OER as appropriate into courses and their subsequent release for use by others.** This was done through web promotion, email, and a survey targeting teaching staff. A number of workshops have been run to build capacity, and a course on the LMS has been prepared on open licensing.
- **Contribution to the global OER repository of resources.** This has contributed to the OER Universitas (for example the Thomas Edison University (US) used one of the courses), and have started working on two MOOCs which build on a Unisa MOOC concept paper.
- **Evaluation and review of institutional policies to incorporate OER values and processes.** This has not yet been done.

Impact

In terms of impact, the policy has been useful to improve capacity building among teachers, to “open the minds” of the educators towards openness, and has prepared the ground for an institutional IPR policy, which will be a great achievement for Unisa.

Lessons Learned and Transferability Opportunities

The Unisa OER strategy is unique in a number of ways, and because of this can serve as an inspiration for other Universities which might want to implement a similar policy. First, it starts from top-level support: the Pro-Vice-Chancellor’s name heads the list of participants in strategy development. Second, the strategy is holistic and detailed, with clear actions, timeframes and responsibilities. Third, it is recognised that OER should be shaping the new business model of the university.

Fourth, emphasis is placed on the support that must be provided to students using OER.

One and a half years after the launch of the policy, some lessons learned can be reported, which should be taken into account by Universities interested in implementing a similar policy. First, continuous engagement of all stakeholders within the university is key: while the engagement was good from the teaching/learning side of the university, it was weaker from other components of the university. It is also important to keep all components (research, teaching, ICT, legal, etc) engaged after the policy has been launched. Second, a clear institutional IPR strategy must be developed before starting with the policy. Third, more than 2 years are needed to allow structural changes to take place within the institution.

In terms of future developments, it is important to notice that (also thanks to the policy) OER is embedded in the OER 2030 strategy; however, the expected big boost planned within the policy will not take place, at least for now, due to the conditions presented above.

Acknowledgements

Our thanks go to Mrs Kerry De Hart, former coordinator of OER within Unisa, for her help in creating this case study.

Open Humanities Press⁷⁰

Completed by Seddik Abdel Salam, Mohamed Belal, and Rasha Elshinety of Alexandria University, Egypt.

OPEN HUMANITIES PRESS

Case Study Overview

Type of initiative: Open access publishing initiative.

Country: UK.

Organization behind the initiative: Open Humanities Press (OHP).

Type of organization: Not-for-profit and Community Interest Company incorporated under the UK Companies Act 2006.

Who funds the initiative?: Mostly self-financed from the sale of hard copies.

History and Goals of the Initiative

Open Humanities Press (OHP) is an international scholar-led publishing initiative established in 2006 with the aim of tackling some of the current problems re publishing academic works in the humanities. In this regard, its mission is to “make leading works of contemporary critical thought freely available worldwide.” More specifically, OHP advocates Open Access, promotes intellectual diversity, improves the experience of academic publishing, explores new forms of scholarly collaboration and fosters a grass-root community concerned with these issues;⁷¹ all this with a special focus on the humanities.

OHP operates through seven thematic series of books and twenty affiliated journals: *Affirmations: Of The Modern, Australian Humanities*

⁷⁰ <http://www.openhumanitiespress.org/>

⁷¹ www.openhumanitiespress.org/about/principles-and-goals/

Review, Cosmos and History, Culture Machine, Culture Unbound, Electronic Book Review, Fast Capitalism, Fibreculture, Film-Philosophy, Filozofski vestnik, Glossator, Image [&] Narrative, Inflexions, International Journal of Žižek Studies, Parrhesia, Postcolonial Text, Religion and Gender, Teknokultura: Journal of Digital Culture and Social Movements, and Vectors.

Figure 15: Open Humanities Press screenshot

Key Aspects of the Initiative

OHP is possible thanks to the work of a broad network of individuals and communities engaged in editorial activities that are aligned with four of key principles:

Access: OHP is fully committed to maximising the free exchange of scholarly knowledge.

Scholarship: All OHP publications, both books and journals, are fully and rigorously peer reviewed.

Diversity: OHP aims to be internationally diverse in its content, editorial process and audience. Ensuring a diversity of critical approaches and voices is central to its mission.

Transparency. OHP's editorial policies are clear and publicly available.⁷²

The initiative is directed by Gary Hall, Sigi Jöttkandt and David Ottina, while relying on a wider editorial board whose members offer strategic advice and perform key editorial tasks. The editorial board includes leading figures in various humanities areas based at universities in Europe, Canada and the United States of America and it is organized in several groups dedicated to activities such as journals assessment, reviewing and approving book series proposals, performing and managing peer review, as well as editing the book series.

OHP has proved that scholars can self-organise and create high quality publications, without having to depend on commercial publishers, that are available to everyone who has access to the Internet.

Lessons learned and Transferability Opportunities

Universities in the S-M region could benefit from OHP pioneering practice. The editorial process developed by the OHP could transfer and maximize the impact of the movement of free exchange of scholarly knowledge.

- The project helps to raise awareness of open access publishing in the humanities, providing promotion and support to open access journals and books.
- It ensures globalisation and sustainability in collaboration with a wide network of scholars, librarians, technology specialists and publishers.
- The project also achieves attentiveness on the part of culturally and politically engaged readers.
- Diversity of globally knowledge leads to the development of the community and changes to attitudes.
- It makes it easier to publish highly specialised and experimental disciplinary research.
- Support of and extension to open access to scholarship in the humanities for free and for everyone.

⁷² www.openhumanitiespress.org/about/principles-and-goals/

- Increased research and publication requirements at traditionally teaching-centred Universities.
- Graduate students can ask to help with some of the work.
Key beneficiaries are: academic staff, students and public bodies.

Open Review Project⁷³

Completed by Katherine Wimpenny, Gemma Tombs, and Sarah Kate Merry of Coventry University, UK.

Open Education Group

Socially responsive research that concretely improves society

Case Study Overview

Type of initiative: Evidence-based review

Country: United States

Organization behind the initiative: Open Education Group

Type of organization: Research group

Who funds the initiative?: Current and past funders of the Open Education Group, (and we assume therefore are supporting the Review Project), are listed as:

- The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation⁷⁴
- The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation⁷⁵
- HASTAC⁷⁶
- The David O. McKay School of Education⁷⁷

Other partners are listed as:

- Lumen Learning (who support open courseware)⁷⁸
- CK-12 Foundation (who offer a dashboard of open access math and science learning objects)⁷⁹
- Mountain Heights Academy (a tuition-free, online public charter

⁷³ <http://openedgroup.org/review>

⁷⁴ <http://www.hewlett.org/>

⁷⁵ <http://www.gatesfoundation.org/>

⁷⁶ <https://www.hastac.org/>

⁷⁷ <http://education.byu.edu/>

⁷⁸ <http://lumenlearning.com>

⁷⁹ <http://www.ck12.org/student/>

school available to students from grades 7 – 12, who want to earn additional college credits, students who travel frequently, are pursuing a career, or like to learn on their own schedule in a safe environment, and any student who is struggling in their current educational situation).⁸⁰

History and Goals of the Initiative

The Open Education Group

The Open Education Group (Open Ed), behind the Review Project, is an interdisciplinary research group focused on improving education. In particular Open Ed seeks to conduct, review and share original, rigorous empirical research on the impact of OER adoption on a range of educational outcomes, and to design and share methodological and conceptual frameworks for studying the impact of OER adoption.

Primary researchers from the group include Lane Fischer, John Hilton III and David Wiley. Researchers are invited to join the group and support the organisation's work. Two current students are listed (although their role and contribution is not detailed). The Group have an Alumni, who may or may not be currently involved in The Review Project.

OER Research Fellowships are offered sponsored by the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation. 22 OER Research Fellows are currently being supported by the group from 19 US and Canadian HEIs.

John Hilton III is primary researcher / lead of the Review Project team, with Stacie Mason as an additional contributor.

Context for the Initiative

The context for the Review Project is influenced by the findings from the national survey of 2,144 US faculty members, which demonstrated a lack of faculty awareness about OER.⁸¹

In this survey, “proven efficacy” and “trusted quality” were cited by

⁸⁰ <http://www.mountainheightsacademy.org>

⁸¹ <http://www.onlinelearningsurvey.com/oer.html>

college professors as the two most important criteria for selecting teaching resources. With this in mind, the Review Project's ambition is to raise awareness about the efficacy and quality of OER so that academic staff in the US and Canada (and beyond) can appreciate what contribution OER can offer to teaching and learning.

The Review aims to identify all known empirical research papers that focus on the efficacy of OER, OER adoption, and teacher and student perceptions of such resources in practice.

Figure 16: Screenshot of the Open Review Project Homepage

The methodology and methods adopted for the review process detail the use of following inclusion criteria:

- Studies in which OER are the primary learning resource(s) compared against traditional learning resources.
- Studies published by a peer-reviewed journal, or as part of an institutional research report not sponsored by the organization adopting the OER.

As of June 2016, twenty-two studies had been reviewed:

- Ten studies exploring the proven efficacy of OER
- Nine studies exploring perceptions of OER
- Three studies that focused on both proven efficacy and perceptions of OER

All of the included studies are linked from the website, either as pre-print publication versions or as final published versions. An overview of each of the studies is presented, which includes the context of the study, study design, numbers of students involved, disciplinary area,

impact on learning, and comparison of OER to traditional learning methods; the detail depends upon the amount of information included in the original study. When mentioned, the Review Project also addresses the limitations in each study.

With regards to the findings of the Review Project, when mentioned, the main OERs referred to in the studies are open textbooks. An overall summary is provided, bringing together the main study findings, including future directions.

The project team welcome suggestions for any other known peer-reviewed efficacy or perceptions studies they have not reviewed, which can be shared via the comments section on the website, or by contacting the team directly.

Key Aspects of the Initiative

It is important to take into consideration that the Review Project is not an OER initiative *per se*, but an analysis of pre-existing empirical research on OER initiatives – namely studies focusing on the efficacy and/or perception of OER as compared to non-open learning resources. Consequently, the important lessons from this case study are distinctly different from others contained in this continuum. These lessons can be considered from two angles. Firstly, the lessons learned from the concept of the Review Project; meaning, what can be discovered about OER and its surrounding context based upon the focus on rigorous and evidence-based research. Secondly, the lessons learned from the content of the Review Project; meaning, what can be discovered about OER and its surrounding context based upon the studies reviewed.

As a project undertaken by the Open Education Group, the Review Project is supported by key individuals and organisations associated with OER, such as David Wiley and the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation.

OER vs Traditional Textbooks

The main positive lesson extracted from the Review Project is that learning outcomes achieved through the use of OER may be equivalent

to those achieved by means of traditional (i.e. commercial) textbooks. Therefore, it shows there are important opportunities for saving money while still using high quality content. As stated on the website of the project, the mainstream adoption of OER could help “save literally billions of dollars without any negative impact on learning.” The implications of this finding are particularly relevant to institutions, students and families within less affluent contexts.

Despite such a noteworthy contribution, the review does not focus on either the organisational changes or the funding models that made possible the creation of the OER under analysis in the original studies that were included into that meta-analysis. Likewise, it does not provide any other insights associated with the incentives or personal motivations for the development of OER, as the key focus is on the adoption stage. Given that the OER covered in the original studies are not fundamentally different from traditional textbooks, the Review Project does not look at innovative pedagogical practices either.

Empirical Evidence

Fueled by the idea that “everyone has the right to education”, as stated by the *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*, the OER movement is grounded on the belief that the creation of learning materials that can be accessed and repurposed for free will widen access to educational opportunities. However, the amount of empirical evidence substantiating that intuition is still rather limited. In this regard, initiatives like The Review Project are very much needed in order to galvanize the efforts already undertaken by organisations and individuals all over the world, as well as to secure long-term support from funding bodies devoted to fostering the common good.

Lessons Learned and Transferability Opportunities

As a relatively recent project with quite strictly-defined parameters, the Review Project does not have a large corpus of literature from which to draw conclusions (if that is the aim). It is also not entirely clear on the criteria employed for selecting and/or discarding studies from the project. However, it provides an overview of recent studies reporting on the use of OER in US Universities, although these are currently

limited in number. It could be useful as a model for the consideration and evaluation of similar experiences.

In terms of the conclusions drawn so far, it appears that the use of OER does not negatively impact students' engagement or performance, and that the lower costs compared to the use of paper textbooks could be a deciding factor in the adoption of OER.

A similar international, or S–M region focused, project could be valuable in providing an overview of the current practice and for encouraging the use of OER. It could also have broader implications: for example, if studies about current practice are evaluated by an external agency this helps to ensure that those studies are rigorously reported, and indeed could encourage more HE institutions to publish about their own experiences. However, it should be borne in mind that before this review could be replicated in the Arab world, it would be required to have more OER initiatives taking place in the region, followed by empirical research conducted on such initiatives.

Plateforme Pédagogique – Centre E-learning UIZ⁸²

Completed by Ahmed Almakari, Hassan El Oizgani, and Omar Baz of Université Ibn Zohr, Morocco.

Case Study Overview

Type of initiative: LMS (two platforms freely available to anyone)

Country: Morocco

Organization behind the initiative: Ibn Zohr University Agadir

Type of organization: Public institution of HE and research

Who funds the initiative?: Ibn Zohr University; Ministry of High Education

History and Goals of the Initiative

The policy of Ibn Zohr University (UIZ) in the field of e-learning seeks the development and dissemination of educational technologies which contribute to and reinforce the quality of education and improve the training offering of the university. UIZ has had a LMS since 2003.

The development of the cooperative programme Suisse Coselearn, initiated by the virtual campus – Campus Virtuel Marocain (CVM) – and coordinated by Ibn Zohr University, has allowed the development of many e-learning teachers and many AUF workshops organized in different establishments. This allowed the creation of an active community which today consists of international experts in the areas of NTICE.

⁸² <http://foadm1.uiz.ac.ma/>

From year to year UIZ has seen the number of students grow exponentially until today it has reached more than 110,000 students. This has justified the investment in the learning platform and dealing with this increasing growth. The objective is not to replace traditional courses with online courses but to reduce the work of teachers in the difficult conditions which are presented by a hybrid scenario in which online courses, (freely available) enrich traditional courses.

With the creation of the Centre of E-Learning, UIZ developed two teaching platforms – Moodle 1 and Moodle 2. The first houses 78 courses in different disciplines and with 15,000 registered students; the second has 22 courses and 6,000 students. In 2016, one online course from the Faculty of Law opened with over 4,000 registered students.

Figure 17: Screenshots of Plateforme Pédagogique’s Moodle 1 and Moodle 2

Key Aspects of the Initiative

True to its policy of encouraging the use of ICT in teaching and training, UIZ, through its E-learning Centre, organizes distance learning sessions via e-learning for teachers, researchers and PhD students at the end of their studies. The UIZ E-learning Centre manages all aspects of e-learning (open online courses, training and ODL – online and distance learning). The teaching platform is also used to train teachers by distance training in FEL e-learning, which is now in its fifth session (more than 200 teachers from Morocco and the Maghreb have attended and passed the modules of this training) and provides various activities including a priority area dedicated to the launch of lesson modules and/or courses. The objective of this axis is, after training, to provide students with a maximum of course modules and/or courses in e-learning.

Potential Candidates

- University lecturers interested in computing in general, and e-learning in particular. These are teachers who do not have the benefit of ad hoc training but who individually possess knowledge and skills in this area. In order to provide a maximum number of modules and/or courses in e-learning mode, we provide training to attract, motivate, persuade and encourage a maximum number of university teachers to put their course module on line. The goal is to achieve a maximum number of modules via e-learning.
- Teachers in TEC. This category has all of the advantages to profit from the training to improve their teaching, particularly taking into account the teaching conditions in TEC within the Faculties of Science, Law, and Arts and Humanities.

Contents Provided in FEL

Four tutored distance learning (open) courses are undertaken and assessed:

- Administration of Distance Learners (ACD)
- Learning and e-learning (PEL)
- Exploitation of Web resources (ERW)
- Development of learning resources (PRW)

There is also a mini training project during which the candidate has an online course module which shows all of the learning elements and techniques acquired during their training and which makes up the core of future online courses.

Working Method

The teacher who wants to participate in FEL training to put their course modules (openly available) online will benefit from support (see below). With regard to the working method, the following guidance is proposed:

- Choose one module (for example a chapter of the course) to put online. Ideally the teacher will put the majority, if not all, of the course online by the end of the training;
- Upload the module. For this work, the teacher will be given general guidelines on the educational approach (see below) and other supports in place. This phase can be considered a

pilot phase for the posting of work that will be conducted by the teacher during training;

- Embed this mode of learning online as part of the course. This module will be considered as a clean unit of the course which is delivered via e-learning, and not as a complement or a reissue of a class which has already been given face-to-face. If necessary (eg due to an equipment problem), students could follow this online training in a computer room;
- Evaluate this online learning module by developing a questionnaire;
- Make improvements and possible changes as required by this experiment. This procedure will lead to the validation of the first learning module, which could be integrated within the course. During this second phase, the teacher could create a second module based on the the working method proposed above.

Thus, after training, the teacher could have posted much of their course. At this stage, they could appropriate this process and complete the process independently. Later, the teacher could play the role of facilitator/trainer for colleagues from their university.

Educational Approach

The educational approach linked online to (an openly available) course or module of a course varies in presentation and in its structure.

Learning online ought to be the result of a harmonious complementarity between the technical aspects and the pedagogical aspects, giving priority to the latter. In fact, this approach refers particularly to theories of constructivism and social constructivism of learning.

As with all training, the educational approach should be appropriate to the stated objectives and to the teaching methods used (here, particularly ICT).

Lessons Learned and Transferability Opportunities

Over the past five years, the FEL initiative from the UIZ E-Learning Centre has trained more than 400 teachers within the university, and also from other national Universities and Maghreb (Tunisia and

Algeria). The success of this initiative is due, essentially, to the quality of the courses and the supervision by the tutors.

Another project which is in progress is the MOOC “Student Job,” which seeks to provide new students with the tools that will allow them to face their university career with educational, social and psychological equanimity. The MOOC is hosted on the EdX platform and will be operational next year.

Revista REDES (REDES Journal)⁸³

Completed by Isidro Maya Jariego, Daniel Holgado, and Fran Santolaya of Universidad de Sevilla, Spain and José Luis Molina of Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona, Spain.

Case Study Overview

Type of initiative: Open access scientific journal.

Country: Spain.

Organization behind the initiative: GRAFO, Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona and LRPC, Universidad de Sevilla.

Types of organization: Universities.

Who funds the initiative?: No funding: voluntary work by researchers and electronic resources provided by the university.

History and Goals of the Initiative

REDES is an international journal that publishes research results in the field of social network analysis. It focuses especially on empirical articles in Spanish and Portuguese on the structure of relationships, with the application of techniques of analysis and visualization of networks. Since its founding in 2002 it has published 30 numbers, grouped into 27 volumes. In 2005 the peer review system started. Currently it publishes two issues a year, in June and December, and it has a multidisciplinary editorial board of researchers from Europe and America.

In 1998 the XVIII Congress of the International Network for Social Network Analysis was held in Sitges, Spain. At that meeting a small group of Ibero–American researchers launched initiatives to promote training in the techniques of network analysis among Spanish–speaking

⁸³ <http://revista-redes.rediris.es/>

researchers. An e-mail distribution list, hosted on RedIRIS⁸⁴, as well as a website, were launched to exchange information, disseminate news, and share training resources.

The journal REDES was launched four years later. Since its inception the objectives of the journal have been (a) to promote academic research on network analysis in Spanish, by extension in Latin America, and (b) to become a space of scientific reference, following the consolidation of the e-mail list REDES and the website REDES as communication tools among Spanish and Latin-American researchers.

REDES is among the most relevant journals specializing in social network analysis, along with *Social Networks*, *Journal of Social Structure* and *Connections*. More recently there have been others linked to the 'network science', such as *Network Science*, covering statistical physics, simulation models and large networks databases. REDES is the only one published in Spanish. It has a wide circulation, especially Latin America. The website of the magazine has more than 1,000 visits a day, over 2,000 subscribers who receive each volume by the e-newsletter, and is supported by more than 800 subscribers of the REDES e-mail list. The countries with the most visits to the journal are Spain, Mexico, Colombia, Argentina, Venezuela, Chile, and the United States.

Since its inception it has been based on the principles of open knowledge and remote cooperative work. REDES publishes, disseminates and promotes network analysis. In its publications it combines quality empirical articles, translations of classics into Spanish, and the results of the early research of young researchers. REDES has been held in a community of practice that has endorsed the words of Antonio Machado⁸⁵: "In matters of culture and knowledge, you only lose what is saved; You earn only what is given"

⁸⁴ RedIRIS is the Spanish network which interconnects the computing resources of Universities and research centres. It is funded by the National R+D+i Plan of the Spanish Government.

⁸⁵ Antonio Machado (1875–1939) was a Spanish poet, who was born in Seville. He was part of the "Generation of 98" literary movement.

Figure 18: Screenshot of Revista Redes Homepage

Key Aspects of the Initiative

In the 2000s many academic journals began to develop an electronic version. That entailed the installation of a web site, defining access policies, adaptation of the publication format, and so on. All this represented a transition to a new management model for the journal, which affected the relationship with authors, readers and the academic community overall; and often it was combined with the continuation of the paper version. However, REDES has been an electronic journal since its inception, which has not gone through this transition process but was originally intended for digital media.

Development of Community

In fact, there was already a virtual Ibero–American community of researchers around the REDES e–mail list before the launch of the journal. The community of practice of academics and professionals interested in social network analysis exchanged information and training resources in this area. In the web REDES they were also gathering and sharing workshops and training materials, translation of technical articles, information on meetings and conferences, demonstrations of software for analysis and visualization of networks, and so on. Thus the e–mail list, with logistical support from the web REDES, functioned as a learning community that facilitated the spread of network analysis in Spanish.

The community of reference of the journal is organised into three segments, corresponding to: the REDES e–mail list (800 subscribers),

users that receive a notification with each new volume published (more than 2000 subscribers), and other readers who access the journal to locate specific content. The community has a core–periphery structure: it is organised around a very active and connected core, exchanging content on network analysis; but it is open, in successive concentric circles of activity, both to pre–doctoral researchers who are starting in the area as well as to occasional readers. This community has developed from the inside out, from the core to less active participants.

The leadership of the administrator of the REDES e–mail list was instrumental to the constitution of an effective community of practice. Especially in the early stages, the administrator provided content, answered questions raised in the list, proposed training activities, and had a central role in the exchanges that occurred in it. Maintaining a minimum level of activity – at least one message a week – gave continuity and promoted participation. Over time, the dynamics of reciprocity and the generalised exchange model built a core of active participants.

This background of open interaction, the sense of community, and collaborative learning gave support to the launch of the journal REDES. During the first years it worked as an informal system of publication of communications in congresses and meetings related to network analysis (2002–2005). In 2005 the peer review system was implemented and began to improve the quality standards of the publication. Since then the journal has improved its publishing format, has implemented the Open Journal System (OJS) for the management of manuscripts, and has been incorporated into scientific databases, improving the indicators of impact. In the period 2013–2016 it received 150 original manuscripts. The journal receives on average 21.43 original articles per semester. In the last 7 numbers, which corresponds to a range of two and a half years, the rejection rate was 31.7%.

Promotion of Analytical Techniques

The magazine is fulfilling the role of diffusing social network analysis in the Latin American academic community. The translation of high impact scientific articles expands the potential audience of recent

research and facilitates the socialisation of researchers that are introduced to the area. At the same time, REDES is a publishing medium for junior researchers. Thus it maintains its original purposes of the promotion of network analysis in Spanish. The audience of the journal has been defined by the fact that the publication is in Spanish, and complementarily in Portuguese. It also has an international editorial team, most of them from Latin America. One of the incentives to participate in REDES has been learning the techniques for relational data analysis. Software analysis and visualisation of networks are complex. The conceptual basis of the indicators of centrality and structural properties require considerable time for familiarisation and training. The web REDES has provided educational materials to learn the techniques. The e-mail list, meanwhile, has served as a guide for novice researchers, solving the doubts that arise during the research process and data analysis.

Voluntary Work

From an organisational point of view, the journal has been based on voluntary work. Although it has some connection with the *International Network for Social Network Analysis* – many of the editorial board members are part of this scientific association – it has worked independently and autonomously since its foundation. In fact, somehow the magazine has served as a bridge, connecting the community of Latin American researchers with the international community. Communication through the list REDES has facilitated the development of weak ties and alliances of academic collaboration. The list REDES came before the boom of Internet forums and was one of the pioneers in Spanish-speaking academia through RedIRIS.

Creative Commons

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⁸⁶ <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>

Lessons Learned and Transferability Opportunities

The REDES journal has functioned as an OER for the community of Latin American researchers interested in social network analysis. The case illustrates the combination of an email list, a web of OER, and an open access scientific journal to support a collaborative learning community. In the collective creation of knowledge, in a bottom-up process, note the following factors:

1. The journal originates in the digital environment and is based on the prior existence of a virtual community of practice of researchers.
2. The community of practice benefits from an open and active leadership, which promotes the dynamics of exchange and reciprocity among participants.
3. The initiative is based on voluntary work, as well as collaborative networks of weak ties, with a low institutional profile and a diffuse connection with the International Network for Social Network Analysis.
4. REDES is an open community, with very active members that form a core-periphery structure, which leads to the development of strong relationships and a strong sense of community.
5. Incentives for participation are organised around learning techniques of data analysis, the translation of classics of network analysis and other elements of scientific legitimacy.
6. REDES is a bridge of Latin American researchers with the international community.

In the case of the journal REDES we have illustrated that, in the electronic media, audience and impact of the contents do not depend only on the number of followers but also on the interaction dynamics and structure of relationships in the community of practice. Open access facilitates the dissemination of research. Below we summarise the above key issues.

Key aspects	Description
Originally designed for digital media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prevents the costs of adaptation to electronic media. Designed for an interactive medium, with respect to users and readers
The virtual community of practice precedes the founding of the journal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The journal was created in response to the needs of researchers. There is a dynamic of interaction and organization of the community prior to the establishment of the journal.
Core-periphery structure of the virtual community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is a cohesive structure and a group of active participants who generate content appropriate for the community.
Leadership of the manager of REDES e-mail list	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weekly generation of content. Increase and reinforce participation in the list. To promote exchange and generalised reciprocity.
Incorporation of the peer review system and improvement of the quality standards of the journal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved publishing format, incorporation into databases. Accreditation process of the journal.
Role of dissemination of network analysis in Spanish	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publication of novel work, translation of classics, links with the international scientific association.
Incentive of learning the techniques of network analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training in analysis techniques. Demonstration of network analysis and visualisation software.
Based on volunteer work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborative networks of weak ties. Publishing with own resources.
CC License 4.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Copying, distribution and transformation of the material is allowed. Attribution is required, citing the original source and material.

Table 5: Lessons learned from Revista Redes

UC@MOOC⁸⁷

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Case Study Overview

Type of initiative: Repository of learning objects, open courseware, platform inspired from MOOC (Massive Open Online Course).

Country: Morocco.

Organization behind the initiative: Cadi Ayyad University (UCA), Marrakech, Morocco.

Type of organisation: HE institution.

Who funds the initiative?: Cadi Ayyad University.

Data sources used for the case study: Platform, videos of courses, interviews, course documentation, conferences.

History and Goals of the Initiative

The issue of massification in higher education is of great concern in Africa. The use of distance and open learning tools provides an avenue for both access to and participation in higher education. UC@MOOC is a pedagogical innovation that has been developed to address the effects of massification which have created constraints at Cadi Ayyad University (UCA), as well as other African universities, over the last five years. UC@MOOC aims to address massification and to overcome the language difficulties of students. Further, through this project, we want to reduce academic

⁸⁷ <http://mooc.uca.ma>

failure and student drop-out rates, and deliver new, improved, training and learning. UC@MOOC has existed at UCA since 2013. At the beginning of this innovative project the main target was to resolve the problem of over-large classes at the university. Following three years of development work, the platform now includes more than 300 scripted sequences of videos (courses) and covers a number of educational fields in French, Arabic, and English.

The online posting of free content allows students to deepen knowledge autonomously and independently, does not require as many resources, and keeps production costs relatively low. UC@MOOC also helps teachers to save time. The idea is not to suppress face-to-face courses but to offer hybrid teaching experiences, or even flipped classroom opportunities in some cases, whilst keeping teachers at the centre of this educational innovation. It is hoped that similar initiatives can be developed to support other Moroccan HEIs also dealing with the growing number of students in the south of the country. UC@MOOC is an educational platform designed to provide Moroccan students with open access to quality learning resources. The educational content is adapted to the Moroccan context, and is run by professors at UCA, with a focus on supporting students in their integration into higher education. The platform design allows students to contact their teachers as many times as they want and thus creates a real interaction that will allow students to deepen their knowledge independently. The UC@MOOC library now includes a multitude of courses in different disciplines in audio-visual form.

The main objectives of UC@MOOC are:

1. The reduction of university dropout (25% in the first year)
2. Mitigating the effects of massification
3. Improving the internal efficiency of the UCA
4. Support with language difficulties.

<http://mooc.uca.ma>

Figure 8: Screenshot of UC@MOOC

The main content of UC@MOOC are podcasts, courseware and videos that offer open and free access to the resources. According to interviews with students, this way of displaying courses is useful and helps them to progress in their studies. Additionally, teachers are very happy to provide their content online, which adds a real value to their courses. Overall, the initiative contributes to reducing the consequences of having a large number of students in the classrooms, and provides these courses to students anytime and anywhere.

Key Aspects of the Initiative

Relevance to theUCA Context

The UC@MOOC strategy was designed according to the needs of the institution. This meant that individuals were motivated to engage in and complete the project.

There were three main ways in which the UC@MOOC project was seen as a solution to challenges at UCA. These were:

1. Massification of HE: UCA has 85,000 students, increasing by 12% per year. On average, there is one teacher to 48 students, and 160 students apply for every 100 places at the institution.
2. Language difficulties: The provision of courses in English, Arabic and French is designed to help students increase their language capabilities.
3. Methodological difficulties: UC@MOOC was seen as a way to reduce student failure and drop-out rates.

Strategies and Policies

UC@MOOC is part of the digital pedagogy implementation strategy of the UCA. In recent years the internet has become integrated into all aspects of our society. Its use is now becoming essential and has had

a significant impact on education and training, influencing all teaching positions. Digital pedagogy opens up new dimensions in relation to sharing knowledge, both for the teacher and the learner. Similarly, its use opens up new communicative possibilities in relation to teacher-student contact, which can be extended.

Thanks to the expansion of the internet, the very structure of our education system is being challenged. UCA, as a national leader, is therefore committed to working with its staff and students in an ever-changing educational environment. UC@MOOC should ensure:

1. More suitable and effective teaching approaches;
2. Better management of different needs in schools and universities;
3. Self-directed and collaborative learning in class;
4. Teaching students according to their needs and abilities;
5. New teaching approaches; and
6. Digital tools for learning.

Organisational Changes

Implementing digital pedagogy is a preferred choice at UCA in the context of massification. The problem of over-large classes in Moroccan universities not only creates difficulties in human resources management, but also problems of employment in the absence of an education and training system which is adequate to the needs of the local economy. Thus strategic planning to manage both the growth in student numbers for 2020, and new solutions in the modes of transmission are required, and should be a national priority in education. The use of infrastructure construction projects may not be the only solution in the medium and long term. The training should also provide innovative solutions to assist in reconsidering our vision of HE.

However, digital education requires students to have a high level of organization and motivation. At the university, the contact with the teacher and discussion with other students remains an important element in a university course. The administration of digital content in the form of course materials, tutorials and lab work gives students a better level of integration and support. This is a revolution that could change the modes of learning in HE.

At the Heart of Pedagogical Innovations

UC@MOOC has revolutionized the relationship between teacher and student. Now with advance courses or via the web or DVD, students have the opportunity to navigate through the different chapters of courses, illustrated with relevant images, and to better assimilate and understand the material.

Furthermore, this method allows the student to follow her/his lecture in better conditions than in the over-crowded lecture hall, just as it allows the teacher to work under different conditions. This means that, in lectures, the teacher can devote more time to the explanation and to questions from students who have already viewed the course via the web or on DVD. In terms of the learning resources produced, they are available:

- on the MOOC platform, which is freely accessible to all students;
- as scripted audio-visual materials;
- in face-to-face classes.

The learning resources produced are supported by:

- Studios equipped with basic equipment;
- Screenwriting support for lecturers; and
- Fast, efficient and affordable post-editing.

At UCA we are also learning from the project teams' implementation of innovative pedagogy. For example, certain courses are tailored to a more hybrid approach (ENCG, FJES) whilst others offer a flipped classroom teaching approach, as seen in the Faculty of Science Semllia. Such a layout is shown in Figure 20:

Figure 20: Pedagogical approaches adopted at UCA

The Point of view of “Infrastructure & Technologies”

UCA has launched, in partnership with Microsoft, a major project to cover Marrakech institutions with broadband Internet via the latest wireless technologies. The launch of the project was completed in June 2015. In addition to Microsoft, the project partner Telecom Operator and the National Agency of Telecommunications Regulation in Morocco are involved in the establishment of an infrastructure (data centre, optical fibre, wireless access points, etc.) to network all of the institutions located in Marrakech. A total of 180 Wi-Fi access points, spread over nine institutions, have been established and are operational, supporting up to 170,000 users. The project also includes the establishment of radio access points called TV White Space (TVWS). Users can also benefit from a suite of free services (e.g. Outlook, Office 365, One Drive) for better collaboration and productivity.

Lessons learned and Transferability opportunities

UC@MOOC was launched on April 2013, based on an individual initiative of a team of colleagues who agreed to record their courses in audio-video format with scripting, in order to provide the students with open access to institutions (license for semester S1 and S2). Following this, and the monitoring/evaluation of these courses by students, UCA has attracted the attention of the entire scientific community of the university, which has now found a meaningful way to help to address several challenges that the university faces today, i.e. massification, language barriers, and student drop-out rates.

Following approximately 18 months of production and distribution, the first results have been most positive in terms of interest in the platform UC@MOOC, including the achievements presented below:

- 17 conferences
- 6 full TD
- 5 full TP (Lab. Activities)
- 70 full courses
- 60 teachers/researchers involved
- 300+ course units available online
- 150+ hours of content available online
- 30+ current recordings or wait and mount.

Finally, a total of 150 complete courses are scheduled to run by the end of 2016. The courses started with lectures, followed by tutorials (with their answers) and finally practical work. Some of this content now offers interactivity between teachers and students.

Below is a non-exhaustive list of the statistical results registered by the platform UC@MOOC:

- Number of views > 2,555,412
- View time > 13,832,360 min (\approx 26 years of viewing duration)
- Average length of viewing is 5 min 28 s
- Shares >9,368
- Videos in playlists 4,008
- Number of subscribers is 17,248.

The ultimate aim is to provide 400 online modules via the UC@MOOC platform for optimal coverage across all UCA faculties. UC@MOOC is, beyond reasonable doubt, an important opportunity to enhance the quality of education delivery in our universities. It is an innovative project, offering new, active and effective learning and teaching situations to be adapted for students. Furthermore, the search for innovation and quality is not only the responsibility of teachers, and as a result students are now taking ownership of co-curating these resources to gain independence with benefits for all. And we came to discover, with the help of their ways of using the resources, the most convenient use.

UC@MOOC plays an important role in opening and leading our university, not only for students of Moroccan universities, but also for visitors from other African universities, and beyond. In addition, because the courses are open, opportunities for learning are offered to new and different audiences. UC@MOOC's production procedures are simple and less expensive, and its positive pedagogical values grant an easily mobile tool for use in S-M countries.

UC@MOOC received the National Governance Day's Award, organized by the Moroccan Ministry of Higher Education, in June 2016.

Recommendations for the Next Phases of OpenMed

Recommendations for the Next Phases of OpenMed

As this compendium has shown, there is a diverse and rapidly-growing interest in OER and OEP in the South-Mediterranean region with exciting influences upon teaching and learning practices. The case studies, profiling practices within the MENA region and beyond, have included the use of MOOCs, learning platforms / repositories, and open access publishing initiatives.

The studies highlight the benefits of opening up education so that Arab learners, researchers, teaching staff, and all those involved in education can engage in mutually enriching educational experiences, not only at a local and national level, but as globally connected learners and contributors.

It is important to recognize the local, national, and international influences upon these practices. For example, if online education is not recognized by national educational authorities, then those institutions face a unique set of challenges in relation to OER and OEP. In the set of recommendations that follow, a range of issues are presented, prompted by the case studies, which require consideration in-context.

Further, in realizing the ambition of the OpenMed project, these recommendations will also be of interest when considering the subsequent work packages of the project.

The recommendations have been considered under the following five themes:

1. Top-Down and Bottom-Up Implementation
2. Supporting Staff in Using and Integrating Open Practices and Open Resources
3. Collaborative Creation in Communities of Practice
4. Enhancing the Quality of Student Learning
5. Licensing of OER Content.

Each is considered in turn, along with relevant excerpts from the interviews conducted with experts in the field of OER and OEP⁸⁸.

1. Top-Down and Bottom-Up Implementation

High-level policies, such as the UNISA OER Strategy, may not be possible in contexts where online learning is not accredited by national higher education bodies. Nonetheless, (university) leadership and support is required in developing policies and strategies, with emphasis on the provision of high-quality OER, to strengthen institutional OEP delivery.

Developing multi-stakeholder governance is suggested, such as that seen in project Jorum, which has enabled their national repository, access to which was initially limited to UK registered teachers, to become an open platform providing worldwide users the possibility to find, share and discuss thousands of learning materials.

Making inroads in OEP requires both top-down and bottom-up approaches, with the recognition that initiating such practices can be achieved through taking small steps, seeking support from OER champions, and finding local, like-minded individuals.

Tel Amiel, UNESCO Chair in OER at UNICAMP and Researcher at NIED/UNICAMP:

“[The] focus is towards working with governmental agencies and other groups to help build open educational practices that identify local challenges and try to cater training to these contexts. So we are trying to build smaller scale policies and take these challenges into consideration and try to promote some ambassadors around OER in different parts of the country and in different agencies. So less than wide ranging and large, state or government or a municipal framework for OER, what we are trying to do is to look at small agencies

⁸⁸ The process of identifying and conducting interviews with experts from the field of OEP and OER is explained in Appendix 1.

and help them change multiple aspects of their practice, so that we don't have the large challenges of implementing a really great educational policy that looks really good on text but won't have the subsidies or the energy or the time or the people to actually get implemented in a large scale."

In addition, **being clear about the justification for the provision of high-quality OEP and OER in HEIs is required.**

Paul Stacey, Associate Director of Global Learning, Senior Project Manager with Creative Commons, US:

"If you want to have impact and generate scale you really need to think clearly about the strategic purpose, so what is the social goal, or the economic goal, or the innovation goal that the open education initiative is trying to achieve? And being really clear about that upfront, and the reason why you are pursuing it."

Given the massification of HE, for example in Morocco where the population is distributed in rural areas, it is of interest to note how UIZ buildings are geographically distributed across 52% of the country, in Ouazarzate, Laayoune, Guelmim, and Dakhla. From their distributed branches UIZ's commitment to reaching learners living in rural areas is evident, alongside their developing practices in open and distance methods of education.

Investment in infrastructure will ease process development and ways to transition materials and programmes, and the work of UC@MOOC offers a useful example of this.

Implementing and building strategies to support OEP means **getting organised according to local need:**

Jean-Claude Guédon, Professor at the Department of Comparative Literature, with focus on Internet Culture, Digital Humanities and Open Access Movement, University of Montreal, Canada:

“It might be useful in the first instance to create a common database of all the topics they want to cover, and then they could take and organize, according to their needs, a subset from that general database, and create the kinds of tools, the kinds of textbooks and the kind of teaching tools that correspond to the needs of their educational laws, demands, systems, issues, so that you can take advantage of economies of scale on the one hand and yet respond to specific local needs on the other.”

As highlighted by Edraak, **getting courses accredited and recognized is a step-by-step process** currently underway **for promoting OEP as a reputable form of learning**. It will be interesting to see the impact of awarding credit hours on the pilot course accreditation scheme that German Jordan University has arranged with Edraak, to offer one of its general elective courses to be run via the Edraak platform.

Building on and using what is already out there, as in OER Commons Arabic, is a fundamental aspect of the open education movement, yet, as the next point goes on to consider, **upskilling staff to get onboard** is also required.

2. Supporting Staff in Using and Integrating Open Practices and Open Resources

In the foreword to this compendium, Professor Sana El Harbi talked about the importance of raising awareness, changing attitudes, and training staff in the use of OER and OEP. The case studies presented in this compendium have demonstrated how some have addressed this. For example, Plateforme Pédagogique is encouraging teaching staff to put their courses online and using OER to train staff across national borders in how to use OER.

However, as the case studies in the compendium acknowledge, OE is not merely about developing learning resources for open access with appropriate licensing, but finding ways to **integrate OER with official academic learning resources**.

Daniel Burgos, Pro–Vice–chancellor for Research & Technology and UNESCO Chair on eLearning at the International University of La Rioja (UNIR):

*“We can have meaningful, useful, high–quality materials over the Internet and in repositories, free of charge, free to re–use, and that is all fine, and we have all the academic programmes with their official learning resources, including academic texts, and that is all fine, but nowadays when the student comes into the classroom it is quite naive to think he can only learn from the teacher, he can only learn from the professor, or even from his peers because actually he has maybe one third or less of his life inside the classroom, but what happens with all the other time? Learning happens everywhere, anytime and nowadays even more with all the social networks and resources available on YouTube etc. and of course from other open additional resources such as MOOCs. So we need to think how we can use these contents in a meaningful way to support student learning – **we need a means of coming back and forth with the content from the academic programmes to the open educational resources so that they can establish a fruitful collaboration**, and so we will get the best of both, and as such a very useful and meaningful support to improve student performance and to improve their interaction, their deep learning and also their analysis of the data and the information.”*

Thus supporting staff in OEP is not merely about shifting focus in developing ways for students to access online learning resources, rather, it is the importance of not viewing official classroom learning materials as separate entities. Problem–solving ways to integrate and weave the two together are required. Further, OE should also involve wider discussion about the benefits of open research, open publishing and other considerations for opening up our education ecosystems.

Cristóbal Cobo, Director of the Center for Research, Ceibal Foundation, Uruguay, Associate Researcher at the Oxford Internet Institute, University of Oxford, UK:

*“I really encourage you to dive into the open educational practice but also to think that **openness has to go far beyond offering contents publicly available**. Because ‘Openness’ opens questions for other possibilities, there are open questions about how to evaluate, open questions about where do we teach, and how can we better combine knowledge from different disciplines and from different backgrounds.”*

A key recommendation is that any **department or institution interested in using OER and OEP must prioritize staff development**. Time must be made available for staff to learn about the benefits of OER in their contexts, and case studies such as the [Open Review Project](#) can help with this. **Staff need incentives to get on board**. Developing communities of practice to support OEP is also recommended, as the next theme goes on to explore.

3. Collaborative Creation in Communities of Practice

As this compendium is focused upon openness in education, any list of recommendations must highlight the advantages of sharing and collaboration within the institution, within local and national contexts, and internationally. We recommend that **a collaborative approach to the creation of OER is adopted**. If teachers are not already working with technicians to create and administer OER, then they must do. Similarly, technicians must reach out to teachers in their institution with interest in creating OER and adopting OEP. In [Discover Palestine](#), for example, the project team included geography, history, and culture experts, instructional designers and multimedia specialists: however, the creators of Discover Palestine reflected that their team would have benefited from including others with expertise in creating MOOCs.

Teresa McKinnon, Principal Teaching Fellow, Certified Member of the Association for Learning Technology, SFHEA, University of Warwick, UK:

“When educators want to become open educational practitioners they have quite a tricky journey to navigate as they move their practice towards the digital, creating the content,

*navigating digital spaces, and understanding the affordances of those spaces. Familiarization can be time consuming, and there are many barriers along the way. What we really need are ways of connecting with other educators to learn from one another and ways of recognizing the efforts that have been made in the professional development that happens. The power of connecting educators around their specific needs within and across communities gives opportunities for professional development which hasn't yet been fully recognized or realized. **Steps are needed to recognize the effort and focus required to work effectively in a digital world**, especially one that is changing so rapidly.... We need to help educators to connect, and to curate the learning resources that are out there, and to learn from each other about the principles of re-mixing and re-purposing and the sustainability of teaching."*

If the level of expertise is not available in the institution, or if people in the institution are reluctant to adopt OER, then **OER advocates should collaborate outside of the institution.**

As can be seen with [Revista REDES](#) the development of an e-mail list was instrumental to the constitution of an effective community of practice. Such an open community, with active members forming a core-periphery structure, can lead to the development of strong relationships and a strong sense of community, bringing together experts in the fields alongside newcomers and novices.

The [OER Commons Arabic](#) portal provides an example of a rich platform for teachers to contact and connect with other teachers of the same or of different disciplines, thus facilitating opportunities for collaboration, open discussions, and reciprocal learning.

Paul Stacey, Associate Director of Global Learning, Senior Project Manager with Creative Commons, US:

*"I think **Open Education has its biggest potential when it involves a consortium of institutions collaborating together rather than something happening within just one***

institution. *So when I think of the MENA or Mediterranean region I would be asking to what extent can we form a consortium of institutions across the region who all agree to collaborate and work on this open education initiative together, sharing resources, sharing practices, and not only sharing them but using them collectively within their own specific environment.”*

As evident in [Open Humanities Press](#), globalization and sustainability can occur when working in collaboration with a wide network of scholars, librarians, technology specialists and publishers. Such collaborations can lead to exciting, new and creative works.

Jean–Claude Guédon, Professor at the Department of Comparative Literature, with focus on Internet Culture, Digital Humanities and Open Access Movement, University of Montreal, Canada:

“[T]here are communities of mathematicians and maths teachers in France that have banded together and have created textbooks for various levels of learning, and these textbooks reflect the demands of the national educational system, whilst at the same time reflecting the deep knowledge of the real situation of teaching in the classroom by teachers. And these textbooks are sometimes produced by communities of 200 – 300 professors working in a distributed manner, correcting each other, and making in the end much better text books that what you can have with just two, three or four authors. And that sort of situation appears to me to be particularly important for developing and emerging nations, because they have teachers, they know the conditions in which they are working much better than someone who is producing a textbook in New York or London, and they know how to really target their audiences at the right level and they have a product they can modify themselves.”

Such networking can offer positive benefits at an individual level as well:

Maha Bali, Associate Professor of Practice at the Center for Learning & Teaching at the American University in Cairo (AUC):

“Open education as a practice starts with myself as I think about my practice and my teaching. I think about it aloud on Twitter and on my blog. You know if I’m thinking of what I’m going to do next semester I’ll write something on my blog and I’ll solicit feedback from other people. I’ll go and look at what other people around the world are doing from their blogs, from articles online, and then I change my project ideas and assignment ideas based on feedback that I get from people. A lot of the best ideas I have are ideas that came from someone else.”

Peter Suber, Director of the Harvard Office for Scholarly Communication, Director of the Harvard Open Access Project, Senior Researcher at the Berkman Klein Center for Internet & Society, and Senior Researcher at the Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition:

“I began by putting my previously published work on my website and right away I started to get correspondence from colleagues at a higher level and a higher quality than I had ever gotten before, in other words people were actually reading it and taking it seriously and taking the time to write to me about it and of course that’s why I published it in the first place – I wanted it to have some impact with my colleagues. And I realised I got this impact more from these online versions of my work than the original print versions, and this was early in the mid 80’s, and I looked around for other scholars who were doing the same thing and I realised that the web was a serious platform for scholarship and I didn’t find too many people, but I found a few, and every time I found somebody I corresponded with them and I would broadcast to other friends that someone else was getting it, and eventually I turned this into a newsletter in which I would notice examples of people using the web for serious scholarship, and I wrote that newsletter for over 10 years”

Developing context-related learning resources, profiling the scholarship occurring in the S–M region, is not only about the value of content transmission, but can also serve to inspire and evoke sharing, collaboration and social commitment, all features befitting a global knowledge-sharing society.

4. Enhancing the quality of student learning

As evidenced from the Open Review Project, learning outcomes achieved through the use of OER may be equivalent to those achieved by means of traditional (i.e. commercial) textbooks. Therefore, **important opportunities for saving money are achievable through developing non-commercial OER while still using high quality content.** The implications of this are particularly relevant to institutions, students and families within less affluent contexts where accessing commercial content can be incredibly difficult and expensive.

Rory McGreal, UNESCO/Commonwealth of Learning Chair in OER, Professor in the Centre for Distance Education at Athabasca University, Canada. Director of the Technology Enhanced Knowledge Research Institute, Co-Editor of International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning, and Founder of the OER Knowledge Cloud:

“I suggest to you that we move away from commercial content and start using more and more open education resources. Legal restrictions reinforce the technological protection measures and they basically say that you cannot legally do what you are being prevented from doing and with other additions. For example, you are not allowed to share your materials, so if a student has a new textbook in his or her computer they cannot share with other students and these are very restrictive elements that we as educators cannot afford to live with. That is why I suggest to you and I am proactively promoting that we move away from commercial content and start using more and more open educational resources. This is a very important consideration because it becomes almost impossible for educators to use commercial content in the

ways they would like. There are many ways of mixing, mashing, remixing, augmenting, removing content, localizing content, and we should be able to do that, and OER are the way we can do that.”

Peter Suber, Director of the Harvard Office for Scholarly Communication, Director of the Harvard Open Access Project, Senior Researcher at the Berkman Klein Center for Internet & Society, and Senior Researcher at the Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition:

*“When I was a teacher I always gave away my course materials to my students... you don’t write course content to keep to yourself, you write it to share.... After a time I had a lot of experience in my own courses and new teachers who didn’t have a lot of experience on the same topics would use my hand-outs as a quick way to get started ... **I think all teachers should share with everybody, and that means students will benefit, other teachers will benefit and if you care about this it means that you will benefit too, as your name and your knowledge and your reputation for knowledge will also spread, there’s no drawbacks whatsoever. ... I don’t think teachers in the MENA region need any special encouragement for this, I think all teachers already share this inclination, they already see the value of doing it, I would just remind them, remember your vocation as a teacher, you only help people if you share your knowledge, not if you keep it to yourself”***

OER can support anytime, anywhere learning, offering new communication possibilities between teachers and students, as exemplified in [UC@MOOC](#) where the administration of digital content in the form of course materials, tutorials, and labs offers students a better level of integration and support despite the challenging teacher–student ratio. Enhancing the learning relationship by offering means by which students can access support, as often as they require it, at the times it best suits their needs, has resulted in reduced attrition rates, and boosted student satisfaction ratings.

OEP should engage students as co-creators. The example of crowd-teaching and promoting student-parent-teacher collaborations as exemplified in [Nafham](#) (with incentives for quality resources submitted), provides a useful co-creation model, transferable into HE domains, especially in terms of students developing educational resources for other learners. As parents and teachers involved in Nafham acknowledged, new talents and engagement in learning emerged amongst the pupils when they were offered the opportunity to submit teaching resources for other learners.

Maha Bali, Associate Professor of Practice at the Center for Learning & Teaching at the American University in Cairo (AUC):

*“I ask my students to find their own resources whether by searching Google or by meeting people on Twitter ... an example of a particular assignment that I give is the ‘Twitter Scavenger Hunt’; and the assignment is to give my students an educational game design, so it’s a game that’s going to teach them how to learn to use Twitter and at the same time it emphasizes the importance of Twitter for connectivity... and I ask people I know online what they know about educational game design, or have they students who are learning something similar who could interact with my students, and I let them know what time I’m meeting to do the activity with the students, and the students go ahead and play the game and they also get to meet people along the way, and by meeting those people they get to ask questions, and **they get to know that I’m not the only resource they have, and that opens up my classroom so that the students don’t feel like they’re talking just to each other, and to me, but they’re actually getting advice from others outside of the classroom, whether they are Egyptian educational gamers, are named designers from all over the world, and they get really, really excited when someone responds to them on Twitter that they’ve never heard of before.**”*

Issues of quality need to be carefully considered and managed. [OER Commons Arabic](#) provides an interesting example of ways to

build in quality mechanisms for OER with the use of a rubric on their portal that enables teachers accessing the resources to rate their contents on their usability and valued added features. For example, the rubric covers how well subject matter is explained, the technological interactivity of resources, the opportunities for deep learning, etc. Further, the portal provides a means for learners to adapt the OER in terms of font, colour and contrast etc., to enable accessibility for people with disabilities. OER need to be accessible to meet a wide range of learner needs.

Edraak similarly provide an example of how they have considered issues of access to OER to ensure a quality learning experience, for example through the consideration of bandwidth versions and printable outputs of learning resources.

Shireen Yacoub, Chief Operating Officer Edraak, Queen Rania Foundation for Education and Development, Jordan:

“We have taken into consideration challenges related to technology and access, so we usually create low bandwidth versions of video lectures and we sometimes offer transcripts that are printable. As more K–12 and university level courses are hosted in Edraak there is a growing opportunity to enhance learners’ support and curriculum design through the use of online learner data. As such we are opening up our data and launching ‘research.edraak’ to enable research communities and educational researchers to tap into our learner data and use our data analysis tools in order to inform curricular design and learner support.”

Extending practices and building on the work of others, for example Revisita Redes and Open Humanities Press, is recommended to maximize the importance of high quality, critical scholarship.

Teresa McKinnon, Principal Teaching Fellow, Certified Member of the Association for Learning Technology, SFHEA, University of Warwick, UK:

*“What we need to do is capitalize on the expertise which is particularly held in languages, in **online intercultural exchange, and in understanding how computer-mediated communication works, and how we connect with each other and build trust within these networks.** We need to help educators to create their online presence, we need to help connect and follow and engage a wider audience using social media, using webinars both live and recorded. Using video and Creative Commons is actually a very important part of that discussion to help acknowledge contribution and to help value the fact that in so doing we are supporting the community and making a difference. There is much to be gained in terms of mutual understanding if we follow those approaches.”*

5. Licensing of OER content

In this final theme, the use of licenses across the case studies using OER varied. For some, each individual resource was licensed, whilst others did not seem to have a licensing strategy in place. We recommend that those providing OER should **review their licensing approach** and work with their institutions, where possible, to **formulate guidelines for OER creators**, in order to best license their OER. It is of course also essential that the licenses of others are respected and adhered to.

Shireen Yacoub, Chief Operating Officer Edraak, Queen Rania Foundation for Education and Development, Jordan:

“We collaborate with Arab instructors and subject matter experts to create high quality educational content in Arabic in an effort to enrich Arabic content online and to eliminate the language barrier for Arab learners. We have recently adopted the Creative Commons Licence as a default licence for Edraak courses and we’re actively encouraging our partners to do so.”

Summary of Recommendations Arising from the Case Studies

The findings from the case studies have been presented in terms of five key themes within which a number of recommendations are proposed. The recommendations are summarized in order to provide a reference of work to be done for OER and OEP, for example, in relation to considering institutional contributions to the regional agenda and the definition of institutional roadmaps.

Top-Down and Bottom-Up Implementation

- Clarity about the justification for the provision of high-quality OEP and OER in HEIs is required
- Investment in infrastructure will ease process development and ways to transition materials and programmes
- Institutions should organize themselves according to local need
- Piloting course accreditation schemes through institutions may be a useful means of promoting OEP as a reputable form of learning, where national educational authorities do not recognize online education
- Building on and using what is already out there is an important premise of OEP/OER
- Resources are required to support the upskilling of staff

Supporting Staff in Using and Integrating Open Practices and Open Resources

- Staff need to be supported to problem-solve ways to integrate OER with their official academic learning resources
- Staff need to appreciate that openness has to go far beyond making content publicly available
- Staff development needs should be prioritized
- Incentives are required to engage staff
- The effort and focus required for staff to work effectively in a digital world needs to be better acknowledged

Collaborative Creation in Communities of Practice

- A collaborative approach to the creation of OER needs to be adopted
- If the level of expertise is not available in the institution, or if people in the institution are reluctant to adopt OER, OER advocates should collaborate outside of the institution
- The potential of Open Education to have greater impact can be realized when a consortium of institutions collaborate together rather than something happening within just one institution
- Context-related learning resources can help to raise the profile of scholarship occurring in the S–M region to inspire and evoke further sharing, collaboration and social commitment

Enhancing the Quality of Student Learning

- Important opportunities for saving money are achievable through developing non-commercial OER while still using high quality content
- OER can support anytime, anywhere learning, offering new communication models and possibilities between teachers and students
- OEP should engage students as co-creators
- Issues of quality need to be carefully considered and managed
- OER need to be accessible to meet a wide range of learner needs including students with disabilities
- Understanding how computer-mediated communication works, including how we connect with each other and build trust within networks, is required for effective online intercultural exchange

Licensing of OER content

- Those providing OER should review their licensing approach and work with their institutions, where possible, to formulate guidelines for OER creators

Appendices

Appendices

Appendices

The Appendices contain the instruments used to collect the data for this compendium, as well as data collected but ultimately not included in the final compendium. These are:

- Appendix 1: Compendium Methodology
- Appendix 2: OEP Participation Survey
- Appendix 3: Case Study Nomination Form
- Appendix 4: Sample Case Study Template
- Appendix 5: Sample OEP Participation Surveys from European Partner Universities
- Appendix 6: Biographies of Expert Interviewees

Appendix 1: Compendium Methodology

The methodology used to collect the information within this compendium is *descriptive case study*. A case study is a qualitative approach in which the investigator explores a real-life, contemporary bounded system (a case) through detailed, in-depth data collection involving multiple sources of information, and reports a case description and case themes (Creswell, 2013: 97⁸⁹).

The cases are the topic of OE and its practice within higher education institutions in the S–M partner regions and in the EU.

Methods used

OEP Participation survey

Participating HEIs in the OpenMed project were asked to complete an online survey to outline the level of participation in OEP within their institution. The survey results provide a picture of current practice at the time of completion (early 2016) and also identify the future OE goals

⁸⁹ Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (3rd Edition). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

of the participating institutions. The survey questions are available in Appendix 2.

Case studies

All OpenMed partners were invited to nominate relevant initiatives, from their institution or elsewhere, to be considered for inclusion in a collection of OE case studies (the nomination form can be found in Appendix 3). Partners were asked to justify why and how they thought a case study of the nominated initiative could help to advance the adoption of OEP in the S–M region.

The criteria for the selection of case studies was:

1. Potential of the initiative for transferability to other contexts within the South Mediterranean region
2. Extent of the initiative to offer valuable insights into the following aspects:
 - Organizational changes
 - Pedagogical innovations
 - Funding model
 - Strategic planning
 - Incentives for engagement of educators
 - Quality assurance mechanisms
 - Assessment of learning outcomes
 - Certification or accreditation of knowledge
 - Technologies
 - Open licences
 - Response to massification and large class teaching

The case study nominations were reviewed by the Coventry University team and by relevant experts.

The quality assurance mechanism

Prior to collecting the case study nominations, the case study template and the concept note outlining the methodology and methods to be used were reviewed by the OpenMed Quality Assurance Team.

Twelve cases were selected and each partner was asked to complete one detailed case study on a nominated initiative, using the template in Appendix 4. Each of the case studies was reviewed by a different partner institution.

The analysis of ‘Open Education by the Supreme Council of Universities in Egypt’ by Cairo University has been included as part of the detail of Open Education in the Country Report of Egypt. All partners were invited to review the country reports and the drafts of the compendium, and an external review was conducted by Javiera Atenas of University College London.

Expert interviews

Throughout the first half of 2016, a number of experts in open education were asked to comment on relevant initiatives and share recommendations with the aim of facilitating and encouraging the adoption OEP in the S–M region. The experts, who were identified by the OpenMed partners, are from the S–M region, the EU, and from the wider international OE community.

The experts were selected purposefully, as recommended by the OpenMed partners based on their reputation for their particular engagement and practices in OE. The purpose of interviewing experts in the field was to share expertise relevant to the goal of fostering OEP in the S–M region, as such, experts from the S–M region were considered as well as from the EU and internationally.

Each participant recorded a short video (5 minutes max) answering the following questions:

- Please introduce yourself: Who are you and what is your involvement in OE?
- Could you please identify an OE initiative or idea you find interesting and explain why (you might focus on any specific elements of interest)?
- What would be your top tips or recommendations to educators and HE decision makers in the MENA region (you can also decide to focus on a specific country) for facilitating the adoption of OEP? You might offer tips relating to the use and/or creation

of OER, but also any other dimension of open education you consider relevant.

All the recordings of the interviews are available at <http://www.openmedproject.eu>.

Data analysis

Case studies provided in Arabic or French were translated into English. Thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006)⁹⁰ was used to analyse the case study and interview data, led by the OER Research Team.

The analysis focused on how the data collected show the range of challenges and opportunities created by the adoption of OEP at the partners in the S–M region, other universities in each of their respective countries and, more broadly, at other higher education organisations in the Arab World. The analytic process involved a progression from description, where the data are organised to show patterns in content and then summarised, to interpretation, where themes were developed, illustrating the significance of the patterns and their broader meanings and implications.

The analysis process also considered the socio–cultural contexts which support the individual accounts that were provided.

⁹⁰ Braun, V. & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*. 3 (2), 77–101.

Appendix 2: OEP Participation Survey Overview

A profile from each of the partner Universities in the S–M countries outlining the key opportunities and challenges for the adoption of OEP at their respective institutions

- Type of university, mission and funding model
- Date institution established
- Names of faculties / schools
- Number of students at the university (and if possible the breakdown in relation to undergrad, postgrad, PhD, students per faculty, students which will require specific types of OEP, e.g. students with disabilities)
- Number of academic and non–academic staff
- Languages most commonly spoken at the institution
- Types of educational technologies and e–learning programmes and/or courses (i.e. types of offerings of e–learning)
- What are the main opportunities for the adoption of OEP at your university? (if there are any relevant OER initiatives already in place they will be explored in more detail in the next section).
- What are the main challenges for the adoption of OEP at your institution? (if there are any relevant OER initiatives already in place they will be explored in more detail in the next section).

Appendix 3: Case Study Nomination Form

The following form, made available via Google Docs, was used for nominations of case studies.

OpenMed Case Studies Nomination

The OpenMed Compendium will include a collection of case studies analysing initiatives that may work as a source of inspiration and will offer valuable lessons to be taken into account while fostering the adoption of OEP in the S–M region.

Please use the form below to nominate initiatives to be considered for inclusion in the collection of case studies. You might nominate as many initiatives as you wish. Your suggestions do not need to be linked to your institutions.

The deadline for nominating initiatives is the 5th of February of 2016.

*Required

Your name and surname *

Your university/institution *

Name of the initiative you would like to nominate *

e.g. Edraak

URL *

e.g. <https://www.edraak.org/en/>

Type of initiative *

Repository

Policy or strategy for the promotion of open educational practices

MOOC

Other:

Country where the initiative has been developed

Organisation responsible for the initiative

Justification *

Please briefly explain why you think this initiative should be analysed as part of the compendium.

What is the potential of this initiative for transferability to other contexts within the South Mediterranean region?

To what extent can this initiative offer valuable insights into the following aspects?

	Not at all	To some extent	A lot
Organizational changes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pedagogical innovations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Funding model	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Strategic planning	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Incentives for engagement of educators	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Quality assurance mechanisms	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Assessment of learning outcomes

Certification or accreditation of knowledge

Technologies

Open licences

Response to massification and large class teaching

Appendix 4: Sample Case Study Template

OpenMed Case Study Template

In preparing the case study please refer to the concept note that accompanies this document which explains the rationale and process underpinning the development of the case studies. (Please note there is flexibility with the word count suggestions for sections 2 – 4, and an overall suggested maximum word count of 2500).

For examples of case studies used in other OE/OER projects please refer to the OportUnidad compendium.

The completed case study needs to be sent for review with your identified OpenMed reviewer and returned to your CU nominated case study contact by 31st March, 2016.

Thank you for your contributions!

OER Research Team, DMLL, Coventry University, UK

Section 1. Background detail about the initiative

Title of the initiative described by the case study (e.g. CU Open Classes)

Contributor/s of the case study: name of the authors writing the case study (e.g. Katherine Wimpenny, Coventry University)

Data sources used for the case study (e.g. interviews with staff and students, course documentation, university policies on use of OER/OEP, data analytics including statistics on the use of the OE, module / course feedback, photographs/screencaptures, websites, publications, including blogs and tweets, disseminating the project)

Type of initiative
(e.g. OCW platform, MOOC, podcasts, repository of learning objects, journal, policy, strategy)

URL of initiative (e.g. globestrategy.net)

Country

Name of the organisation/institution behind the initiative

Type of organisation: (e.g. university, foundation, public body)

Organisation's webdomain (e.g. www.coventry.ac.uk)

Funding: Who is providing the financial resources (if any) required for the initial development and subsequent functioning of the initiative?

Section 2. Introduction to the case: brief history and goals of the initiative

Description of the initiative analysed by the case study, covering its history, goals and approach. (Recommend approx. 500 words)

Section 3. Key aspects of particular importance

Description of relevant aspects such as institutional policies, key people involved in the design and development of the initiative, underpinning pedagogy, motivations to be involved etc. (Recommend approx. 1500 words)

Authors can decide which aspects from this list are particularly relevant to each case. These are just factors that authors might want to explore, but they are free to ignore or choose to focus on a few of them depending on how relevant they are for each of the initiatives under examination:

Things you may wish to consider:

- Organizational change
- Associated pedagogical innovations, (e.g. Types of learning activities, underlying teaching and learning approach, level of participation of learners, interactivity of the tasks, role of peer-support)
- Funding models
- Strategies and/or policies
- Incentives for educators to contribute
- Quality assurance mechanisms
- Assessment of learning outcomes
- Certification or accreditation of knowledge
- Infrastructure
- Technologies
- Search engine optimization
- Licences (for example, Creative Commons licenses)
- Accessibility for disabled learners
- Diversity and communication adjustments (for example, to ensure intercultural sensitivity and inclusive practices, and respect of all participants, online etiquette)

Section 4. Lessons Learnt and Transferability Opportunities

Including for example, engagement, challenges, successes, key beneficiaries, opportunities for community building, mechanisms for evidencing engagement and/ or achievement of learning. (Recommend approx. 200 words)

Appendix 5: Sample OEP Participation Surveys from European Partner Universities

Coventry University, UK

Coventry University (CovUni) has an established regional, national and international presence, with over 24,000 students in total, 5,000 international students from over 140 different countries, research ventures across the globe, and international business activity. The Disruptive Media Learning Lab is situated on the top floor of the University Library, encouraging and supporting new ways of teaching and learning through digital media.

Definition of Open Education

CovUni does not currently have a formal institutional definition of open education; nor does it have a policy on open education.

Online Teaching and Learning

CovUni runs a number of online-only modules and degrees, as well as blended learning degrees.

The use of open educational resources is supported by departmental learning technologists; in addition, Academic Liaison Librarians are involved in developing OER for their students, and share these resources throughout the community.

CovUni has a YouTube channel⁹¹ and a research blog (CURB)⁹², and also runs several Twitter and Facebook pages which facilitate the sharing of online educational resources.

The institutional LMS used by CovUni is Moodle.

Institutional Resources

CovUni has an institutional repository called CURVE⁹³, which contains research and scholarly publications, open educational resources,

⁹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/user/covstudent>

⁹² <http://blogs.coventry.ac.uk/researchblog/category/homepage/>

⁹³ <http://cuba.coventry.ac.uk/curveresearch/>

and digital library collections. The repository is not completely open access; it contains both university-only collections and fully open-access materials.

CovUni releases online educational content using open licences, and uses CrossRef DOIs to link to digital content created by teaching and research staff. There is support available to assist staff in deciding which CC license is most appropriate for their needs.

Current Practice and Future Goals

There are a number of staff within CovUni who are 'champions' of OER.

University of Seville, Spain

The University of Seville is a 'Public Law' institution, founded in 1505, and is the second biggest Spanish university by number of students. Its academic offering includes more than 78 degrees in Bio-sanitary, Scientific, Technological, Humanistic and Social areas of study; 86 Doctorate programmes, 86 official master's degrees and another 150 master's, Expert and Advanced training courses endorsed by the University of Seville. In addition to this educational offering, the University holds academic and exchange partnerships with 850 institutions throughout the world. More than 2,000 incoming and outgoing exchange students are monitored every year.

Definition of Open Education

The University of Seville (US) states that the highlight of open education within the institution is

... the creation of open access repositories in research, doctoral theses and teaching resources.

US has an institutional declaration which commits to open access to promote

... wider dissemination, accessibility, visibility and impact

of the research and teaching of the university.

Online Teaching and Learning

US has no online-only degree courses.

The default institutional platform for sharing educational resources online is Blackboard. Staff may choose to use another VLE such as Moodle, but if they do so there is no technical support available and they would not be able to connect to student information.

Support and training in the use of open educational resources is provided by the office of audiovisual resources⁹⁴ and the library⁹⁵.

Institutional Resources

US has a research repository (idUS), containing more than 26,000 open access items (research papers, presentations, videos) generated by teaching and research staff⁹⁶, and a separate repository for doctoral dissertations⁹⁷. In addition, US has an OpenCourseWare site⁹⁸ which makes educational materials freely and openly available to all. US has clear guidance for staff who wish to deposit materials into the idUS repository⁹⁹: all idUS content is licensed under a CC Attribution–NonCommercial–NoDerivatives 4.0 International (CC BY–NC–ND 4.0) license¹⁰⁰.

Current Practice and Future Goals

US identified Nieves González, a member of the Library of the University of Seville, as an OER ‘champion’¹⁰¹.

A current and ongoing project in which US is involved (with three other Universities) is the Observatory of Personal Networks

⁹⁴ <http://www.sav.us.es/>

⁹⁵ <http://bib.us.es/>

⁹⁶ <https://idus.us.es/xmlui/>

⁹⁷ <http://fondosdigitales.us.es/tesis/>

⁹⁸ <http://ocwus.us.es/>

⁹⁹ <http://guiasbus.us.es/idus/depositar>

¹⁰⁰ <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>

¹⁰¹ <http://www.nievesglez.com/>

(OPeN)¹⁰² which collects data on personal networks of research in different socio-cultural contexts, which is then made available to other researchers.

Politecnico di Torino, Italy

Established in 1859, Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) is the oldest technical University in Italy. For more than 150 years it has been one of the most prestigious public institutions in Italy for education, research, technological transfer and services in all sectors of architecture and engineering. Ranking among the first twenty European technical Universities, it is recognized worldwide as a high quality centre for education and research.

At POLITO, 900 professors and researchers carry out research and provide education to 30,000 students (20,000 undergraduate and 10,000 postgraduate), of which 5,000 are international students from 100 different countries. At the graduate level, POLITO offers 32 MSc and 12 PhD courses, many of which are in English.

POLITO has been able to reconcile tradition and innovation by being deeply rooted locally and at the same time by establishing itself as an attractive University for students and staff coming to study and work from all over the world. Thanks to the quality of its research and to the tradition of liaising with companies, POLITO ensures students a swift work placement and attracts significant investments and collaborations with blue chip companies.

Definition of Open Education

POLITO has no institutional definition of open education, nor does it have a policy relating to OEP.

Online Teaching and Learning

POLITO does not run any online-only degree courses.

Teaching staff are able to load material such as PDFs and video files to an online repository where they can also interact with students.

¹⁰² <http://centresderecerca.uab.cat/personal-networks/content/open>

Learning Management Systems used within POLITO are Moodle and Chamilo. These platforms, as well as the Open edX platform, are supported by dedicated non-teaching staff.

Educational content is shared via an internal repository for students and staff, and also via a YouTube channel¹⁰³.

Institutional Resources

POLITO has an institutional repository, which is not open access, and is not available to those outside the university. This repository contains research papers and presentations.

POLITO releases educational content under open licenses.

Current Practice and Future Goals

Many POLITO teaching staff are using innovative technology within their teaching practice. Currently, a group of staff are working on developing a MOOC.

Universidad Internacional de la Rioja, Spain

UNIR Research¹⁰⁴, the Research Department of the Universidad Internacional de La Rioja (UNIR)¹⁰⁵ works on selected scientific and humanistic fields of study with particular focus on information and communication technologies (ICT) applied to education (Technology-Enhanced Learning). All of them are designed for practical implementation and subsequent exploitation in the market (i.e. end-user, industry, academia, and public administration). Specific majors are Game-based Learning, Learning Analytics, Recommendation systems, User experience, Community building, Interoperability, Innovation in Education, and University Social Responsibility. UNIR also focusses on exploitation and time-to-market strategies to implement project outcomes.

UNIR provides international courses, in English and Spanish, and comprises an academic community of over 1,000 highly

¹⁰³ <https://www.youtube.com/user/PolITOvideo>

¹⁰⁴ <http://research.unir.net>

¹⁰⁵ <http://www.unir.net>

knowledgeable lecturers across the world, along with a strong team of over 500 multidisciplinary staff members (including 150 tutors), working on R&D projects and support services (i.e. tutoring, legal, publishing, editing, technical, administrative, etc.). Student numbers keep increasing exponentially, reaching over 20,000 in 2015. UNIR has campuses in Spain (Logroño and Madrid), Argentina (Buenos Aires), Bolivia (Santa Cruz), Mexico (Mexico D.F.), and Bogotá (Colombia), along with a large number of collaboration agreements, primarily with Latin American and European universities.

In addition, UNIR Research provides a strong layer of networks such as the UNESCO Chair on eLearning, TELSpain, TELEARC: all of them very much focused on Technology-Enhanced Learning, Educational Innovation, and related work areas. Out of all this activity, UNIR contributes to a number of European R&D projects such as EduMotion, EU-University Social Responsibility, eMundus, Virtual Mobility Passport, Inspiring Science Education, Hotel, Intuitel and Social Seducement.

Definition of Open Education

UNIR does not currently have a formal institutional definition of open education. UNIR's policy with regard to open education has three levels: 1) fully open; 2) open and free registration; and 3) open for registered students.

Online Teaching and Learning

UNIR runs approximately 100 degrees which are online-only.

The use of open educational resources is widely encouraged; all teaching and support staff are aware and involved in the use and development of these resources.

Learning Management Systems used within UNIR are Sakai, Moodle, Blackboard, and Canvas, as well as internally developed systems.

Educational content is shared online via a variety of platforms and repositories, including Sakai, Moodle, Blackboard, Canvas, WordPress, YouTube, and DSpace.

Institutional Resources

UNIR has a completely open access institutional repository, which includes content such as papers, theses, videocasts, podcasts, open lectures, and presentation slides.

UNIR releases content under open licenses through Creative Commons, GNU, GPL and Copy-left.

Current Practice and Future Goals

Current open education projects which UNIR is involved in include: Open Education Factory – from teachers to open educators; MOOC on Emerging Technology for K-12; uR-Tutor – Learning analytics for better learning and better teaching; and uR-Mentor – Personalised recommendations for students.

Appendix 6: Biographies of Expert Interviewees

Tel Amiel, UNESCO Chair in OER at UNICAMP and Researcher at NIED/UNICAMP

Tel Amiel is a researcher at NIED/Unicamp (University of Campinas) and UNESCO Chair in OER. He completed his doctorate in instructional technology (University of Georgia) and was visiting fellow/researcher at the University of Wollongong, Stanford University and Utah State University. He is currently engaged in projects focused on data-based school improvement, understanding organizational barriers to new media use in schools, and promoting open resources and policies in higher education

Maha Bali, Associate Professor of Practice at the Center for Learning & Teaching at the American University in Cairo (AUC).

Maha is a full-time faculty developer and also teaches creative educational game design to undergraduates. Maha is co-founder of virtuallyconnecting.org, and co-founder & co-facilitator of Edcontexts. She is the editor of Hybrid Pedagogy journal and blogger at Prof Hacker. She is also International Director of the Digital Pedagogy Lab. Maha got her PhD in Education from the University of Sheffield in the UK, and believes very strongly in critical/interpretive approaches to social research, especially participatory approaches such as collaborative autoethnography.

Daniel Burgos, Pro–Vice–chancellor for Research & Technology and UNESCO Chair on eLearning at the International University of La Rioja (UNIR).

Daniel leads the research group on eLearning and Social Networks (TEL SOCK). Previously, he worked as Director of Education Sector and Head of User Experience Lab at the Research & Innovation Department of Atos, Spain, since 2007; and as assistant professor at the Open University of The Netherlands, from 2004. His interests are mainly focused on Adaptive and Informal eLearning, Learning & Social Networks, eGames, and eLearning Specifications. He is or has been involved in a number of R&D projects, i.e. Intuitel, VM–Pass, eMundus, Edumotion, Hotel, USR, Inspiring Science Education, Stellar, Gala, IntelLEO, Go–MyLife, Grapple, Telma, GameTEL, Pauta, Unfold, ProLearn, TenCompetence, EU4ALL, NiHao, Kaleidoscope, Suma, Sister, Comeln, et cetera. He holds degrees in Communication (PhD), Computer Science (Dr. Ing), Education (PhD), and Business Administration (BSc).

Cristóbal Cobo (Phd) is Director of the Center for Research – Ceibal Foundation in Uruguay, and also an associate researcher at the Oxford Internet Institute, University of Oxford

Cristóbal coordinates research on innovation, open knowledge initiatives and future of learning research projects. Currently he works on different projects funded by European Commission. Cristobal has been distinguished by the British Council of Economic and Social Research (ESRC) and associate research fellow at the Centre on Skills, Knowledge and Organisational Performance,

University of Oxford. He was Professor and Director of Communication and New Technologies at the Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences, Mexico. He has served as External Evaluator for the Inter-American Development Bank; the National Science Foundation and MIT Press (US), International Labour Organization (UN), and the International Development Research Centre (Canada). Invited Expert for RAND EU in future trends on technology and education commissioned by the Bureau of European Policy Advisors (BEPA). Dr Cobo currently serves on the board of the Global Open Educational Resource (OER) Graduate Network (UNESCO). He has PhD “cum laudem” Communication Sciences at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Co-author of the book *Invisible Learning* (with more than 50,000 downloads). He has been a speaker in more than 30 countries (+ 4 TEDx).

Jean-Claude Guédon, Professor at the Department of Comparative Literature, with focus on Internet Culture, Digital Humanities and Open Access Movement, University of Montreal, Canada

Prof. Jean-Claude Guédon began his career at Glendon College (York University) in Toronto, Ontario in 1970 and has been a Professor at the Université de Montréal since 1973, first in the Institut d’histoire et de sociopolitique des sciences, and, since 1987, in the Département de littérature comparée. He is a long-time member of the Internet Society serving as co-chair of the programme committee in 1996, 1998 and 2000, and member of the same committee in 1997, 1999 and 2002.

Picture by Susanne Christensen (CC BY-SA-NC 2.0)

Sana El Harbi is a Professor of Quantitative Methods at the University of Sousse.

Professor El Harbi initiated the team of Open Education Resources at the University. She involves her students and colleagues in activities and projects that reflect Open Educational Practices. In the last years, her academic interest focuses on the economic value and the business model underpinning OER. In addition, Sana Harbi is a member of the University board and the academic commission at the Higher Education Ministry. She was recently honored as a UNESCO Chair in OER.

Professor Rory McGreal is the UNESCO/ Commonwealth of Learning Chairholder in Open Educational Resources.

Professor McGreal is a professor in the Centre for Distance Education at Athabasca University–Canada’s Open University based in Alberta, Canada. He is also the Director of the Technology Enhanced Knowledge Research Institute (TEKRI). He is a co–Editor of the International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning (IRRODL), and founder of the OER Knowledge Cloud. Formerly, he served as the Associate Vice President Research.

Teresa McKinnon, Principal Teaching Fellow, Certified Member of the Association for Learning Technology, SFHEA, University of Warwick, UK.

Teresa is an award winning language teacher and Certified Member of the Association for Learning Technology. She is experienced in technology enhanced learning design in secondary and higher education. Recent projects include the development of Languages@Warwick, a platform for language

learning. She curates CPD resources for language tutors, is an active advocate of computer-mediated communication and is an Open Educational Practitioner.

Paul Stacey, Associate Director of Global Learning, Senior Project Manager with Creative Commons, US.

Paul helps government, organizations, and businesses around the world adopt Creative Commons based open policy, business models, and practices. Paul excels at facilitating and supporting groups in defining strategies and implementation practices for Creative Commons use. He is an advocate for the Commons as a means of maximizing citizen participation in education and culture and creating a more equitable and sustainable economy. Paul has over 25 years of technology, online learning, and open education experience in both the public and private sectors. Prior to Creative Commons Paul helped found BCCampus and its open education initiative. Paul holds four degrees including an MEd in Adult Learning and Global Change. He lives just outside Vancouver Canada where he enjoys gardening and the Pacific Northwest wilderness.

Peter Suber, Director of the Harvard Office for Scholarly Communication, Director of the Harvard Open Access Project, Senior Researcher at the Berkman Klein Center for Internet & Society, and Senior Researcher at the Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition.

Peter works for the free circulation of knowledge and research in every field and region. In practice that means education, collaboration, research,

writing, tool–building, direct assistance, and pro bono consulting for open access. He wears several hats: Director of the Harvard Office for Scholarly Communication (based in the Harvard Library) Director of the Harvard Open Access Project (based in the Berkman Klein Center); Senior Researcher at the Berkman Klein Center for Internet & Society; and Senior Researcher at the Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition. Peter’s primary field is philosophy (Ph.D., Northwestern University, 1978). He is also a non–practicing lawyer (J.D., Northwestern, 1982).

Shireen Yacoub, Chief Operating Officer Edraak, Queen Rania Foundation for Education and Development, Jordan.

Shireen Yacoub is the Chief Operating Officer of Edraak.org – the first Arab non–profit massive open online platform of the Queen Rania Foundation for Education and Development launched in May 2014 using OpenEdx technology. Shireen also leads Edraak’s partnerships and strategic initiatives including collaborations with local, regional and international universities. Among the strategic initiatives she has spearheaded are Edraak’s first series of employability skills courses developed in collaboration with the Middle East’s number one job search platform, Bayt.com and Edraak’s adoption of the Creative Commons License. Before joining Edraak, Shireen worked on multiple economic development and youth empowerment programmes mainly aimed at bridging the skills gap. She holds a B.A. degree from Manhattanville College in International and Human Resources Management with minors in Communications and French. She is also a certified instructional designer from the Association for Talent Development (ATD)

and has recently received certificates on “Strategic Frameworks for NGOs” from Harvard University Executive Education and “Instructional Design and Blended Learning” from the GeorgetownX Institute of Georgetown University.

Editors

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